

6th Asia-Pacific Conference on **Luminescence**
and Electron Spin Resonance Dating
26-28 September 2022, Ankara, Türkiye, Online

Scientific Program and
Abstract Book

6th Asia-Pacific Conference on Luminescence
and Electron Spin Resonance Dating
26-28 September 2022, Ankara, Türkiye, Online

Online Conference

Dear Colleagues;

It is our pleasure to announce The Sixth Asia-Pacific Conference on Luminescence and Electron Spin Resonance Dating – APLED 2022, which will be held online on 26-28 September 2022, organized by Ankara University.

The theme for the conference is to bring together academic researchers and scientists worldwide. The language of the conference is English. The topics of the conference are:

- Basic physical processes for luminescence dosimetry and dating
- Material characterization for luminescence dosimetry and dating
- Innovative dating and dosimetry approaches
- Advances in dose rate determination
- Instrumentation and procedures
- Luminescence and ESR Dosimetry
- Advances and applications of ESR
- Advanced technologies and methods on luminescence, ESR dosimetry and dating
- Applications in earth and planetary sciences
- Applications in archaeology
- Simulation studies
- Other related topics

We would like to invite you to submit your research article in APLED-2022. The conference includes invited lectures, oral and poster presentations. The presentations will be in sessions covering the conference topics. There will also be Q&A at the end of each session. There will be poster sessions in which a video related to the research can be uploaded.

Proceedings of the APLED-2022 online conference will be published as a Special Issue in Radiation Physics and Chemistry journal by Elsevier, a multidisciplinary journal linking science and industry.

We hope that you take the opportunity to attend our online conference and meet colleagues.

Looking forward to meet in APLED-2022.

**Best Regards,
on behalf of Organising Committee
Eren Şahiner
Conference Chairman**

COMMITTEES

Honorary Committee

Rector	Prof. Dr. Necdet Ünüvar	Ankara University, Türkiye
Vice Rector	Prof. Dr. Mustafa Fener	Ankara University, Türkiye

The International Scientific Advisory Committee

Niyazi Meriç (Emeritus, president)	Ankara University, Türkiye
Eren Şahiner (Chairman)	Ankara University, Türkiye
Georgios S. Polymeris (Co-Chairman)	National Center for Scientific Research “Demokritos”, Greece
Liping Zhou (president of 5th APLED)	Peking University, China
Nigel Spooner (president of 4th APLED)	University of Adelaide, Australia
Shin Toyoda (president of 3th APLED)	Okayama University, Japan
Ashok Kumar Singhvi (president of 2nd APLED)	Physical Research Laboratory, India
Sheng-Hua Li (president of 1st APLED)	University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong
Grzegorz Adamiec	Silesian University of Technology, Poland
Lee Arnold	University of Adelaide, Australia
Constantin Athanassas	National Technical University of Athens, Greece
Ian Bailiff	Durham University, UK
Makaiko L. Chithambo	Rhodes University, South Africa
Jeong-Heon Choi	Korea Basic Science Institute, South Korea
Regina DeWitt	East Carolina University, USA
Steven Forman	Baylor University, Texas, USA
Rainer Grün (Emeritus)	Australian National University, Australia
Mayank Jain	DTU, Denmark
Georgina E. King	University of Lausanne, Switzerland
Dileep Koul	Bhabha Atomic Research Center, India
Ioannis Liritzis	Henan University, China
Sumiko Tsukamoto	Leibniz Institute, Germany
Eduardo Yukihiro	Paul Scherrer Institute, Switzerland

**sorted by last name*

COMMITTEES

Organizing Committee

Eren Şahiner	Ankara University, Türkiye
George Polymeris	National Center for Scientific Research “Demokritos”, Greece
Gaye Özgür Çakal	Ankara University, Türkiye
Şule Kaya Keleş	Ankara University, Türkiye
Engin Aşlar	Ankara University, Türkiye
Yusuf Kağan Kadioğlu	Ankara University, Türkiye
M. Erturaç	Gebze Technical University, Türkiye
Niyazi Meriç (Emeritus)	Ankara University, Türkiye

Conference Secretary

Dr. Eren Şahiner Ankara University, Earth Sciences Application and Research Center, Luminescence Dating Researches Laboratory, Ankara, Türkiye erenshnr@gmail.com	Dr. Gaye Çakal Ankara University, Institute of Nuclear Sciences gayecakal@gmail.com	Dr. George S. Polymeris National Center for Scientific Research Demokritos g.polymeris@inn.demokritos.gr
--	---	--

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

26th September – Monday	
08:30-09:00	Opening ceremony
Session 1: Advanced technologies and methods on luminescence, ESR dosimetry and dating Convenor: Eren Sahiner	
09:00-09:30	Invited Speaker: Bo Li A Bayesian hierarchical model for optical dating of single grains of quartz
09:30-09:50	Furong Cui Comparison of the pulsed blue and green light stimulation in isolating quartz source signal of rock slice by using time-resolved signature
09:50-10:10	Alicja Chruścińska Dose response of the fast OSL component in quartz for doses above 200 Gy
10:10-10:30	Ting Cheng Bleachability of pIRIR signal from single-grain K-feldspar
10:30-10:50	Questions & Answers
Session 2: Applications in earth and planetary sciences Convenor: Shin Toyoda	
10:50-11:20	Invited Speaker: Constantin Athanassas From electron trapping to exhumation tracking
11:20-11:40	Anoop Ambili The Late Holocene climate variability and their impact on cultural dynamics in the central India
11:40-12:00	Shashank Nitundil Increasing our understanding of Holocene dune activity in the Thar Desert, India using a portable luminescence reader
12:00-12:20	Yashi Sui Pulse chronological sequences and surface processes constrained by luminescence of K-feldspar grains: message from the central section of Altyn Tagh Fault
12:20-12:40	Questions & Answers
12:40-13:30	Break
Session 3: Applications in earth and planetary sciences Convenor: Jintang Qin	
13:30-13:50	Mahadev Rawat Palaeoflood records of ~3000 years from the lower reaches of Kaveri and its adjacent River Basins, Tamilnadu, India
13:50-14:10	Kechang Li Single-grain K-feldspar pIRIR Dating of a thick alluvial sequence on northern piedmont of Chinese Tian Shan
14:10-14:30	Vasiliki Kanavou Is TL thermochronometry using low sensitivity quartz from metamorphic rocks feasible? A pioneer case study from phyllite-quartzite assemblages in southern Greece
14:30-14:50	Mehmet Erturaç Investigation of past hydrological extremes (HEX) using river flood plain sediments: Sakarya River, NW Türkiye
14:50-15:20	Invited Speaker: James K. Feathers First People in the Western Hemisphere: The Contribution from Luminescence Dating
15:20-15:40	Questions & Answers
15:40	End of the day

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

27th September – Tuesday

Session 4: Computational and statistical applications

Convenor: Liping Zhou

08:30-09:00	Invited Speaker: Georgios Polymeris Computational and statistical analysis using raw luminescence data
09:00-09:20	Miriam Saleh Parameters of multi-level statistical analysis affecting the OSL ages of mortar samples from Northern Italy
09:20-09:40	Magdalena Biernacka The medium OSL component in quartz measured using the thermally modulated OSL method
09:40-10:00	Efstathios Tsoutsoumanos OTOR application in nano-sized luminophores; the impact of nano-crystallite sizes on the Thermoluminescence glow-curve shape, activation energies and kinetic parameters
10:00-10:20	Questions & Answers

Session 5: Basic physical processes for luminescence dosimetry and dating

Convenor: Georgios Poymeris

10:20-10:40	Volkan Altunal Effect of oxygen vacancies on luminescence characteristics of BeO Ceramics produced by Sol-Gel synthesis technique
10:40-11:00	Chahra-Zed Benkhelifa Study the kinetics of thermally stimulated luminescence and the TL dose-response of dosimeter based on beryllium oxide BeO
11:00-11:20	Veysi Guckan TA-OSL from KMgF ₃ :Eu,Yb,Li dosimeter; comparison with OSL and TL dose responses
11:20-11:40	Monika Devi Post Violet-Infrared Stimulated Luminescence (pVIRSL) Dating using Potassium Feldspars
11:40-12:00	Questions & Answers
12:00-13:30	Break

Session 6: Basic physical processes for luminescence dosimetry and dating

Convenor: Dileep Koul

13:30-14:00	Invited Speaker: Paulramasamy Morthekai Role and nature of Pb in the luminescence emission of feldspars
14:00-14:20	Natalia Pawlak Luminescence centres competition impact on the dose dependence of the OSL signal in quartz
14:20-14:40	Pavlos G. Konstantinidis Correlation between the decays of the NTL signal following isothermal and infrared stimulation in feldspar and apatite samples
14:40-15:00	Caroline Fernandes The effects of heat treatment on the OSL signal in sodium chloride crystals
15:00-15:20	Questions & Answers
15:20	End of the day

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

28th September – Wednesday	
Session 7: Advances in dose rate determination	
Convenor: Grzegorz Adamiec	
09:00-09:20	Loic Martin In which extent field conditions may affect the gamma dose rate evaluation using portable gamma spectrometry?
09:20-09:40	Sonia Tatumi Radiometric characterization of Amazonian sediments
09:40-10:00	Amalia Chambon Determination of NaI(Tl) scintillator calibration factors for field application based on MCNP6 modelling
10:00-10:20	Questions & Answers
Session 8: Luminescence and ESR Dosimetry	
Convenor: Jeong-Heon Choi	
10:20-10:50	Invited Speaker: Mathieu Duval ESR dating of quartz grains: evaluating the uncertainty associated to ESR measurements at low temperature.
10:50-11:10	Alida Timar-Gabor Luminescence and electron spin resonance (ESR) characterisation of quartz from different lithologies of different ages
11:10-11:30	Zuzanna Kabacińska Dating sediments by EPR using Al-h centre: a comparison between the properties of fine (4-11 µm) and coarse (> 63 µm) quartz grains
11:30-11:50	Yasemin Kavas Investigation of dosimetric properties of natural salt minerals by examining them with TL, ESR techniques
11:50-12:10	Şule Kaya-Keleş Determination of the dosimetric properties of boron nitride by TL/OSL techniques
12:10-12:30	Questions & Answers
12:30-13:30	Break
Session 9: Innovative dating and dosimetry approaches & Instrumentation	
Convenor: Makaiko L. Chithambo	
13:30-14:00	Invited Speaker: Georgina E. King Working towards a robust thermochronometer based on the ESR of quartz minerals
14:00-14:20	Myungho Kook A luminescence imaging instrument for rapid in-situ assessment of bleaching depth in rocks
14:20-14:40	Madhusmita Panda OSL retrospective dosimetric investigations of SMD capacitors
14:40-15:00	Levent Aksu Development of domestic irradiator in compliance with ISO4037 standard
15:00-15:20	Jalil Pazhuhish Investigation of dosimetric properties and performance test of AL ₂ O ₃ luminescence dosimeters for diagnostic radiology
15:20-15:50	Questions & Answers
15:50-16:50	Discussion & closing remarks

ABSTRACTS

INVITED SPEAKERS

IS-01. First People in the Western Hemisphere: the Contribution from Luminescence Dating

James K Feathers 2

IS-02. Role and nature of Pb in the luminescence emission of feldspars

Morthekai, P.^{1,2,3*}, Grün, R.², Spooner, N.^{3,4} and Fang, F.⁵ 3

IS-03. From electron trapping to exhumation tracking

Constantin Athanassas 4

IS-04. ESR dating of quartz grains: evaluating the uncertainty associated to ESR measurements at low temperature

Mathieu Duval 5

IS-05. Working towards a robust thermochronometer based on the ESR of quartz minerals

G.E King^{1*}, M. Bartz¹, L. Bossin^{1,2*}, X. Wen¹, S. Tsukamoto³, Y. Li⁴, F. Herman¹, M. Ogata⁵, S. Sueoka⁵ 6

IS-06. A Bayesian hierarchical age model for optical dating of single grains of quartz

Bo Li^{1,2*}, Zenobia Jacobs^{1,2}, Richard G. Roberts^{1,2} 7

IS-07. Computational and statistical analysis using raw stimulated luminescence data

Georgios S. Polymeris..... 8

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

OP-01. The Late Holocene climate variability and their impact on cultural dynamics in the central India

Diptimayee Behera¹, Anoop Ambili¹, Sharmila Bhattacharya¹, Praveen Mishra², Pandurang Sabale³ 10

OP-02. Study the kinetics of thermally stimulated luminescence and the TL dose-response of dosimeter based on beryllium oxide BeO

Benkhelifa Chahrazed^{1,2}, Kharfi Faycal^{1,2} 11

OP-03. Post Violet-Infrared Stimulated Luminescence (pVIRSL) Dating using Potassium Feldspars

Monika Devi^{1,2}, Naveen Chauhan¹, A.K. Singhvi¹..... 12

OP-04. Dating sediments by ESR using Al-h centre: A comparison between the properties of fine (4-11 µm) and coarse (> 63 µm) quartz grains

Zuzanna Kabacińska¹, A. Timar-Gabor^{1,2} 13

OP-05. Luminescence and electron spin resonance (ESR) characterisation of quartz from different lithologies of different ages

Alida Timar-Gabor.^{1,2}, Zuzanna Kabacińska¹, Constantin, D¹, Aditi K. Dave.¹, Ducea, M. N.^{3,4} 14

OP-06. Luminescence centres competition impact on the dose dependence of the OSL signal in quartz

Natalia K. Pawlak¹, Alicja Chruścińska¹ 15

OP-07. Combined ¹⁴C, OSL and ESR dating of representative loess-paleosol sequence from Songnen Plain, Northeast China

Chuanyi Wei¹, Gongming Yin¹, Jinhui Yin¹, Huili Yang¹, Chunru Liu¹, Hao Ji¹ 16

OP-08. Palaeoflood records of ~3000 years from the lower reaches of Kaveri and its adjacent River Basins, Tamilnadu, India.

Mahadev Rawat¹, Manoj Kumar Jaiswal², and Atul Kumar Singh¹..... 17

OP-09. In which extent field conditions may affect the gamma dose rate evaluation using portable gamma spectrometry?

Loic Martin¹, Mathieu Duval² 18

OP-10. The medium OSL component in quartz measured using the thermally modulated OSL method

Magdalena Biernacka¹, Alicja Chruścińska, P. Palczewski 19

OP-11. OSL retrospective dosimetric investigations of SMD capacitors

Madhusmita Panda¹, Shailesh Joshi¹, O. Annalaskhmi^{1,2}, Venkata Srinivas C^{1,2} 20

OP-12. Single-grain K-feldspar PIRIR Dating of a thick alluvial sequence on northern piedmont of Chinese Tian Shan

Kechang Li¹, Jintang Qin², Jie Chen³ 21

ABSTRACTS

OP-13. High-resolution chronological sequences and surface processes constrained by luminescence of K-feldspar grains: message from the central section of Altyn Tagh Fault	
<u>Yashi Sui</u> ¹ , <u>Kechang Li</u> ¹ , <u>Jintang Qin</u> ¹ , <u>Zhaode Yuan</u> ¹ , <u>Qi Liu</u> ¹ , <u>Jie Chen</u> ¹	22
OP-14. Comparison of the pulsed blue and green light stimulation in isolating quartz source signal of rock slice by using time-resolved signature	
<u>Furong Cui</u> ^{1,2} , <u>Jintang Qin</u> ¹ , <u>Jinfeng Liu</u> ¹ , <u>Huili Yang</u> ¹	23
OP-15. Dose response of the fast OSL component in quartz for doses above 200 Gy	
<u>Alicja Chruścińska</u> ¹ , <u>P. Palczewski</u> ¹	24
OP-16. Parameters of multi-level statistical analysis affecting the OSL ages of mortar samples from Northern Italy	
<u>M.Saleh</u> ^{1*} , <u>G.S. Polymeris</u> ² , <u>L. Panzeri</u> ¹ , <u>E. Tsoutsoumanos</u> ^{2,3} , <u>G. Ricci</u> ^{4,5} , <u>M. Secco</u> ^{5,6} , <u>G. Artioli</u> ^{4,5} , <u>S. Dilaria</u> ^{5,6} , <u>M. Martini</u> ¹ , <u>A. Galli</u> ¹	25
OP-17. Correlation between the decays of the NTL signal following isothermal and infrared stimulation in feldspar and apatite samples.	
<u>Pavlos G. Konstantinidis</u> ^{1*} , <u>V. Giannoulou</u> ¹ , <u>E. Tsoutsoumanos</u> ^{2,3} , <u>G.S. Polymeris</u> ³ , <u>G. Kitis</u> ¹	27
OP-18. Effect of oxygen vacancies on luminescence characteristics of BeO Ceramics produced by Sol-Gel synthesis technique	
<u>Volkan Altunal</u> , <u>Veysi Güçkan</u> , <u>Zehra Yenigil</u>	28
OP-19. The effects of heat treatment on the OSL signal in sodium chloride crystals	
<u>Caroline Fernandes</u> ¹ , <u>Rocca, R. R.</u> ¹	29
OP-20. TA-OSL from KMgF₃:Eu,Yb,Li dosimeter; comparison with OSL and TL dose responses	
<u>Veysi Güçkan</u> ¹ , <u>Volkan Altunal</u> ¹ , <u>Adnan Özdemir</u> ² , <u>Zehra Yenigil</u> ¹ , <u>George Kitis</u> ³ , <u>George Polymeris</u> ⁴	30
OP-21. Is TL thermochronometry using low sensitivity quartz from metamorphic rocks feasible? A pioneer case study from phyllite-quartzite assemblages in southern Greece	
<u>V. Kanavou</u> ¹ , <u>G.S. Polymeris</u> ² , <u>C.D. Athanassas</u> ¹ , <u>K. Stamoulis</u> ³ , <u>V. Mouslopoulou</u> ⁴ , <u>X. Aslanoglou</u> ⁵	31
OP-22. Investigation of dosimetric properties of natural salt minerals by examining them with TL, ESR techniques	
<u>Yasemin Kavas</u> , <u>Eren Şahiner</u>	32
OP-23. Investigation Of Dosimetric Properties and Performance Test Of Al₂O₃ Luminescence Dosimeters For Diagnostic Radiology Energy Range	
<u>Jalil Pazhuhish</u> ¹ , <u>Eren Şahiner</u> ¹	33
OP-24. Determination of the dosimetric properties of boron nitride by TL/OSL techniques	
<u>Hakan Çağan Öztoprak</u> ¹ , <u>Gaye Özgür Çakal</u> ¹ , <u>Şule Kaya-Keleş</u> ¹ , <u>Eren Şahiner</u> ¹ , <u>Georgios S. Polymeris</u> ²	34
OP-25. Development of domestic irradiator in compliance with ISO4037 standard	
<u>Levent Aksu</u> ¹ , <u>Ergun Togay</u> ²	35
OP-26. Radiometric characterization of Amazonian sediments	
<u>Sonia H. Tatumi</u> ^{1*} , <u>Márcio Yee</u> ¹ , <u>Emílio A.A. Soares</u> ² , <u>Jefferson J. de Souza</u> ² , <u>Emanuele D.O. Grudzin</u> ¹ , <u>René R. Rocca</u> ¹ , <u>Carolina P. Fernandes</u> ¹ , <u>Matheus T. Mathias</u> ¹ , <u>Nagabhushana K.R.</u> ¹ , <u>Marcelo S. Rocha</u> ² , <u>Luis A.C. Lopez</u> ² , <u>Diego W.P. Venâncio</u> ² , <u>Solange dos S. Costa</u> ² , <u>Casimiro S. Munita</u> ³ , <u>Rogério B. Ribeiro</u> ³	36
OP-27. Determination of NaI(Tl) scintillator calibration factors for field application based on MCNP6 modelling	
<u>Amalia Chambon</u> ^{1*} , <u>E. B. Klinkby</u> ¹ , <u>M. Bu</u> ¹ , <u>A. S. Murray</u> ² , <u>M. Kook</u> ¹ , <u>H. Olesen</u> ¹ , <u>K. B. Nielsen</u> ¹	37
OP-28. Increasing our understanding of Holocene dune activity in the Thar Desert, India using a portable luminescence reader	
<u>Shashank Nitundil</u> ^{1*} , <u>Abi Stone</u> ¹ , <u>Aayush Srivastava</u> ² , <u>Tim Kinnaird</u> ² , <u>Komal Songara</u> ³	38
OP-29. OTR application in nano-sized luminophores; the impact of nano-crystallite sizes on the Thermoluminescence glow-curve shape, activation energies and kinetic parameters.	
<u>Efstathios Tsoutsoumanos</u> ^{1,2,*} , <u>M. Saleh</u> ³ , <u>P.G. Konstantinidis</u> ⁴ , <u>V. Altunal</u> ⁶ , <u>P.D. Sahare</u> ⁵ , <u>Z. Yengigil</u> ⁶ , <u>T. Karakasidis</u> ¹ , <u>G. Kitis</u> ⁴ , <u>G.S. Polymeris</u> ²	39

ABSTRACTS

OP-30. A luminescence imaging instrument for rapid <i>in-situ</i> assessment of bleaching depth in rocks Myungho Kook ^{1*} , Elaine Louise Sellwood ¹ , Mayank Jain ¹	40
OP-31. Investigation of past hydrological extremes (HEX) using river flood plain sediments: Sakarya River, NW Türkiye Hilal Okur, Mehmet Korhan Erturaç, Meltem Çelen, Eren Şahiner, Zeki Bora Ön, Nesibe Köse, Sena Akçer-Ön, Özlem Makaroğlu, Nurgül Karloğlu-Kılıç, Hüseyin Tuncay Güner, Emrah Bulut, Fatma Küçük, Burçin Aşkırm Gümüş, Alper Gürbüz, Mehmet Salim Öncel	41
PP-01. Firing temperature estimation of archeological burned materials using sensitivity change of OSL optically stimulated luminescence Yorinao Shitaoka ¹ , Yasuhiro Takai ² , Ken'ichi Kobayashi ³	43
PP-02. Evaluation of the ESR intensity associated to the Al centre measured in optically bleached coarse quartz grains: a comparative study Ben Arous, E. ^{1,2,3} , Duttine, M. ⁴ , Duval, M. ^{2,5}	44
PP-03. Testing infrared radiofluorescence dating on polymineral fine-grains from the Luochuan loess-palaeosol sequence, Chinese Loess Plateau. Gwynlyn Buchanan ¹ , Tsukamoto, S. ¹ , Zhang, J. ¹ , Long, H. ²	45
PP-04. An empirical study on the variability of luminescence ages for coeval loess samples Constantin, D. ^{1*} , Begy, R. ^{1,4} , Vandenberghe, D.A.G.J. ² , Veres, D. ³ , Timar-Gabor, A. ^{1,4}	46
PP-05. Different Fitting Functions And Its Implications For Equivalent Dose Determination In Multiple Centers ESR Dating: A Case Study In Jiangnan Basin, Middle Yangtze River, Central China Yawei Li ^{1,2*} , Chuanyi Wei ^{2*} , Changan Li ³ , Chunru Liu ² , Rujun Guo ³	47
PP-06. Luminescence sensitivity of quartz, a tracer for aeolian transport? An example from the Ili Basin of SE Kazakhstan Aditi K. Dave ^{1,2*} , Saida Nigmatova ⁴ , Kathryn E. Fitzsimmons ^{1,2}	48
PP-07. ESR signals in recrystallized carbonates and their suitability for dating Hao Ji ¹ , Chunru Liu ¹ , Peiquan Zhang ² , Chuanyi Wei ¹ , Gongming Yin ¹	49
PP-08. Provenance analysis of muds with luminescence properties Kento Yokoo ^{1*} , Toru Tamura ²	50
PP-09. Investigation on radiation-induced radicals in primary alkylamines in silica clathrates Nobuyuki Tamai ^{1*} , Shusuke Isogai ² , Yuka Yokoyama ² , Atsushi Tani ^{2†}	51
PP-10. Estimation of ESR age of chibaite using organic radicals Shusuke Isogai ^{1*} , Yuka Yokoyama ¹ , Kenta Kusuki ¹ , Hirotsugu Nishido ² , Atsushi Tani ¹	52
PP-11. Feldspar pIRIR dating for defining depositional sequences in an uplifted coast since the Middle Pleistocene, eastern Japan Tamura T. ^{1,2,3*} , Okazaki, H. ⁴ , Naya, T. ¹ , Nakashima, R. ¹ , Nakazato, H. ⁵ , Seike, K. ¹ , Okuno, J. ⁶	53
PP-12. Cross-shore and longshore variations in residual doses of modern K-feldspar sands in the Kujukuri coast, central Japan Kotaro Komori ^{1*} , Koji Seike ² , Toru Tamura ²	54
PP-13 Luminescence chronology of point bars and their utilisation in Past discharge estimation in the Southern West Bengal Dr. Manoj Kumar Jaiswal	55
PP-14. Interdisciplinary analysis of bricks from Royal Castle in Poznań (Poland) Małgorzata Mrozek-Wysocka ¹ , Piotr Moska ² , Danuta Michalska ¹	56
PP-15. Kinetic analysis of the thermoluminescent glow curve of aquamarine (Be₃Al₂(SiO₃)₆) Rafael Cogollo ^{1*} , Jorge Herrera C ¹ , Omar D. Gutiérrez ²	57
PP-16. Effective Mineral Extraction: A note on improving heavy liquid density separation during sample preparation in Trapped Charge Dating Gloria I. López ^{1,2,3*}	58

ABSTRACTS

PP-17. Thermoluminescence characterization of Cu or Ag doped Lithium Triborate <u>Lois Sevastidis</u> ^{1*} , S. Iflazoglu ^{2,3} , P.G. Konstantinidis ¹ , A. Yilmaz ² , G. Kitis ¹ , G.S. Polymeris ⁴	59
PP-18. Late Quaternary evolution of the Belan River Basin, Central India <u>S. Singh</u> ^{1,2*} , Mahadev ¹ , B. Narzary ¹ , V. Shivsagar ¹ , M.K. Jaiswal ¹ , P. Singh ³	60
PP-19. Secondary electron equilibrium revisited: when doses are given by photons <u>Shin Toyoda</u> ^{1*} , Ulku Sayin ² , Emel Ece ³ , Naoya Obata ⁴	61
PP-20. Optical bleaching and thermal annealing of the ESR signals in quartz <u>Naoya Obata</u> ^{1*} , Shin Toyoda ²	62
PP-21. Late Quaternary evolution of alluvial fans in Northern Tripura, India <u>Ria Kar</u> ^{1*} , Manoj K. Jaiswal ²	63
PP-22. Luminescence dating of neotectonic activity on the foothills of the Assam- Bhutan Himalaya, India <u>Belligraham Narzary</u> ¹ , Saurabh Singh ² , Manoj Jaiswal ¹ , Vibhuti Shivsagar ¹ , Mahadev Rawat ³ , Atul Singh ³	64
PP-23. Kinetic analysis of the glow curve of α-Al₂O₃ <u>Rafael Cogollo Pitalua</u> ^{1*} , Yulissa Espitia ¹ , Omar D. Gutiérrez ²	65
PP-24. Fitting supralinear dose responses using non-empirical expressions; optimization using two computing environments <u>Konstantina Prevezanou</u> ^{1*} , G. Kioselaki ¹ , P.G. Konstantinidis ¹ , E. Tsoutsoumanos ^{2,3} , G.S. Polymeris ³ , V. Pagonis ⁴ , G. Kitis ¹	66
PP-25. Python in stimulated luminescence: a further step in dose response fitting <u>Georgia Kioselaki</u> ^{1,*} , K. Prevezanou ¹ , P.G. Konstantinidis ¹ , E. Tsoutsoumanos ^{2,3} , G.S. Polymeris ³ , G. Kitis ¹ , V. Pagonis ⁴	67
PP-26. Simulation study of a nanomaterial interacting with ionizing radiation using OTOR and IMTS for different grain sizes <u>Efstathios Tsoutsoumanos</u> ^{1,2,*} , T. Karakasidis ¹ , P.G. Konstantinidis ³ , G.S. Polymeris ² , V. Pagonis ⁴ , G. Kitis ³	68
PP-27. Characterisation of grain extractions from Brazilian sand sediments using FT-IR, XRD, SEM/EDS, and ESR Methods <u>Rogério Baria</u> ^{1*} , Shiguo, W. ¹ Chubaci, J. F. D. ² , Cano, N. ³ , Gennari, R. F. ²	69
PP-28. Quartz OSL dating of loess deposits from the eastern margin of the Tibetan Plateau <u>Shengli Yang</u> ^{1*} , Li Liu ¹ , Xiaojing Liu ¹ , Pushuang Li ¹ , Qiong Li ¹	70
PP-29. New insights on ESR dating of siliceous sinter and travertine outcrops on Tibet Plateau and its information for geothermal history <u>Sheng Wang</u> ^{1,2,3} , Tongyan Lü ^{2,3*} , Zhonghai Wu ^{2,3}	71

Online Conference

September 26th-28th, 2022 - Online

INVITED SPEAKERS

IS-01. First People in the Western Hemisphere: the Contribution from Luminescence Dating

James K Feathers

University of Washington, USA

The initial migration of people to the Western Hemisphere has been a contentious subject in American archaeology for more than 100 years. Although most scholars believe the first people in the Americas originated from northeast Asia, the questions of when they first arrived, what route they took, and what they did once they arrived have not produced any consensus. An early consensus that Clovis sites, dated to about 13.5 ka, represented the first Americans has given way to a widely held view that the first migration dates earlier, to about 16ka. That view in turn is being challenged by purported earlier sites dating more than 20 ka.

Any site that may have bearing on this issue is subject to intense scrutiny and is required to meet at least three criteria. First, the artifacts must be unambiguous. Second, the site must have stratigraphic integrity with minimal post-depositional mixing. Third, the site must be well dated by radiometric means.

Luminescence dating is well suited to address the last two criteria. Not only have methods for dating sediments been increasingly improved over the last 20 or so years, but the advent of single-grain dating has allowed issues of stratigraphic integrity to be addressed. Luminescence has thus been employed at a number of early sites, mostly in Alaska, the southeastern United States, and South America, particularly Brazil.

This talk reviews these applications and introduces some new dating by our laboratory in Brazil that support occupation earlier than 20 ka.

IS-02. Role and nature of Pb in the luminescence emission of feldspars

Morthekai, P.^{1,2,3*}, Grün, R.², Spooner, N.^{3,4} and Fang, F.⁵

¹*Birbal Sahni Institute of Palaeosciences, 53 University Road, Lucknow - 226 007, India.*

²*Australian Research Centre for Human Evolution, Griffith University, Brisbane, QLD - 4111, Australia.*

³*Institute of Photonics and Advanced Scanning, The University of Adelaide, Adelaide, SA - 5005, Australia.*

⁴*Defence Science & Technology Group, PO Box 1500, Edinburgh, SA - 5111, Australia.*

⁵*Research School of Earth Sciences, Australian National University, Canberra, ACT - 2601, Australia.*

A comprehensive understanding of the luminescence characteristics of feldspars has been obtained in recent years. However, we have little knowledge of the charge trapping centres in feldspars. In this study we attempt to test the role of Pb in the luminescence emission in feldspars, i.e. whether Pb is playing a role of electron or hole trapping. Pb may be involved in its single ionic state (Pb^+) or associated with other ions ($[\text{Pb-Pb}]^{3+}$, $\text{Pb-O}^{\text{I-X}}$).

Nine feldspar specimens of different composition and order were chosen for this study in addition to Pb doped KCl powder. Both Q-band and X-band ESR (Bruker Eleksys E580) spectra of annealed feldspars (< 150 mm) were recorded at room temperature before and after gamma irradiation (~5000 Gy). Most of the K-feldspar specimens exhibited microwave energy absorption at a g-value of 2.02 with two satellite absorptions at either side (2.07 and 1.97). Considering the width of the main microwave energy absorption peak and the distance between the peaks in absorption spectra, this can be attributed to a hole trapping centre, $\text{Pb-O}^{\text{I-X}}$ (Marfunin and Bershov, 1970, Speit and Lehmann, 1982).

Radiofluorescence (RL) spectra (200 - 1100 nm) were measured on these feldspar specimens using a CCD system (Princeton Instruments PIXIS:256, with SpectraPro 2300i spectrograph, Roper Scientific, USA) and a 1.85 MBq $\text{Sr}^{90}/\text{Y}^{90}$ b-source. The spectra showed decreasing intensities at 870 nm and 920 nm emissions (Pb^+ emission) after b-irradiation. However, there was a subsequent increase in a peak at 280 nm, which is generally attributed to Pb^{2+} emission. The decrease of Pb^+ emission and a subsequent increase of Pb^{2+} emission during b-irradiation suggest that Pb^{2+} ions receive electrons and become Pb^+ . If this interpretation is correct, Pb is an electron trapping centre in its single ionic nature. Petrov et al. (1993) suggested that it was not possible for Pb^+ to be an isolated ion, instead they proposed a dimer centre $[\text{Pb-Pb}]^{3+}$ where an electron is trapped in between two adjacent Pb divalent ions. However, our ESR measurements suggest that Pb is playing the role of a hole trapping centre where Pb is associated with oxygen and a small divalent ion X. On behalf of the authors, I (P. Morthekai), shall present the experimental data we obtained and discuss the role and association of Pb in the form among the following Pb^+ , $[\text{Pb-Pb}]^{3+}$ and $\text{Pb-O}^{\text{I-X}}$.

References

- [1] Speit, B. and Lehmann, G., 1982. Radiation defects in feldspars. *Physics and Chemistry of Minerals* 8, 77 - 82.
- [2] Marfunin, A. S. and Bershov, L. V., 1970. Paramagnetic centers in feldspar and their possible crystallochemical and petrologic significance (in Russian). *Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR* 193, 412-414.
- [3] Petrov, I., Mineeva, R. M., Bershov, L. V. and Agel, A., 1993. EPR of $[\text{Pb-Pb}]^{3+}$ mixed valence pairs in amazonite-type microcline. *American Mineralogist* 78, 500 - 510.

IS-03. From electron trapping to exhumation tracking

Constantin Athanassas

National Technical University of Athens, Greece

Probing the thermal structure of the Earth's upper continental crust in exhuming terrains requires understanding the relationships between time, depth and temperature. Tectonic exhumation involves ductile thinning of the crust, mainly due to tensile faulting which lifts footwall rocks towards the surface. Erosion accounts for far more exhumation than tectonic mechanisms alone, and is an important agent of crustal cooling in both tectonically active and inactive areas. Some of the principles that govern solid-state diffusion of species in minerals are also used for understanding the diffusion of heat in the crust. As the half-life of trapped charge in metastable states within crystalline minerals depends on the ambient temperature, the thermoluminescence (TL) signal may reveal information about a rock's thermal history. Metamorphic rock complexes are exhumed from beneath overlying unmetamorphosed rocks, and have gone through the operation of pressure and temperature over time. In rapidly exhuming terrains, the thermoluminescence (TL) closure ages of metamorphic quartz represent the duration of steady accumulation of electric charge following an episode of fast cooling from high to low temperatures where little signal loss occurs. A wide variety of approaches are available for modeling the thermal structure of the crust and the thermal histories of rocks, including end-user computer applications intended for use with the data.

IS-04. ESR dating of quartz grains: evaluating the uncertainty associated to ESR measurements at low temperature

Mathieu Duval

Centro Nacional de investigación sobre la Evolución Humana (CENIEH). Paseo de Atapuerca, 3, 09002 Burgos, Spain. mathieu.duval@cenieh.es

While ESR dating of quartz has progressively become quite a popular application in Quaternary sciences over the last couple of decades, as attested by the increasing number of dedicated laboratories and research groups around the world, there are still no unified or standardised measurement procedures within the ESR community. Quartz differs from other materials typically measured by ESR (e.g., tooth enamel, carbonates, alanine), in the sense that it has never been subject to any interlaboratory comparisons, and ESR measurements are significantly more challenging due to nature of the material, its heterogeneity and the experimental conditions involved. In particular, radiation-induced signals used for dating purpose are only visible at cryogenic temperature. The truth is that each laboratory uses its own analytical procedure, and there is no general consensus at a community level about the best laboratory practices for the ESR measurements at low temperature. For example, there is a significant variability as far as equipment used, measurement temperatures employed, experimental conditions or even how the ESR intensities are measured. This variability makes it extremely complicated, or even impossible, to directly compare results obtained from different laboratories. As a result, the true uncertainty associated to ESR measurements is currently unknown.

In this talk, I will try to provide some initial insights into this uncertainty, with an overview our methodological investigations carried out at CENIEH over the last decade. We have been specifically aiming to identify the various sources of uncertainty involved in the ESR measurements of quartz, and quantify their potential impact on data outputs. These sources of uncertainty are mostly related to (i) the experimental conditions (e.g., experimental setup, acquisition parameters, measurement temperature), (ii) the sample itself (e.g., homogeneity, variability of the ESR spectra), (iii) or the data reduction process (e.g., measurement of ESR intensities, baseline correction, signal to noise ratio). A special emphasis will be given to measurement repeatability, and about the importance of carrying out repeated measurements of a given sample.

Acknowledgments: This work would not have been possible without the input and feedback from all the staff, students and researchers working in the laboratory over the last 15 years, with a special mention to V. Guilarte, M.J. Alonso Escarza, M. Bartz, M. del Val and E. Ben Arous.

IS-05. Working towards a robust thermochronometer based on the ESR of quartz minerals

G.E King^{1*}, M. Bartz¹, L. Bossin^{1,2*}, X. Wen¹, S. Tsukamoto³, Y. Li⁴, F. Herman¹, M. Ogata⁵, S. Sueoka⁵

¹*Institute of Earth Surface Dynamics, University of Lausanne, Switzerland.*

²*Paul Scherrer Institute, Villigen, Switzerland.*

³*Leibniz Institute for Applied Geophysics, Hanover, Germany.*

⁴*School of Ocean Science, China University of Geosciences, 100083 Beijing, China.*

⁵*Tono Geoscience Center, Japan Atomic Energy Agency, Toki, Japan.*

*Corresponding author; Email: georgina.king@unil.ch; Telephone: +41 21 692 35 33

Electron spin resonance dating of quartz minerals offers a significant advantage over luminescence dating because of its later signal saturation. We are seeking to exploit this to build upon earlier studies (e.g. Scherrer, 1993) in the development of a routine thermochronometry system capable of resolving rock cooling rates throughout the Quaternary. Whereas the luminescence thermochronometry system is limited to areas experiencing very rapid rock cooling (exhumation) of 10s of mm/yr, preliminary data (King et al., 2020) indicate that ESR thermochronometry could resolve rates of <1 mm/yr over Quaternary timescales.

In order to determine a rock cooling history, it is necessary to constrain both signal accumulation and signal thermal loss robustly within the laboratory. We have collected a series of geological samples including rocks from boreholes that have known isothermal histories to investigate the potential of this technique. Our objective is to use the latter rocks to confirm the validity of our laboratory measurements and data-fitting/numerical models. Specifically, we have investigated known-thermal history samples from the MIZ1 borehole (Japan) and the KTB borehole (Germany).

Preliminary data reveal that the ESR dose response and thermal decay of different quartz samples is highly variable. Whereas the Al-centre of some samples exhibits linear dose response to laboratory irradiation up to 15 kGy, the Al-centre of other samples exhibits exponential, or double-exponential growth and saturates at doses of 3-4 kGy. The Ti-centre of most samples is well described by a single saturating exponential function, however samples from the MIZ1 borehole exhibit pronounced sub-linearity in the low-dose response region. Furthermore, whereas for some samples the Al-centre is less thermally stable than the Ti-centre, for other samples the inverse is observed. These observations suggest that a uniform measurement protocol and data-fitting approach may not be appropriate for quartz ESR data.

Inversion of two KTB samples yielded temperatures within uncertainty of borehole temperature, however results for the MIZ1 borehole are more variable and can only recover temperature at best within ~10%. Investigations into the cause of the poor results for the MIZ1 borehole are ongoing (i.e. measurement protocol, data-fitting/numerical model) and will be discussed.

References

- [1] Scherer, T., Agel, A., and Hafner S. S.: Determination of uplift rates using ESR investigations of quartz, KTB Rep. 93-2. Kontinentales Tiefbohrprogramm der Bundesrepublik Deutschland Niedersächs. Landesamt Bodenforsch., Hannover, 121–124, 1993.
- [2] King, G.E., Tsukamoto, S., Herman, F., Biswas, R.H., Sueoka, S., Tagami, T. Electron spin resonance (ESR) thermochronometry of the Hida range of the Japanese Alps: validation and future potential. *Geochronology* 2, no. 1 (2020): 1-15.

IS-06. A Bayesian hierarchical age model for optical dating of single grains of quartz

Bo Li^{1,2*}, Zenobia Jacobs^{1,2}, Richard G. Roberts^{1,2}

¹ Centre for Archaeological Science, School of Earth, Atmospheric and Life Sciences, University of Wollongong, Wollongong, NSW 2522, Australia

² ARC Centre of Excellence for Australian Biodiversity and Heritage, University of Wollongong, Wollongong, NSW 2522, Australia

*Corresponding author: bli@uow.edu.au

In optical dating, the last time that a sample of sediment was exposed to sunlight is determined by dividing its equivalent dose (D_e) by the dose rate. For single-grain dating, the sample D_e is based on the statistical analysis of the distribution of D_e values estimated for individual grains, whereas the dose rate is usually determined from measurements of the environmental radioactivity of the bulk sample, together with allowances for radiation sources internal to the grains and cosmic rays.

Conventionally, the D_e and dose rate are measured and analysed separately to produce an estimate of the depositional age of a sample, but this approach may result in loss of information because distributions of single-grain D_e values are influenced by several factors. Existing statistical models do not incorporate all the key information contributing to age estimation, such as the pattern and scale of dispersion of single-grain D_e values and dose rates, the associated measurement uncertainties, the effect of natural variability among grains, and the outlier probabilities of D_e and dose rate estimates.

Here we propose a Bayesian hierarchical age model (BHAM) for optical dating of quartz samples that incorporates the above information to estimate their depositional ages. The BHAM is based on the implementation of standardised growth curve and $L_n T_n$ methods to integrate information on the full distribution of single-grain D_e values, sources of measurement uncertainty, beta-dose heterogeneity (observed or modelled), and detection of outliers. We present the results of validation tests using data sets of OSL measurements and dose rates obtained for quartz samples dated previously from Denisova Cave (Russia) and for simulated samples. We conclude that the BHAM represents a robust and flexible approach to dealing with data for single grains of quartz within a Bayesian hierarchical framework, and is suitable for application to sediments deposited in a variety of depositional settings, including those affected by insufficient bleaching or post-depositional disturbance.

IS-07. Computational and statistical analysis using raw stimulated luminescence data

Georgios S. Polymeris

Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, National Centre for Scientific Research "Demokritos", Athens, Greece

Thermoluminescence (TL) and its counterpart, Optically Stimulated luminescence (OSL) have both been applied to progressively more geoarchaeological applications. While the new available instrumentation in stimulated luminescence dating and dosimetry provides with a plethora of advances as well as alternatives, interpretation of the results is still a challenging task. The use of instrumentation with technological features such as spatially resolved measurements, allows measuring alternative as well as innovative luminescence signals, such as TA – OSL and IRPL, in excellent alignment with the current need for luminescence age limit's extension effort internationally. Thanks to this new instrumentation advances, luminescence measurements become both more complicated as well as more numerous, making thus the role of analysis decisive. The present talk will attempt to present implementation more robust either signal or statistical analysis routines, by applying the latest trends in information technology and computer science. The R-package software has been extremely helpful on the statistical analysis of the calculated (equivalent) doses. Nevertheless, major information is included within the original, raw signals of either TL or OSL curves. Special emphasis will be given to the analysis of the rudimentary luminescence signals, namely TL glow curves as well as OSL decaying curves of any type. Building up on the knowledge, experience and precision that has developed over the last years, the luminescence community should fully comprehend the importance of the signal analysis. New signal analysis tools will be presented, including deconvolution models and fitting algorithms, along with new analysis software tools. Examples of (a) inefficient as well as physically meaningless deconvolution approaches and (b) modelling of stimulated luminescence signals using either numerical simulations will be given. Finally, a preliminary discussion on the possibility of applying statistical based machine learning methodologies based solely on the raw (TL or OSL) signals will be conducted.

September 26th-28th, 2022 - Online

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

OP-01. The Late Holocene climate variability and their impact on cultural dynamics in the central India

Diptimayee Behera¹, Anoop Ambili¹, Sharmila Bhattacharya¹, Praveen Mishra², Pandurang Sabale³

¹ Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Mohali, India

² Wadia Institute of Himalayan Geology, India

³ Deccan College, India

The understanding of long-term climate variability may provide valuable perspective on possible response of human societies to modern climate changes. The present study, based on the geochemical and sedimentological analyses on well dated (using AMS 14C and optically stimulated luminescence-OSL dates) fluvial deposits alluvial sediments from Sina River (in Maharashtra, central India) provides a detailed understanding of complex interplay between climate and cultural dynamics during the Late Holocene. The radiocarbon dates of the organic residues from the potsherds represents the Medieval period (~1600 to 950 cal yr BP), whereas the OSL sample shows the age of $\sim 7.5 \pm 0.4$ ka. Further, several cultural objects (e.g., potsherds, shell bangles, and copper artefacts) available at the site were also investigated in order to understand the extent of human activity in the region. The temporal changes in the proxies along with the abundance of cultural materials in the fluvial section during the medieval period suggest that the human population attempted to adapt against the fluctuating climate conditions. The regional comparison of geoarchaeological data sets shows that the pronounced weakening of the monsoonal rainfall during the Late Holocene coincides with the disruption, migration and resettlement of the indigenous societies, deciphering the possible impact of climate on human settlement.

Keywords: Indian summer monsoon; Late Holocene; Culture-climate dynamics; Fluvial archives; Geochemical proxies

OP-02. Study the kinetics of thermally stimulated luminescence and the TL dose-response of dosimeter based on beryllium oxide BeO

Benkhelifa Chahrazed^{1,2}, Kharfi Faycal^{1,2}

¹*Department of physics, University of Ferhat Abbas-Sétif 1, Campus El-Bèz, 19000 Sétif, Algeria*

²*Laboratory of Dosing, Analysis and Characterization with High Resolution (DAC-HR), Campus El-Bèz, 19000 Sétif, Algeria*

Beryllium oxide (BeO) is an important luminescent material used in personal, medical and environmental dosimetry. The glow curve of BeO has a single main TL peak at about 180°C and its response as a function of doses is linear up to 1Gy. In the course of this work, BeO was stimulated thermally and optically for different doses, two peaks appear at about 220°C and 330°C. The TL glow curve was fitted using GlowFit to deconvolute the TL parameters such as the activation energy E and frequency factor s , and the linearity of dosimeter was tested in the range from 2 to 10 Gy.

Keywords: luminescent materials, dosimetry, TL, GlowFit

OP-03. Post Violet-Infrared Stimulated Luminescence (pVIRSL) Dating using Potassium Feldspars

Monika Devi^{1,2}, Naveen Chauhan¹, A.K. Singhvi¹

¹AMOPH division, Physical Research Laboratory, Navrangpura, Ahmedabad-380009, India

²Indian Institute of Technology, Gandhinagar-382355, India.

Over the past decade, luminescence dating using feldspars is being explored due to its higher luminescence sensitivity and higher saturation dose (~1000 Gy) as compared to quartz. These attributes of feldspars offer the potential to increase the dynamic range of luminescence dating from a few years to up to a Ma. Its use has however been limited due to anomalous fading: the athermal loss of luminescence signal in addition to that predicted by the kinetic considerations. Considerable theoretical and experimental efforts have been made to develop procedures to account for athermal fading and have met with qualified success.

Devi et al. (2022) recently reported a new signal from feldspar, comprising a post violet IR stimulated luminescence (pVIRSL), and demonstrated that pVIRSL signal suffered near zero fading. The present work explores the properties of pVIRSL signal for its use in dating i.e., rapid bleachability (<10% in 60 min), recuperation (<5%), reproducibility, and dose recovery (within 10%). An optimized regeneration protocol enabled the dating of feldspars from sediments 2 ka to ~500 ka. The ages were consistent with geological reasoning and other age controls. In addition, new insights on the feldspar luminescence mechanism will be presented.

Reference: Devi, M., Chauhan, N., Rajapara, H., Joshi, S., Singhvi, A.K., 2022. Multispectral athermal fading rate measurements of K-feldspar. *Radiat. Meas.* 156, 106804. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2022.106804>

Keywords: Thermoluminescence; Optical stimulated luminescence; K-feldspar; Anomalous fading; Luminescence dating.

OP-04. Dating sediments by ESR using Al-h centre: A comparison between the properties of fine (4-11 μm) and coarse ($> 63 \mu\text{m}$) quartz grains

Zuzanna Kabacińska¹, A. Timar-Gabor^{1,2}

¹*Interdisciplinary Research Institute on Bio-Nano-Sciences, Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania*

²*Faculty of Environmental Science and Engineering, Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania.*

The possibility of ESR dating of sediments using Al-h signals of fine (4-11 μm) grains of quartz has not been previously discussed. Here the Al-h and peroxy ESR spectra of fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (63-90, 125-180 μm) sedimentary quartz from thoroughly investigated loess sites in Eastern Europe were examined. By comparing the experimental spectra with a simulated signal, we evaluated the overestimation observed when using the standard approach of Toyoda and Falguères (2003) to measuring the Al-h intensity, for different doses of radiation up to 40 000 Gy. This overestimation, caused by the presence of peroxy signals, was much more pronounced for fine grains. Fine grains exhibited some additional dose-dependent signals, which for some samples caused a complete distortion of the Al-h spectra at high doses, making it impossible to measure the standard amplitude. We propose a new approach to measuring the Al-h signal intensity, focusing on the peak-to-baseline amplitude of the part of the signal at $g \approx 2.0603$, which is not affected by the peroxy signals, and therefore has a potential of providing more accurate results. The shapes of dose response curves constructed for coarse and fine grains using the new approach show a considerable similarity, suggesting that the Al-h centre formation in fine and coarse grains upon artificial radiation at room temperature follows the same pattern.

[1] Toyoda, S.; Falguères, C. 2003. The Method to Represent the ESR Signal Intensity of the Aluminum Hole Center in Quartz for the Purpose of Dating. *Adv. ESR Appl.*, 20, 7–10.

[2] Kabacińska, Z.; Timar-Gabor, A. 2022. Dating Sediments by EPR Using Al-h Centre: A Comparison between the Properties of Fine (4–11 μm) and Coarse ($>63 \mu\text{m}$) Quartz Grains. *Molecules*, 27, 2683.

OP-05. Luminescence and electron spin resonance (ESR) characterisation of quartz from different lithologies of different ages

Alida Timar-Gabor^{1,2}, Zuzanna Kabacińska¹, Constantin, D¹, Aditi K. Dave¹, Ducea, M. N.^{3,4}

¹*Interdisciplinary Research Institute on Bio-Nano-Sciences, Babes-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania*

²*Faculty of Environmental Science and Engineering, Babes-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania*

³*University of Arizona, Department of Geosciences, Tucson, AZ, USA*

⁴*Faculty of Geology and Geophysics, University of Bucharest, Bucharest, Romania*

**Presenting Author: alida.timar@ubbcluj.ro*

Paramagnetic defects such as E' [1], as well as optically stimulated luminescence sensitivity [2] of quartz were proposed as potential indicators for the provenance of the sediments. However, most of the previous studies are targeting minerals deposited in sinks and focus only on observing the characteristics of signals displayed by different samples, followed by clustering. Also, there is no proper explanation of the variability of luminescence sensitivity (by up to ten orders of magnitude) observed between samples in the luminescence dating community, and in most dating studies it is implicitly or explicitly assumed that transport history is the main factor increasing the sensitivity. Based on the observations that quartz from young metamorphic rocks displays poor luminescence properties [3] and based on the fact that we observed a clear increase in the sensitivity of OSL signals of quartz from loess (windblown sediment, thus by its nature transported over long distances) in areas where the source material has components from cratonic areas we hypothesize that the defects of quartz in the host rock (formed during crystallisation as well as due to subsequent exposure to radioactivity in time) are an important factor controlling the type and abundance of the defects that characterise quartz grains in sediments, consequently dictating their luminescence properties.

Here we perform in depth characterisation of electron spin resonance signals (due to extrinsic defects such as $[AlO_4/h^+]^0$, $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$, as well as intrinsic defects such as E' and "peroxy" centers, an overlap between the peroxy radical and the nonbridging oxygen hole centre) as well as luminescence properties (OSL and TL) of quartz extracted from different lithologies of varied ages. By analysing granite samples of different ages (information provided by U-Pb zircon chronology) ranging from ~25 Ma to 1.4 Ga as well as by the analysis of quartz from well identified metamorphosed protoliths we have observed an increase in both the OSL sensitivity as well as the concentration of intrinsic defects with the age of the sample, in the absence of metamorphic events. The analysis of sediments derived from these lithologies is in progress and results will be presented at the time of the conference.

References

- [1] Toyoda S., Nagashima K., Yamamoto Y. 2016. ESR signals in quartz: Applications to provenance research – A review. *Quat. Int.*, 397, 258-266
- [2] Sawakuchi A. O., Jain M., Mineli T. D., Nogueira L., Bertassoli D. J., Häggi C., Zabel M. 2018. Luminescence of quartz and feldspar fingerprints provenance and correlates with the source area denudation in the Amazon River basin. *Earth and Planetary Sci. Lett.*, 492, 152-162
- [3] Brezenu D., Avram A., Micaleff A, Cinta Panzaru S., Timar-Gabor A., 2021. Investigations on the luminescence properties of quartz and feldspars extracted from loess in the Canterbury Plains, New Zealand South Island. *Geochronometria*, 48, 46-60

OP-06. Luminescence centres competition impact on the dose dependence of the OSL signal in quartz

Natalia K. Pawlak¹, Alicja Chruścińska¹

¹Institute of Physics, Faculty of Physics, Astronomy and Informatics, Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń, Grudziądzka 5/7, 87-100 Toruń, Poland

**natalia@umk.pl*

In quartz, different behavior of the OSL components with dose increase is observed (Palczewski & Chruścińska, 2019; Singarayer & Bailey, 2003). The intensity enhancement of the slower OSL components, observed in a much wider range than for the fast component, is of particular interest. It applies to the slow component identified as S3 by Singarayer and Bailey (Singarayer & Bailey, 2003) and component A of the OSL signal measured with violet light, VOSL (Ankjærgaard et al., 2013). Earlier, there were several new experimental data on the increase in these signals for doses above 1kGy and problems with proper inclusion of changes in OSL sensitivity during the implementation of the equivalent dose measurement protocol (Ankjærgaard, 2019; Colarossi et al., 2018). Recently, however, an increase in the signal from the fast component isolated using the thermally modulated (TM-OSL) method was also observed beyond the dose of 200 Gy (Palczewski & Chruścińska, 2022), among others in reference quartz samples FB and MR (Schmidt et al., 2022).

The fast OSL component in quartz can be separated from the rest of the components using the TM-OSL measurement with a stimulation wavelength of 620 nm during heating to 240 C (Chruścińska & Szramowski, 2018). In the measurements of the dose-response curves carried out with this optical stimulation method, a linear increase of the signal above the dose of 1000 Gy was observed. Its rate is sample dependent. In the samples where one observed a more rapid increase in the fast component intensity in the high dose range, a more significant increase in the TL signal was also detected after extending the spectral detection window to longer wavelengths. Therefore, the effects observed in measuring the dose-response may be related to the competition processes between different recombination channels in the OSL process. In these studies, this possibility was verified using computer simulations of the OSL process in quartz.

In the simulations, the kinetic model of Bailey (Bailey, 2001) was used to construct dose-dependence curves for various parameters controlling competition between recombination centres. One investigated the mechanism of the fast component linear growth for high doses and the influence of the OSL detection window width on its character. The dependence of the OSL increase with dose on centre concentrations was tested to explain the dependence of effects observed in experiments on the sample.

Acknowledgments: This work has been financed by the grant of the National Science Centre, Poland, No. 2018/31/B/ST10/03917.

References

- [1] Palczewski P., Chruścińska A., 2019. *Radiat. Meas.* 121, 32-36.
- [2] Singarayer J. S., Bailey R. M., 2003. *Radiat. Meas.* 37, 451 – 458.
- [3] Ankjærgaard, C., Jain, M., Wallinga, J., 2013. *Quat. Geochronol.* 18, 99-109.
- [4] Colarossi, D., Chapot, M. S., Duller, G. A. T., Roberts, H. M., 2018. *Radiat. Meas.* 120, 104-109.
- [5] Ankjærgaard, C., 2019. *Quat. Geochronol.* 51, 99-109.
- [6] Palczewski P., Chruścińska A., 2022. *This Book of abstracts.*
- [7] Schmidt C. et al., 2022. *J. Lumin.* 250, 119070.
- [8] Chruścińska A., Szramowski A., 2018. *Radiat. Meas.* 120, 20-25.
- [9] Bailey R. M., 2001. *Radiat. Meas.* 33, 17-45.

OP-07. Combined ^{14}C , OSL and ESR dating of representative loess-paleosol sequence from Songnen Plain, Northeast China

Chuanyi Wei¹, Gongming Yin¹, Jinhui Yin¹, Huili Yang¹, Chunru Liu¹, Hao Ji¹

¹State Key Laboratory of Earthquake Dynamics, Institute of Geology, China Earthquake Administration, Beijing 100029, China

chuanyiwei@ies.ac.cn; chuanyiwei@cug.edu.cn;

The expansion of Asian inland aridification not only resulting in the desert and Gobi development in the mid-high latitudes of the northern hemisphere, but also become the main source of the global aeolian dust, which even today profoundly affect billions of people. Consequently, understanding the origination, development and expansion history of those aeolian deposits have been a hot research topic around the world, which could provide essential information for assessing future regional and global trends of climate and environmental conditions and social-economic activities organizing in this area. However, previous studies were mainly focus on central Asia; the Northeast China as the eastmost Eurasia boundary of the aeolian dust transportation and expansion, has been rarely studied.

The loess-paleosol sequences, as the typical surface aeolian deposit in late Cenozoic, have been confirmed as the classic recording archives of the Asian aridification history and contain a direct indicator of past atmospheric circulation. Especially, the loess-paleosol accumulation located at the sand-desert downwind area, has an excellent coupling relationship with the formation and evolution of Asian aridification expansion, which can well constrain the evolution process of Asian aridification expansion. Songnen Plain is located at the easternmost Eurasian arid-semi-arid zone, which is the final inland area for aeolian dust accumulation, and is sensitive to the climate fluctuations and could provide the earliest timing record of the Asian aridification eastward-expansion.

After late Quaternary mammal fossils and paleolithic investigations at the 1970s, the systematic lithostratigraphic division studies of the Songnen plain are started from 1980s. Based on the magnetostratigraphy, ^{14}C and OSL dating results, combined with excavation of *Mammuthus primigenius* Blumenbach and *Coelodonta antiquitatis* Blumenbach, Sun et al. (1982) and Wu et al. (1984) divided the stratum of Songnen plain into Huangshan formation (early Pleistocene), Dongfeng formation (middle Pleistocene), Harbin formation (late Pleistocene), and Tantu formation (Holocene) from bottom to top, respectively. However, because of the unknown of exactly location at which the fossils were found, the stratigraphic division of Songnen plain remains debate.

In this study, we present an iconic ~55 sediment section (including ~29.9m loess-paleosol sequences) deposited at north Songnen Plain, Northeast China. On the basis of magnetostratigraphy, the chronostratigraphy of the ^{14}C , OSL and ESR dating were performed on this section, which could provide a better absolute dating constrain on the evolution history of the Asian aridification expansion and climate change.

Keywords: OSL dating, ESR dating, Asian inland aridification, loess-paleosol sequences, the Northeast China

OP-08. Palaeoflood records of ~3000 years from the lower reaches of Kaveri and its adjacent River Basins, Tamilnadu, India.

Mahadev Rawat¹, Manoj Kumar Jaiswal², and Atul Kumar Singh¹

¹*Inter-University Accelerator Centre, Aruna Asaf Ali Marg, New Delhi-110067, India*

²*Department of Earth Sciences, Indian Institute of Science Education and Research, Kolkata- 741246, West Bengal, India*

Paleochannels are the rivers' remnant and potential sites for economic minerals and groundwater accumulation. They also provide an opportunity to explore the past climatic conditions based on the sedimentation pattern. Identifying these fluvial deposits and exploring the causative factor may provide ample information about past climate and tectonics. Numerous floods in southern India prompted studying extreme events and their relation to climate. Lower reaches of the present-day Kaveri River and palaeochannel of the Gingee, Vaigai, which are in the north-eastern part of Tamilnadu, is chosen in this study. Samples were collected for geochemical and optical-stimulated luminescence dating (OSL) studies. Lithofacies were identified based on lithology, grain size, and sedimentary structures. The OSL ages indicate paleofloods for four distinct groups i) at ~40 years, ii) at ~150 years, iii) at ~1.70 ka. iv) and at ~2.85 ka. The first two sets (~40 and ~150 years B.P.) indicate a change in rainfall intensity associated with recurring tropical cyclonic events, which have resulted in high-frequency flooding events in recent times. The third set of OSL ages (~1.70 ka) suggests a large-scale flooding event and can be associated with the Roman Warming Period (RWP). The fourth set of flood events is clustered at ~2.85 ka, which is also associated with increased temperature. These changes in rainfall can also be attributed to shifting in the Inter-Tropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ).

OP-09. In which extent field conditions may affect the gamma dose rate evaluation using portable gamma spectrometry?

Loic Martin¹, Mathieu Duval²

¹ *Newton International Fellow, SUERC, Glasgow, UK*

² *National Research Centre Human Evolution (CENIEH), Burgos, Spain*

Field gamma spectrometry has become a standard method to measure local gamma dose rate for palaeodosimetric (i.e., electron spin resonance and luminescence) dating methods. In contrast to laboratory-based evaluations, in situ measurements of radioactivity usually provide more accurate and reliable results, and especially in heterogeneous sedimentary environments, using either peak window or threshold calibration methods. However, measurement conditions in the field may significantly differ from calibration conditions, and sometimes do not meet the ideal conditions.

Using Geant4 Monte Carlo simulations, we modelled a range of field conditions and explored the resulting impact on the signal measured by a NaI probe. In particular, we investigated the influence of the following on the measured gamma dose rate: (i) depth and shape of the measurement hole in which the probe is inserted, (ii) sediment moisture, (iii) geometry of the close environment, i.e. closed (e.g., cave, trench, etc...) or open (plain field, cliff, etc...). Our results show that some of the differences between calibration and field conditions may significantly bias the values measured in situ. This issue may be addressed by using specific correction factors, or by taking into account an additional uncertainty associated in the dose rate evaluation.

OP-10. The medium OSL component in quartz measured using the thermally modulated OSL method

Magdalena Biernacka¹, Alicja Chruścińska, P. Palczewski

¹*Institute of Physics, Faculty of Physics, Astronomy and Informatics, Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń, Grudziądzka 5/7, 87-100 Toruń, Poland.*

Recently was shown that various OSL components in quartz can be observed when simultaneous thermal and optical stimulations (*thermally modulated* OSL method – TM-OSL) are conducted using the proper wavelength [1, 2]. The OSL components' separation is of key importance, for example when the so-called fast OSL component is used for dating or thermochronometry applications. This component in quartz can be effectively separated from the other using the TM-OSL_{620nm} method [3]. This method uses the dynamic dependence of the optical cross-section of the trap on temperature for the stimulation energy significantly below the optical trap depth. Parameters of the trap responsible for the fast OSL component in quartz were established recently using the TM-OSL_{620nm} method in the *OSL thermal depletion curve* (OTDC) experiment [4, 5] and agree with the earlier obtained e.g. by Murray and Wintle [6].

However, not always the fast OSL component dominates the OSL signal in quartz. The variety in the share of components in the OSL quartz signal has been reported so far e.g. [7, 8]. Following works [9, 10] we can find that the medium OSL component is associated with the emission of phototransferred charges at the 170 °C TL trap, which originated from the 325 °C TL trap (maxima of TL peaks are given for heating rate 5 °C/s). However, from our experimental LM-OSL and TM-OSL studies ([11], Fig. 9) is clear that another trap is responsible for the medium OSL component in quartz – visible as a separate LM-OSL and TM-OSL component. Therefore, the deeper investigation of the medium OSL component observed in TM-OSL measurement with 530 nm is justified.

It turns out that determining the thermal stability of traps responsible for this component is challenging because the TM-OSL signal related to this component is complex. In this work, we present the results of OTDC experiments using the TM-OSL_{530nm} method to attempt the medium OSL component separation in two sedimentary quartz samples - sample FB, where the OSL signal is dominated by the fast component and sample MR with the very low contribution of this component, which was confirmed by both the LM-OSL and the TM-OSL methods [11]. Also, the persistence of the part of the OSL signal stimulated using 530 nm for both quartz samples is shown. This hard-bleachable component can be observed after bleaching the more intensive main TM-OSL_{530nm} component. It can be measured many times by TM-OSL_{530nm} with heating up to 250 °C. Its intensity decreases very slowly from one measurement to the next. The participation of this secondary component is the cause of problems with the correct determination of the trap parameters responsible for the dominant component in the TM-OSL_{530nm} measurement. Experiments were made using Risø TL/OSL-DA-20 reader with EMI 9235QB photomultiplier and a 7.5 mm Hoya U-340 filter. Optical stimulation was performed using LEDs modules with wavelengths 620 nm and 530 nm.

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by the National Science Centre, Poland, grant no. 2018/31/B/ST10/03917.

References

- [1] Chruścińska, A., Szramowski, A. J. *Lumin.* 195 (2018) 435-440.
- [2] Palczewski P., Chruścińska A. *Radiat. Meas.*, 121 (2019) 32-36.
- [3] Chruścińska, A., Szramowski, A. *Radiat. Meas.* 120 (2018) 20-25.
- [4] Biernacka, M., et al. (2022). Available at SSRN 4045568.
- [5] Pawlak, N. K., et al. *Meas.* (2022) 111505.
- [6] Murray, A. S., Wintle, A. G. *Radiat. Meas.* 30 (1999) 119-125.
- [7] Jeong, G. Y., Choi, J. H. *Quat. Geochronol.*, 10 (2012) 320-326.
- [8] Guralnik, B., et al. *Quat. Geochronol.*, 25 (2015) 37-48.
- [9] Wang, X. L., et al. *J. Lumin.*, 159 (2015) 147-157.
- [10] Peng, J., Wang, X. *Radiat. Meas.*, 138 (2020) 106448. [11] Schmidt, C., et al. *J. Lumin.*, 250 (2022) 119070.

OP-11. OSL retrospective dosimetric investigations of SMD capacitors

Madhusmita Panda¹, Shailesh Joshi¹, O. Annalaskhmi^{1,2}, Venkata Srinivas C^{1,2}

¹Environmental Assessment Division, Indira Gandhi Centre for Atomic Research, Kalpakkam – 603102, India

²Homi Bhabha National Institute, Mumbai 400094, India

(Corresponding Author: Email: madhusmita@igcar.gov.in; Phone: +91-44-27480352)

Introduction: Widespread application of ionizing radiation in different fields like industry, agriculture, forensics, research etc. has increased the risk of unintentional exposure of occupational radiation workers and civilians. In such cases, it is necessary to segregate the highly exposed personnel from one exposed to lower doses or unexposed, for proper medical management (Gonzalez et al., 2007). Thus, the development of dosimetric methods for the retrospective estimation of dose received by exposed individuals is of prime importance. For this, retrospective dosimetry can be done with commonly available materials that are present in the exposure site when conventional dosimeters are not available (Mrozik et al., 2014 and Menon et al., 2017). The aim of the present work was to investigate the optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) retrospective dosimetric properties of surface mount devices (SMD) capacitors which are commonly placed in electronic instruments.

Material and Methods: The dosimetric studies have been carried out on SMD capacitors of different values 10 nF (C1), 10 pF (C2), 100 nF (C3), and 100 pF (C4). OSL measurements were carried out using an automatic Risoe TL/OSL reader (model DA-20) with blue LEDs ($\lambda=470 \pm 30$ nm) as stimulation source with stimulation power level at 90% of the maximum stimulation intensity (80 mW/cm²) and a bialkali EMI 9235QA photomultiplier tube (PMT) with Hoya U-340 and Schott BG-39 optical filters in front of the PMT. All the irradiations were carried using an inbuilt ⁹⁰Sr/⁹⁰Y beta source.

Results and Discussion: Fig. 1 represents the OSL decay curves of four SMD capacitors C1, C2, C3, and C4 irradiated with beta dose of 5 Gy. Based on the OSL signal intensity C1 was considered to be a better material for retrospective dosimetry.

The OSL response of SMD capacitor C1 has been investigated from 500 mGy to 40 Gy. It was found that the response is linear from 500 mGy to 15 Gy and beyond 15 Gy became sublinear. Minimum detectable dose (MDD) was found to be 26 mGy. From the fading studies of C1 samples, it was observed that signal faded to 45 % within 24 hours and remained stable up to 6 days. Fig 2 depicts the recovery of dose from irradiated C1 sample using single aliquot regenerative (SAR)-dose protocol. It can be inferred that the recovered dose is within ± 5 % of the delivered dose.

Conclusion: In this work the feasibility of SMD capacitors as retrospective dosimeter was investigated. The MDD was about 26 mGy. The fading is almost negligible after 24 hours of irradiation for a period of about 6 days. The dose reconstructed using SAR protocol shows very good precision and accuracy. Hence this study suggests the possibility of using SMD capacitor as retrospective dosimeter in case of emergencies in the absence of any conventional dosimeters.

References

- [1] Gonzalez-Angulo, et al., (2007), Overview of resistance to systemic therapy in patients with breast cancer, Breast Cancer Chemosensitivity, 1-22.
- [2] Menon, et al., (2017), OSL studies of commonly available medicines for their use as retrospective dosimeters, Radiat. Meas., 101, 7–12.
- [3] Mrozik, et al., (2014), Investigation of OSL signal of resistors from mobile phones for accidental dosimetry, Radiat. Meas, 71, 466–470.

OP-12. Single-grain K-feldspar pIRIR Dating of a thick alluvial sequence on northern piedmont of Chinese Tian Shan

Kechang Li¹, Jintang Qin², Jie Chen³

¹*State Key Laboratory of Earthquake Dynamics,*

²*Xinjiang Pamir Intracontinental Subduction National Observation and Research Station*

³*Institute of Geology, China Earthquake Administration, Beijing, China*

The rise and fall of luminescence signal intensity of mineral is due to the burial and exposure of the mineral grain across Earth surface. The luminescence signal of grains experienced sufficient sunlight exposure records the time elapsed since their last burial, while it bears the pre-deposition information for grains not fully exposed to sunlight before their recent burial.

Alluvial fans develop extensively across the arid northern Tian Shan piedmont. During the building of those landscape, the coarse clast experienced complex burial and transport processes. Jingou River entrenches more than 100m deep into the alluvial fan and unravels complex sedimentary sequences, which provides a window to probe the evolution of the foreland alluvial systems, for which a detailed chronology framework is essential.

In this study, post-IR IRSL protocol is employed to establish the chronological sequence of the alluvial fan along the Jingou River. By optimizing the experimental parameters, the single grain pIRIR₂₂₅ signal of K-feldspar is used to measure De values. The preliminary results show that the 100m thick alluvial sequence deposited in between ~100ka and ~10ka ago. The over-dispersion values were between 30% and 50% for all samples, indicating a complex pre-deposition history of these samples, which will be investigated in this study.

Keywords: Fluvial terrace, luminescence dating, single grains, chronological sequence

OP-13. High-resolution chronological sequences and surface processes constrained by luminescence of K-feldspar grains: message from the central section of Altyn Tagh Fault

Yashi Sui¹, Kechang Li¹, Jintang Qin¹, Zhaode Yuan¹, Qi Liu¹, Jie Chen¹

¹State Key Laboratory of Earthquake Dynamics, Xinjiang Pamir Intracontinental Subduction National Observation and Research Station, Institute of Geology, Earthquake Administration, Beijing, 100029, China

* Presenting Author e-mail: 1642086796@qq.com

The mineral grains transferred and deposited via various Earth surface dynamics may vary significantly, with respect to their luminescence emissions and resultant luminescence ages, even though they have experienced the same time since their last burial. Therefore, complex sedimentary dynamics pose challenges to derive their depositional ages. Measuring luminescence ages on grain level and analyzing their distribution characteristics for a sedimentary sequence enable us to disentangle the chronological information of the last burial from the combo age distribution, and also shed light on temporal variations of sedimentary dynamics.

The Wuzunxiaer trench, which revealed multiple paleoseismic events, is located on the piedmont alluvial area in front of Altyn Shan. While the sedimentary sequences are clearly identified, the sedimentary facies vary a lot. The micro-topography due to fault activity further perturbed the local surface dynamics. We collected samples for luminescence dating at high resolution from the trench sediments with a total thickness of 13.6m, aiming to establish its high-resolution chronological sequence and tie its sediment dynamics to the luminescence age distribution obtained by measuring luminescence of single potassium feldspar (K-feldspar) grain. Coarse K-feldspar grains (125-180 μm) were extracted from 19 samples, and post- IR_{110} IRSL_{170} ($\text{pIR}_{110}\text{-IR}_{170}$) single grain SAR protocol was applied to determine their D_e values (modified after Fu et al., 2015). The dependences of over-dispersion (OD) value and MAM-D_e values on the threshold $\text{pIR}_{110}\text{-IR}_{170}$ sensitivity (T_n) for screening grains for analysis, are employed to identify grains for which the $\text{pIR}_{110}\text{-IR}_{170}$ signals were well-bleached before burial and reasonably stable after burial. The "Baylum" package (Guérin et al., 2021) is further applied to reduce the error of chronological sequence. Preliminary results show that the 13.6 m thick sediments deposited from 11 ka ago to 2 ka ago, with distinct sedimentation rates in two phases. The luminescence age distribution also hint a transition of dominant surface processes from aeolian to alluvial.

Keywords High resolution chronological sequences; Feldspar; Bayesian model; Sedimentary environment

References

- [1] Guérin G, Lahaye C, Heydari M, et al. Towards an improvement of optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) age uncertainties: modelling OSL ages with systematic errors, stratigraphic constraints and radiocarbon ages using the R package BayLum[J]. *Geochronology*, 2021, 3(1): 229-245.
- [2] Fu X, Li S H, Li B. Optical dating of aeolian and fluvial sediments in north Tian Shan range, China: Luminescence characteristics and methodological aspects[J]. *Quaternary Geochronology*, 2015, 30: 161-167.

OP-14. Comparison of the pulsed blue and green light stimulation in isolating quartz source signal of rock slice by using time-resolved signature

Furong Cui^{1,2}, Jintang Qin¹, Jinfeng Liu¹, Huili Yang¹

¹State Key Laboratory of Earthquake Dynamics, Institute of Geology, China Earthquake Administration, Beijing, 100029, China

²School of Earth Sciences and Resources, China University of Geosciences (Beijing), Beijing, 100083, China

*Presenting Author e-mail: liujf81@ies.ac.cn

Compared with the IR signal of feldspar, the luminescence signals from quartz, as an alternative dosimeter, has more potential in rock surface luminescence dating. But it is challenging to isolate quartz-dominated OSL signals from mixed mineral rocks (Cui et al., 2022). In general, the post-infrared (post-IR) pulsed blue or green light stimulated luminescence (PBLSL or PGLSL) method could be isolated quartz source signal from a mixed quartz-feldspar sample (Ankjærgaard et al., 2010; Qin et al., 2021). This approach relies on much longer relaxation time for quartz OSL signal than that for feldspar IRSL signals, which can be measured by time-resolved OSL (TR-OSL) technique (Chithambo and Galloway, 2000). However, there is no research to prove which stimulation of pulsed blue light or pulsed green light is more effective to isolate quartz source signals from rock slices.

In this study, we investigated the characteristics of the TR-OSL signals from granite slices and its' quartz extracts, quartzite slices and its' quartz extracts and potassium feldspar slices stimulated by the blue (~470 nm) and green (~525 nm) pulsed LEDs light following the IR stimulations. In order to identify the optimum measurement conditions for decreasing the contribution of feldspar, five temperatures and three temperatures were selected for IR and pulsed stimulation temperature respectively. Furthermore, we also compared the decay characteristics of TR-OSL spectra and pulsed stimulation curves from annealed (500 °C) and unheated granite slices. Preliminary results show that the post-IR PGLSL method has more potential to isolate pure quartz source signals in mixed mineral rocks than post-IR PBLSL method.

Keywords: TR-OSL signals; Quartz source signal; Post-PGLSL; Post-PBLSL

References

- [1] Ankjærgaard, C., Jain, M., Thomsen, K.J., et al., 2010. Optimising the separation of quartz and feldspar optically stimulated luminescence using pulsed excitation. *Radiat. Meas.* 45, 778–785.
- [2] Chithambo, M. L, Galloway, R. B, 2000. On luminescence lifetimes in quartz. *Radiat. Meas.* 32: 621-626.
- [3] Furong Cui, Jintang Qin, Jinfeng Liu, et al., 2022. Isolating quartz-dominated OSL signal of rock slice by using pulsed stimulation: Implications for dating burial age of cobbles. *Quat. Geochronol.* 72, 101367.
- [4] Qin, J.T., Chen, J., Li, K.Z., 2021. Characteristics of pulsed blue and green light stimulated luminescence signals of quartz and feldspars. *Geochronometria* 48, 138–146.

OP-15. Dose response of the fast OSL component in quartz for doses above 200 Gy

Alicja Chruścińska¹, P. Palczewski¹

¹*Institute of Physics, Faculty of Physics, Astronomy and Informatics, Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń,
Grudziądzka 5/7, 87-100 Toruń, Poland*

**alicja@fizyka.umk.pl*

Previous studies show that the OSL signal in quartz, especially when its fast component is dominant, becomes saturated for doses higher than 200 Gy [1-3]. It is known, however, that the slowest OSL components' intensity increases over a much wider range of doses. According to various studies, the signal saturation for these components is from over 600 Gy to over 3000 Gy [4-5]. One also observed a linear increase in the OSL signal in quartz after high laboratory doses. Attempts have been made to explain such a behaviour of the OSL dose-dependence in various ways, including the appearance of a new trap or centre for large doses [6] or competition between radiative and non-radiative centres [7].

As recent studies of dose-response curves (DRC) in the range up to 3kGy for the fast OSL component showed the dependence of this curve on the quartz sample [8], extended studies of this issue were undertaken for samples for which an earlier composition analysis had confirmed the purity of the quartz. Reference samples FB and MR [9] and a quartz sample provided for source calibration by the Risø laboratory were tested using three different methods of DRC measurement.

In two protocols, the TM-OSL measurement with the light wavelength of 620 nm (TM-OSL₆₂₀) was applied to separate the fast component from the total OSL signal. The first of these protocols was implemented for two different spectral detection windows limited by the U-340 filter and the set of filters BG-39 and BG-9. A wider detection window is possible due to the 620 nm wave used for optical stimulation. Heat to 500 °C allowed for emptying OSL traps after the TM-OSL measurement after each dose. The second protocol is the TM-OSL SAR [10], in which the highest heating temperature in the cycle is 260 °C. The results obtained by two protocols with TM-OSL measurement were compared with those obtained using the SAR protocol used commonly in OSL dating for the DRC construction.

For all samples, one can observe changes in the OSL intensity in the region above 1000 Gy, where one expects signal saturation. The nature of these changes depends on the procedure used. The scale of these changes depends on the test dose used in the protocol to monitor and correct changes in OSL sensitivity and, secondly, on the sample. In the case of the TM-OSL protocol with the heating to 500 °C after each cycle, the corrected OSL signal above 1 kGy increases linearly with the dose. In contrast, in protocols which do not include annealing to such a high temperature, the DRC drops in the same dose range. Both effects are more significant for the smaller test dose. The possible mechanisms of changes observed in DRCs are discussed.

Acknowledgments: This work has been financed by the grant of the National Science Centre, Poland, No. 2018/31/B/ST10/03917. The work was partially realised thanks to the help of the Centre for Modern Interdisciplinary Technologies, Nicolaus Copernicus University in Torun, ul. Wilenska 4, 87-100 Torun, Poland (e-mail: icnt@umk.pl).

References

- [1] N.G. Kiyak et al., *Radiat. Meas.* 42, (2007), 144-155.
- [2] M.S. Chapot et al., *Radiat. Meas.* 47, (2012), 1045-1052.
- [3] A. Timar-Gabor, A.G. Wintle, *Quat. Geochronol.* 18, (2013), 34-40.
- [4] J. S. Singarayer and R. M. Bailey, *Radiat. Meas.* 37, (2003), 451 – 458.
- [5] N. Rahimzadeh et al., *Quat. Geochronol.* 65, (2021), 101194.
- [6] Z.P. Lai et al., *Radiat. Meas.* 43, (2008), 763–766.
- [7] S.E. Lowick et al., *Radiat. Meas.* 45, (2010), 975–984.
- [8] P. Palczewski and A. Chruścińska, *Radiat. Meas.* 121, (2019), 32-36.
- [9] C. Schmidt et al., *J. Lumin.* 250, (2022), 119070.
- [10] A. Chruścińska et al., *Measurement* 167, (2021), 108448.

OP-16. Parameters of multi-level statistical analysis affecting the OSL ages of mortar samples from Northern Italy

M.Saleh^{1*}, G.S. Polymeris², L. Panzeri¹, E. Tsoutsoumanos^{2,3}, G. Ricci^{4,5}, M. Secco^{5,6}, G. Artioli^{4,5}, S. Dilaria^{5,6}, M. Martini¹, A. Galli¹

¹ *Department of Material Science, University of Milano-Bicocca, Milan, Italy*

² *Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, NCSR "Demokritos", Athens, Greece*

³ *Condensed Matter Physics Laboratory, Physics Department, University of Thessaly, Lamia, Greece*

⁴ *Department of Geosciences, University of Padova, Padua, Italy*

⁵ *Inter-Departmental Research Centre for the Study of Cement Materials and Hydraulic Binders (CIRCe), University of Padova, Padua, Italy*

⁶ *Department of Cultural Heritage (DBC), University of Padova, Padua, Italy*

*Corresponding Author e-mail: m.saleh1@campus.unimib.it

Scientific dating and chronology of historical and archaeological mortars are nowadays quite an attractive research topic. Mortars stand among the very few materials that theoretically cannot be reused due to irreversible hardening processes. Among the various dating techniques, Radiocarbon and Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL) struggle for being selected as the most robust and reliable dating technique for the specific material [1–3]. The principle of mortar OSL dating depends on the bleaching of the quartz grains of the sandy aggregate while mixing and laying the mortar to daylight. Thus, the OSL ages strongly depend on the effective bleaching of the quartz [4–6] OSL dating was applied to earthen mortars, consisting in a quartz-rich aggregate dispersed in silty-clayey matrix. The samples were taken from two independently dated structures in Cremona, Northern Italy (Palazzo Raimondi, 1495–1499 AD and Palazzo Soldi, 1770–1790 AD).

Here, we deal with OSL ages from two sites in Northern Italy: the Medieval Castle of Cannero, on the shore of Lake Maggiore, and the old Roman Theatre of Padua. The geological, archaeological and historical context of these sites have been previously presented along with the preliminary Radiocarbon ages [7–9]. Preliminary OSL results based on Single Aliquot Regeneration (SAR) protocol using three regenerated doses to Multigrain (MG) quartz aliquots, indicated distributions of ED (Equivalent Dose) leading to significant mismatch of these results compared to the expected ages.

The present work attempts to discuss the influence of various data analysis approaches such as: (a) exclusion criteria like recycling ratio and recuperation values, (b) selection of the suitable region of interest in the signal's integral along with the correct background (late or early) subtraction technique [10] an initial integral of the OSL decay curve is used in the calculation of equivalent dose, once a background integral has been subtracted. Because the OSL signal commonly contains a number of exponentially decaying components, the exact choice of time intervals used for the initial-signal and background integrals determines the composition of the net signal. Here we investigate which combination of time intervals will produce the net signal most dominated by the fast OSL component, while keeping an acceptable level of precision. Using a three-component model of OSL decay, we show that for a specified level of precision, the net signal most dominated by the fast component can be obtained when the background integral immediately follows the initial signal and is approximately 2.5 times its length. With this 'early-background' approach, the contribution of slow components to the net signal is virtually zero. We apply our methods to four samples from relatively young deposits. Compared to the widely used 'late-background' approach, in which the background integral is taken from the last few seconds of OSL, we find less thermal transfer, less recuperation and a higher proportion of aliquots yielding an equivalent dose in agreement with expectations. We find the use of an early background to be a simple and effective way of improving the accuracy of OSL dating, and suggest it should be used in standard protocols.

"container-title": "Quaternary Geochronology", "DOI": "10.1016/j.quageo.2010.08.004", "ISSN": "18711014", "issue": "6", "journalAbbreviation": "Quaternary Geochronology", "language": "en", "page": "657-666", "source": "DOI.org (Crossref and (c) appropriate statistical analysis by selecting the suitable age model (descriptive statistics, Central Age Model, Minimum Age Model) on the final distribution as well

as both value and precision of the E.D., enabling thus to obtain ages than are not only more accurate, but also closer to what was expected [11]. Alternative statistical indicators of either the symmetry of the ED distributions (like skewness, kurtosis, etc) or the OSL signal itself (residual distribution analysis, kinetic parameters, and percentage contribution of each OSL component to the overall signal) will be assessed in an effort to investigate possible correlations.

References

- [1] I. Hajdas *et al.*, «Preparation and Dating of Mortar Samples—Mortar Dating Inter-Comparison Study (MODIS)», *Radiocarbon*, vol. 59, n. 6, pagg. 1845–1858, dic. 2017, doi: 10.1017/RDC.2017.112.
- [2] R. Hayen *et al.*, «Mortar Dating Methodology: Assessing Recurrent Issues and Needs for Further Research», *Radiocarbon*, vol. 59, n. 6, pagg. 1859–1871, dic. 2017, doi: 10.1017/RDC.2017.129.
- [3] P. Urbanová, E. Boaretto, e G. Artioli, «The State-of-the-Art of Dating Techniques Applied to Ancient Mortars and Binders: A Review», *Radiocarbon*, vol. 62, n. 3, pagg. 503–525, giu. 2020, doi: 10.1017/RDC.2020.43.
- [4] L. Panzeri, M. Cantù, M. Martini, e E. Sibilìa, «Application of different protocols and age-models in OSL dating of earthen mortars», *Geochronometria*, vol. 44, n. 1, pagg. 341–351, dic. 2017, doi: 10.1515/geochr-2015-0072.
- [5] L. Panzeri, M. Caroselli, A. Galli, S. Lugli, M. Martini, e E. Sibilìa, «Mortar OSL and brick TL dating: The case study of the UNESCO world heritage site of Modena», *Quat. Geochronol.*, vol. 49, pagg. 236–241, feb. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.quageo.2018.03.005.
- [6] L. Panzeri, F. Maspero, A. Galli, E. Sibilìa, e M. Martini, «Luminescence and Radiocarbon Dating of Mortars at Milano-Bicocca Laboratories», *Radiocarbon*, vol. 62, n. 3, pagg. 657–666, giu. 2020, doi: 10.1017/RDC.2020.6.
- [7] J. Bonetto, E. Pectenò, F. Veronese, F. Trivisonno, e C. Previato, «Il teatro romano di Padova», *Orizzonti*, n. 22, 2021, doi: 10.19272/202107501003.
- [8] G. Ricci *et al.*, «The Cannero Castle (Italy): Development of Radiocarbon Dating Methodologies in the Framework of the Layered Double Hydroxide Mortars», *Radiocarbon*, vol. 62, n. 3, pagg. 617–631, giu. 2020, doi: 10.1017/RDC.2020.31.
- [9] M. Volpin, «Recenti indagini archeologiche hanno permesso una rilettura delle strutture dello "Zairo", in Prato della Valle, e l'acquisizione di nuovi dati sulle tecniche edilizie usate.», pag. 8, 2020.
- [10] A. C. Cunningham e J. Wallinga, «Selection of integration time intervals for quartz OSL decay curves», *Quat. Geochronol.*, vol. 5, n. 6, pagg. 657–666, dic. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.quageo.2010.08.004.
- [11] R. F. Galbraith, R. G. Roberts, G. M. Laslett, H. Yoshida, e J. M. Olley, «optical dating of single and multiple grains of quartz from jinnium rock shelter, northern australia: part i, experimental design and statistical models», *Archaeometry*, vol. 41, n. 2, pagg. 339–364, ago. 1999, doi: 10.1111/j.1475-4754.1999.tb00987.x.

OP-17. Correlation between the decays of the NTL signal following isothermal and infrared stimulation in feldspar and apatite samples.

Pavlos G. Konstantinidis^{1*}, V. Giannoulatou¹, E. Tsoutsoumanos^{2,3}, G.S. Polymeris³, G. Kitis¹

¹ Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Physics Department, Nuclear Physics and Elementary Particles Physics Section, 54124-Thessaloniki, Greece

² Condensed Matter Physics Laboratory, Physics Department, University of Thessaly, GR-35100, Lamia, Greece

³ NCSR "Demokritos", Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology Demokritos, Ag. Paraskevi, 15310 Athens, Greece

*Corresponding Author e-mail: pavkonst@physics.auth.gr

Studying the recombination pathways of either IRSL or prompt isothermal decay (PID) of Thermoluminescence (TL) signals in feldspars and apatites has been quite an interesting topic lately. In a recent paper, Sfampa *et al.* (2019) have attempted to compare the Isothermal TL to the IRSL signals following artificial irradiation inside the laboratory, in four K-feldspar samples which belong to microclines, and sanidines. The present work follows directly from this later study, attempting the exact same correlation for the case of the naturally accrued TL (NTL) signal in 4 different geological materials, namely an Amazonite from Turkey, two K-feldspar samples collected from Nepal and Greece, along with one fluorapatite from Canada.

All samples were subjected to the protocol suggested by Polymeris *et al.* (2020), which includes a unique luminescence measurement for each isothermal temperature that consists of two parts; the initial increasing part up to a specific T_{PID} , followed by an isothermal decay at T_{PID} . A set of similar combined measurements performed for different T_{PID} , is used in order to determine the recombination pathways for each trap, being either de-localized, via the conduction band, or localized, involving tunnelling through an excited state of the trapped electrons. Using this unique for each T_{PID} measurement, the initial rise method could be applied to the first half of the signal up to the T_{PID} , in conjunction to an analysis on the isothermal decay part, using the decay equation of General order Kinetics. Also, the protocol utilizes the Peak Shape Methods for the deconvolution of the RTL signals of the experiments, to calculate the activation energy of the contributing traps. Thus, by using three different methods of analysis, one can clearly discover if a trap follows the localized or the de-localized model; in the former case, the activation energy via the analysis of the PID curves is being severely underestimated.

In order to study the IRSL and the decaying part of the PID signal, further analysis is undergone, using a new equation describing the localized recombination pathway, based on the Lambert W function of Kitis *et al.*, (2018). So, a new excel spreadsheet is created, which successfully uses this new equation and its new parameters. The series of experiments showed that the equation works as intended with very good fitting results. Moreover, the energies that are calculated strongly suggest that tunnelling effect (the delocalized transition model) might be the dominant recombination pathway in these four materials.

References

- [1] Kitis, G., & Pagonis, V. 2018. Localized transition models in luminescence: A reappraisal. Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms 432, 13–19.
- [2] Polymeris, G. S., Pagonis, V., & Kitis, G. 2020. Investigation of thermoluminescence processes during linear and isothermal heating of dosimetric materials. Journal of Luminescence 222, 117142.
- [3] Sfampa, I.K., G., Polymeris, G.S., Pagonis, V., Kitis, G., 2019. Correlation between isothermal TL and Irsl in K-Feldspars of various types. Radiation Physics and Chemistry 165, 108386.

OP-18. Effect of oxygen vacancies on luminescence characteristics of BeO Ceramics produced by Sol-Gel synthesis technique

Volkan Altunal, Veysi Güçkan, Zehra Yenigil

Çukurova University, Türkiye

Understanding whether the luminescence of BeO ceramics is due to Beryllium or Oxygen defects is very important for the development of this material as an OSL dosimeter. This study investigates the effect of oxygen vacancies (Vo) in undoped BeO synthesized by sol-gel, on luminescence properties following different sintering processes. Herein, we suggest that BeO has luminescence caused by oxygen defects. Considering that Vo defects are formed by sintering in an inert gas environment, we compared the structural and luminescence properties of this material with that of sintered in the air atmosphere.

The crystallite properties of BeO and BeO(Vo) ceramics were defined by XRD analysis, and all the BeO samples were assigned to the ICDD pdf card no. 98-006-1181, indicating the single phase of hexagonal formation. The presence of Vo defects was confirmed by EPR analyses. On the other hand, the effects of these vacancies on the surface morphology were also investigated and some blistered surface structures were observed in SEM images. When the RL signals of BeO and BeO(Vo) ceramics were compared, it was observed that an emission band originating from Vo was obtained between 600 and 800 nm. In addition, it was observed that the characteristic BeO emission band located between 200 and 400 nm increased significantly with sintering in an argon gas environment. Ten times more sensitivity was observed in BeO(Vo) ceramics when compared with the BeO ceramics. A 10 s reduction in the lifetimes of fast components of BeO(Vo) OSL decay curves was evaluated.

Through this study, it can be concluded that the source of luminescence of BeO ceramics may originate from the oxygen vacancies that occur during synthesis in the structure and that this luminescence can be controlled under appropriate conditions.

Keywords: Beryllium Oxide (BeO); Oxygen vacancies; Optically stimulated luminescence (OSL); Thermoluminescence (TL); Radiation dosimetry; Luminescence mechanism

OP-19. The effects of heat treatment on the OSL signal in sodium chloride crystals

Caroline Fernandes¹, Rocca, R. R.¹

¹ Federal University of Sao Paulo, Marine Institute, Sao Paulo, Brazil

*Corresponding Author e-mail: paschoal.caroline@unifesp.br

The crystals of sodium chloride are the focus of luminescence study in different parts of the world, like Brazil, India, Greece, Türkiye, Australia, Spain, Poland, among others. This promising material has already demonstrated high sensibility, good reproducibility, linear response and a low minimum detectable dose. Besides this, it has potential application in accident dosimetry, in addition with relevant results for dating and retrospective dosimetry. There are other types of sodium chloride such as the Himalayan black salt, rock salt and pink salt, for example. The reason for the existence of these types of salt is that in the composition, in addition to sodium chloride, there are other types of elements, like magnesium, potassium, sulfur and calcium. For this study we used crystals of pink salt. Initially, the pink salt crystals were divided into three groups according to their color: light, intermediate and dark colored crystals. Afterwards, the groups were submitted to different heat treatment temperatures (200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450 and 500 °C) for different times (2, 24 and 48 h). The OSL curve was studied for each heat treatment temperature, in addition to some dosimetric tests, such as reproducibility, fading and linearity. Besides the OSL, we used another technique to analyze the influence of heat treatment: the thermoluminescence (TL). The glow curve after the heat treatment shows peaks at 88.3, 103.3, 147, 260.3 and 292.1 °C, which is not so different from before the treatment, but the intensity of the second characteristic peak was increased by up to 15 times. After X-ray Fluorescence analysis, we found that the darker the color, the greater the presence of other chemical elements such as aluminum, cadmium, iron and rare earth (neodymium and samarium). However, among the three groups, the one that obtained the best results was the group with light crystals.

Keywords: pink salt, OSL, heat treatment, dosimetry.

OP-20. TA-OSL from KMgF₃:Eu,Yb,Li dosimeter; comparison with OSL and TL dose responses

Veysi Güçkan¹, Volkan Altunal¹, Adnan Özdemir², Zehra Yenigil¹, George Kitis³, Geroge Polymeris⁴

¹ Çukurova University, Türkiye

² Kahramanmaraş İstiklal University ESMYO, Türkiye

³ Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece

⁴ Demokritos University, Greece

This Fluoroperovskite (KMgF₃) has shown promising dosimetry properties suitable for the detection and measurement of ionizing radiation [1, 2]. However, as still the study on the luminescence mechanisms in these materials are still pending, selecting the most effective stimulation mode is currently a hot research topic. The present study presents the dose-response of luminescence signals following a variety of stimulation modes, such as optical, thermal and a specific combination, namely Thermally Assisted Optically Stimulated luminescence (TA-OSL). The latter, a somehow unconventional technique that efficiently combines both optical and thermal stimulation, appears as a promising tool for stimulating electrons from very deep traps, without heating the samples to temperatures greater than 500 °C. TA-OSL of both Al₂O₃:C and quartz has been reported to be effectively applied toward extending the maximum detection dose thresholds [3]. As a secondary aim, the present study further exploits the applicability of the technique to another, well-established luminescent phosphor, KMgF₃:Eu,Yb,Li. The experimental procedure involved two basic protocols. To obtain more information about the thermal behavior of the source traps which cause it, the first protocol was applied in order to study the TA-OSL signal versus the temperature at which the OSL measurement is performed. The second protocol was applied to investigate the dose-response of the TA-OSL signal. Several isothermal TA-OSL features are studied, including the shape of the TA-OSL curve, the dependence of both shape and intensity on the stimulation temperature after selecting the optimum stimulation temperature. The TA-OSL dose response features are compared to the respective OSL and TL dose response counterparts, following deconvolution analysis. This work presents the TA-OSL dosimetric properties of KMgF₃ phosphorus in addition to a number of well-known luminescent phosphors. Keywords: Fluoroperovskites; Parascandolaite (KMgF₃); Optically stimulated luminescence; Thermal-Assisted OSL (TA-OSL); Beta irradiation; Deconvolution

Acknowledgments: This research is sponsored by NATO's Emerging Security Challenges Division in the framework of "The Science for Peace and Security Programme (SPS)" under project number G5647 and Cukurova University Research Projects Development and Coordination Unit under contract number FOA-2022-14574.

Keywords: Fluoroperovskites; Parascandolaite (KMgF₃); Optically stimulated luminescence; Thermal-Assisted OSL (TA-OSL); Beta irradiation; Deconvolution

References

- [1] V. Guckan, D. Kaya, V. Altunal, A. Ekicibil, F. Karadag, A. Ozdemir, Z. Yegingil, Impact of Li concentration in KMgF₃:Eu,Yb fluoroperovskite on structure and luminescence properties, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 902 (2022) 163810.
- [2] L. Pérez-Cruz, E. Cruz-Zaragoza, D. Díaz, J.H. Alcántara, E.C. García, I. Camarillo-García, H.M.J.A.R. Sánchez, Isotopes, Synthesis, optical and thermoluminescence properties of thulium-doped KMgF₃ fluoroperovskite, 177 (2021) 109913.
- [3] G.S. Polymeris, S. Raptis, D. Afouxenidis, N.C. Tsirliganis, G. Kitis, Thermally assisted OSL from deep traps in Al₂O₃:C, *Radiation Measurements*, 45 (2010) 519-522.

OP-21. Is TL thermochronometry using low sensitivity quartz from metamorphic rocks feasible? A pioneer case study from phyllite-quartzite assemblages in southern Greece

V. Kanavou¹, G.S. Polymeris², C.D. Athanassas¹, K. Stamoulis³, V. Mouslopoulou⁴, X. Aslanoglou⁵

¹Department of Geological Sciences, School of Mining and Metallurgical Engineering, National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), Greece, kanavouv@mail.ntua.gr; athanassas@central.ntua.gr

²Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, National Center for Scientific Research (NCSR), Demokritos, Greece, g.polymeris@inn.demokritos.gr

³Archaeometry Center, University of Ioannina, Greece, kstamoul@cc.uoi.gr

⁴Institute of Geodynamics, National Observatory of Athens, Greece, vasiliki.mouslopoulou@noa.gr

⁵Department of Physics, University of Ioannina, Greece, xaslanog@uoi.gr

*Corresponding Author email: kanavouv@mail.ntua.gr

Thermoluminescence (TL) from quartz may be suitable in demonstrating the exhumation of rocks from deeper to shallower depths and from higher to lower temperatures, respectively, because of its remarkable thermal stability (lifetime from <ka to Ba) [1, 2, 3, 4]. However, signal saturation is a great limitation of trapped charge thermochronometry [3]. Nevertheless, para-metamorphic rocks are rich in sizable quartz phacoids (~ 30 cm in radius), which are inherently low in radionuclides while, due to their size, their interior is shielded from external γ -ray penetration. These conditions form an environment of *extremely* low radioactivity within the quartz phacoids, potentially allowing us to push the dating envelope back in geological time by one order of magnitude (i.e., from several ka to a few Ma). This study explores the suitability of TL thermochronometry on Miocene phyllite-quartzite exposures from Mani Peninsula, South Greece, by testing quartz samples that meet the above properties. Initial measurements delivered faint TL (as well as OSL) signals. Because of this, a series of experiments were designed and executed in order to characterize the TL behavior of the sampled metamorphic quartz. Specifically, the stability of the signal was estimated by calculating the lifetimes of the traps corresponding to the TL peaks above 200 °C; frequency factors and activation energies were calculated using both the fractional glow technique as well as deconvolution analysis of the natural TL (NTL), following correction for thermal quenching. Besides, a number of thermal sensitization patterns were studied following measurement protocols that take advantage of purely thermal as well as pre-dose sensitization. The thermal history of the quartz samples has been studied using the 110 °C TL peak quartz as a probe. The presence of geologically stable but unsaturated traps around 360-400°C implies that the dose must have been delivered at a very low rate, while saturation of deeper traps indicates that heating hardly exceeded 400°C. Due to the low amounts of radioelement concentrations, calculation of secular dose rates for these samples proved to be very challenging using conventional analytical (e.g., ICP-MS) and γ spectrometry. The geochronological and geological implications of the characterization experiments, which are presented here, will be considered once the dose rate is evaluated accurately.

References

- [1] E. Aşlar et al., Applied Radiation and Isotopes, 129, 142-151 (2017)
- [2] R.H. Biswas et al., Earth and Planetary Science Letters, 495,56-58 (2018)
- [3] G. King et al., Chemical Geology, 446, 3-7 (2016)
- [4] E.G. Yukihara et al., Radiation Measurements, 120, 274-280 (2018)

OP-22. Investigation of dosimetric properties of natural salt minerals by examining them with TL, ESR techniques

Yasemin Kavas, Eren Şahiner

Ankara University Institute of Nuclear Sciences

Corresponding Author e-mail: yaseminkavas@gmail.com

It is intended to study the artificially irradiated and natural TL/ESR properties of natural salt minerals. In this context, reproducibility, thermal/non-thermal damping, sensitivity, investigation of the available dose limits, linearity indices of natural salt minerals were examined. Radiation-sensitive signals were investigated by examining irradiated and natural ESR signals.

In this study, TL/ESR signal measurements of a total of 12 salt minerals, including samples obtained from salt deposits in the Himalaya, Asal Lake and Central Anatolia region, were examined for their dosimetric properties. For TL measurements, salt samples were gently crushed in agat pestle and turned into grains and sifted in special sieves and ~125-160 µm grains were obtained by screening. For all other experiments except natural thermoluminescence and ESR signal measurements, the salt samples were pre-annealed at 500 °C for 1 hour. During the TL measurement phase, all samples were weighed in steel containers on a precision balance and prepared in equal masses. For ESR measurements, the annealed salt samples were placed in 3mm diameter Quartz sample tubes cleaned with alcohol as ~1gr precisely. Thermo Scientific Harshaw TLD 3500 system was used for TL signal measurements and Bruker EMX ESR Spectroscopy was used for ESR signal measurements. Elsec 9010 Irradiation Unit was used for annealing of salt samples.

As a result of artificial irradiation of 25 mGy, 3 discrete TL peaks were formed in MCKTJ, KT, HT, ST, CIT, TGT, KKT salts and these TL peaks were observed at approximately 125-145 °C, 295-310 °C, 420-450 °C. It has been observed that it occurs at °C. As a result of artificial irradiation of 10 Gy, it was observed that there were 2 separate TL peaks in all natural salt samples and these TL peaks were formed between approximately 100-105 °C, 200-295 °C. When the natural ESR obtained as a result of the ESR measurements of all salt samples examined and the ESR signal intensities obtained as a result of 15 Gy artificial irradiation were compared, a decrease was observed in the signal intensity except for the KT salt. When the natural signal intensities were examined, it was observed that there was a ~20-fold difference between the highest signal strength and the lowest signal strength. While the g factor values of natural ESR signals were determined between 1.9817-2.0028, these values were observed to be between 1.9817-2.0045 in irradiated salt samples.

Keywords: thermoluminescence, electron spin resonance, natural salt material

References

1. Deniz, K., Kadioglu, Y.K., 2021 "Geochemistry of salts and the effect of trace elements on human health: Turkey salt resources". International Journal of Environmental Analytical Chemistry (DOI: 10.1080/03067319.2021.1934830).
2. G.S. Polymeris et al., 2011. "Dissolution and subsequent re-crystallization as zeroing mechanism, thermal properties and component resolved dose response of salt (NaCl) for retrospective dosimetry". Applied Radiation and Isotopes 69 (2011) 1255–1262.
3. Spooner, N.A et al., 2011. "Analysis of luminescence from common salt (NaCl) for application to retrospective dosimetry". Radiat. Meas. 46, 1856e1861.
4. Şahiner, E. 2015. Paleosismolojik Çalışmalarda TL/OSL ve ESR Yöntemlerinin Kullanılması: Kütahya-Simav ve Kuzey Anadolu Fay Hattı. Ankara Üniversitesi Fizik Mühendisliği, Doktora Tezi, Ankara, 216s.
5. P.C. Hunter, N.A. Spooner, B.W. Smith, D.F. Creighton. 2012, "Investigation of emission spectra, dose response and stability of luminescence from NaCl", Radiat. Meas. 47, 820–824.

OP-23. Investigation Of Dosimetric Properties and Performance Test Of Al₂O₃ Luminescence Dosimeters For Diagnostic Radiology Energy Range

Jalil Pazhuhish¹, Eren Şahiner¹

*¹Institute of Nuclear Science, Ankara University, 06100, Beşevler, Ankara, Türkiye
Pjalil20@gmail.com*

In this study, the TL glow curve kinetic parameters of α -Al₂O₃:C dosimeter were calculated numerically (computerized glow curve deconvolution CGCD) and experimentally using different methods such as initial rise, fractional glow, and various heating rates. The deconvolution analyses of glow curve investigated according to the general order of kinetics (GOK) model. As a result, activation energy of the dosimetric TL peak, ($T_{max}=170^{\circ}\text{C}$) were obtained as ~ 1 eV with 14% uncertainty both numerically and experimentally. Furthermore, the dosimetric properties of this dosimeter investigated under ⁹⁰Sr/⁹⁰Y beta source (1Gy-1kGy) and x-ray. A linear behavior up to 40 Gy was observed.

Keywords: thermoluminescence, α -Al₂O₃:C, dosimeter, kinetic parameters

OP-24. Determination of the dosimetric properties of boron nitride by TL/OSL techniques

Hakan Çağan Öztoprak¹, Gaye Özgür Çakal¹, Sule Kaya-Keleş¹, Eren Şahiner¹, Georgios S. Polymeris²

¹ Institute of Nuclear Sciences, Ankara University, Besevler, 06100, Ankara, Turkey

² Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology NCSR Demokritos, 15310 Agia Paraskevi, Attika, Greece

*Corresponding Author e-mail: sule.kaya@ankara.edu.tr

Different materials yielding intense thermoluminescence (TL) and/or optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) properties are usually investigated in personal, clinical, or environmental dosimetry research. Examples involve LiF:Ti,Mn, CaF₂:Dy, CaSO₄:Dy, LiBO₄:Cu,In; all these can be listed among these artificial dosimeters. Research on boron products has an increasing interest due to their vast application areas and their added value to the end product. Boron nitride (BN), one of the special boron products, having two different crystal structures, namely cubic boron nitride (c-BN) and hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN) was examined in this study in terms of luminescence behavior as a possible passive dosimeter. First, h-BN and c-BN samples were characterized in terms of structure and morphology using XRD and SEM-EDS respectively. TL, IR-OSL and Blue-OSL properties were studied, using a Risø TL/OSL DA-20 system having an internal ⁹⁰Sr/⁹⁰Y beta source with a dose rate of 115 mGy/s. During the acquisition of luminescence signals, a HOYA U-340 optical filter was used. Specific properties of all three luminescence signals were studied for both BN samples, such as radiation dose-response, reproducibility, minimum detectable dose (MDD) values, and fading (only for TL). Trap parameters in the TL glow curve were examined by the fractional glow technique and the deconvolution methods. In addition, residual TL (RTL) glow curves after OSL were investigated. For TL measurements, the minimum detectable dose (MDD) values of h-BN and c-BN samples were found to vary depending on the analysis and the stimulation mode. In the measurements made without preheating, it was observed that c-BN had a distinct peak at 130 °C and satellite peaks were observed at temperatures above 200 °C in the glow curve. On the other hand, h-BN was observed to consist of many overlapped peaks. In the measurements with preheat up to 200 °C, the dosimetric properties of the more stable peaks of c-BN were investigated. According to the results, the suitability of both samples for being used as a dosimeter was examined.

Keywords: Boron nitride, luminescence, dosimeter, radiation dose response, TL, OSL

OP-25. Development of domestic irradiator in compliance with ISO4037 standard

Levent Aksu¹, Ergun Togay²

¹*RADLAB Inc., Turkiye*

²*Radiation Protection Association, Turkiye*

Radiation measuring devices used in various radiation applications and dosimeters are used to determine the radiation doses received by those working in the radiation fields. Calibration of radiation devices and dosimeters at certain intervals are required.

Standard Cesium-137 radioactive source was used in this work. Irradiations can be carried out between 100 mSv and 1 uSv with a sensitivity of 1 mm using a computer-controlled linear rail. X0, X1, X10, X100, X1000 lead attenuation disks are used to reduce the collimator and doses in accordance with ISO 4037.

Uncertainty was calculated as a result of the measurements made within the scope of ISO 17025 Laboratory accreditation.

Keywords: ISO 4037, irradiator, dosimetry, dosimeter, accreditation

OP-26. Radiometric characterization of Amazonian sediments

Sonia H. Tatum^{1*}, Márcio Yee¹, Emílio A.A. Soares², Jefferson J. de Souza², Emanuele D.O. Grudzin¹, René R. Rocca¹, Carolina P. Fernandes¹, Matheus T. Mathias¹, Nagabhushana K.R.¹, Marcelo S. Rocha², Luis A.C. Lopez², Diego W.P. Venâncio², Solange dos S. Costa², Casimiro S. Munita³, Rogério B. Ribeiro³

¹ Federal University of São Paulo/Marine Science Department, Rua Carvalho de Mendonça, 144, 11070-100, Santos, Brazil

² Federal University of Amazon/ Geosciences Department, Av. Rodrigo Otavio 6200, 69077-000, Manaus, Brazil

³ Instituto de Pesquisas Energéticas e Nucleares IPEN-CNEN/SP/Department of Nuclear Chemical, Av. Prof. Lineu Prestes, 2242, 05508-000, São Paulo, Brazil

*Corresponding Author e-mail: sonia.tatumi@unifesp.br

Sediments taken from fluvial terraces of the Rio Negro, Barcelos city, Amazonian, were analysed in relation to their natural radioisotope contents. For this, the technique gamma spectroscopy was used. In addition, crystallographic analysis was performed using X-ray diffraction.

The natural radioactive contents (U, Th and K-40) were determined by γ -spectroscopy, and the spectra of the samples from sediments, were measured with the hyper-pure germanium (HPGe) detector with ultra-low background shield of Canberra Inc. and compared with the soils patterns spectra JR-1, JB-3, JG1a and JG-3. A mass of approximately 60 g of dry sample is inserted into a sample holder and sealed for two weeks, to reach secular equilibrium, to be measured during 42 h, in the case of much low content the samples was measured during 100 h. XRD diffraction measurements were carried out with a Miniflex 300 diffractometer of Higaku Corporation. The measurements were made in the range of 10 to 60° (2 θ), step of 0.02°, time 2.5 s and at RT. Twenty-one samples collected at various points and depths were studied, ranging from 60 to 2640 cm. The γ spectroscopy results showed that 38% of the samples contain natural radioisotopes in very low concentrations, in the case of Th they ranged from 0.75 to 2.47 ppm, the U from 0.35 to 0.94 ppm and for K-40 four samples showed results below the equipment detectable limit, the other up to 0.22 %. The other 62% ones had a Th concentration from 4.70 to 14.8 ppm, U from 1.03 to 4.19 ppm and for K40 was from 0.13 to 0.71%. It is observed that the concentration of K-40 is extremely low in all samples, it is a characteristic of the sediments found in the region [1]. XRD results corroborate to the low values of K-40, as it is observed that the samples are practically composed of quartz from the hexagonal system (code reference 01-085-1053). In this way the samples do not contain feldspar, which usually has potassium in its crystal lattice. In the samples with the highest content of radioisotopes, in addition to the quartz, other silicates were found as zirconia silicate, ZrSiO₄ (reference code 01-071-0991), from the tetrahedral system, lithium aluminium silicate, LiAlSiO₄ (reference code 01-073-0257), hexagonal system and titanium sodium silicate, Na₂TiSiO₅ (reference code 00-019-1250), orthorhombic system.

The sediments results characterization indicate different concentrations of minerals present in their composition, providing distinct values of radioactive isotopes. There was no dependence of these concentrations in relation to depth, thus there is no evidence that the isotopes have gone to greater depths over time due to leaching, which would be problematic for the dating of these samples, suggesting that they could be deposits from different sources.

Keywords: fluvial sediment, Amazon, radioactive isotopes, XRD

References

[1] Tatum, Sonia Hatsue, Dilce de Fátima Rossetti, and Emílio Alberto Amaral Soares, eds. *Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL) Dating in the Amazonian Wetlands*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2020.

OP-27. Determination of NaI(Tl) scintillator calibration factors for field application based on MCNP6 modelling

Amalia Chambon^{1*}, E. B. Klinkby¹, M. Bu¹, A. S. Murray², M. Kook¹, H. Olesen¹, K. B. Nielsen¹

¹ *Department of Physics, Technical University of Denmark, Roskilde, Denmark*

² *Nordic Laboratory for Luminescence Dating, Aarhus University, Roskilde, Denmark*

**Corresponding Author e-mail: amacha@dtu.dk*

NaI(Tl) scintillation detectors are widely used for field measurements of gamma rays due to their robustness and low cost; at least in case of high activity concentrations or large samples, they can provide accurate measurements. Measurements of naturally occurring activity concentrations of ⁴⁰K, and of the decay series of ²³⁸U and ²³²Th, are of interest in the earth sciences in general, and in particular, NaI(Tl) scintillator-based gamma spectrometers can be used for the low cost determination of burial dose rates in natural geological samples [1]. We are currently developing a robust, portable, and wireless detector specifically intended for field measurement of natural radionuclide concentrations and dose rates.

One of the challenges in developing such an instrument is reliable calibration. Currently most calibrations of field instruments depend on infinite matrices of known K, U, Th activity concentrations, in either a 4 π or 2 π geometry [2]. There are only a limited number of these facilities available in the world, and for most laboratories repeated access for regular calibration is clearly difficult. We are now investigating an alternative approach, based on the measurement of small samples (~300 g) containing well-known activity concentrations of only K or U or Th, and MCNP modelling to convert the observed spectra to those expected from specific activity concentrations in an infinite 4 π geometry.

The determination of the infinite matrix calibration spectra is based on three main steps:

- MCNP simulations of NaI spectra for individual K, U and Th wax impregnated calibration cups of known major element composition, validated against observed spectra.
- MCNP simulations of individual K, U, Th spectra expected from field measurement (infinite matrix) for a chosen major element composition [3].
- The resulting spectra ratios are used to multiply the observed calibration cup spectra to give predicted infinite matrix calibration spectra.

These modelled calibration spectra are validated by (i) combining in appropriate proportions, and comparing with measured spectra from infinite matrices of known mixed K, U, Th composition, and (ii) by deriving these (known) K, U, Th concentrations using least squares fitting of the calibration spectra to the measured spectra (after subtraction of instrument background) [4].

This modelling approach to calibration also allows us to investigate the sensitivity of our analytical results to variations in water content and major element composition.

Keywords: NaI(Tl) detector, field measurement, calibration, MCNP

References

- [1] M. Bu et al., Radiation Measurements 120 (2018) 253-259
- [2] D.C. Stromswold, Journal of Radioanalytical and Nuclear Chemistry 194 (1995), 393-401
- [3] P. H. G. M. Hendriks et al., Applied Radiation and Isotopes 57 (2002), 449-457
- [4] M. Bu et al., Geochronometria 48 (2011), 161-170

OP-28. Increasing our understanding of Holocene dune activity in the Thar Desert, India using a portable luminescence reader

Shashank Nitundil^{1*}, Abi Stone¹, Aayush Srivastava², Tim Kinnaird², Komal Songara³

¹ *Department of Geography, University of Manchester, Manchester, UK*

² *School of Earth and Environmental Sciences, University of St. Andrews, St Andrews, UK*

³ *Water Resources Department, Government of Rajasthan, India*

**Corresponding Author e-mail: shashank.nitundil@postgrad.manchester.ac.uk*

Understanding future changes to dune activity in the densely populated Thar Desert, India will be aided by a comprehensive understanding of its complex dune developmental history. This requires a dunefield-scale investigation with sufficient sampling resolution to provide insights into the spatio-temporal variations in dune accumulation history. However, establishing dune accumulation histories using traditional chronological techniques is time and resource intensive. For this reason, this study utilises rapid-age estimates, derived from portable luminescence reader signals (port-OSL), calibrated via a regression against existing laboratory-based luminescence ages. 222 samples were collected from ten linear dunes on a 100 km transect in western Thar, a hyperarid region that lacks robust dune chronologies. Port-OSL (IRSL: BSL signal ratios of 0.29 to 0.35), along with particle size analysis (moderately–well-sorted medium to fine sand) suggests a similar provenance for all samples, which demonstrates the feasibility of using calibrated port-OSL measurements for rapid age estimates. Additionally, the influence of bulk sample moisture content on port-OSL signals was investigated, showing an attenuation of 30% up to a threshold of 1% moisture by weight.

Calibration of port-OSL measurements was carried out using ages of samples with previously established chronologies from central Thar ($n=40$)^[1] as well as newly dated samples collected as part of this study ($n=4$) and showed a good fit using a linear regression model approach^[2] ($R^2=0.84$). Based on calibration, all 222 samples were within the Holocene, ranging between 150 and 11000 years old and corresponding to port-OSL BSL totals of 0.2 million and 14 million counts. The spatio-temporal patterns of dune accumulation seen are that eastern flanks are younger and have a higher accumulation rate than the western flanks, suggesting an eastward migration of the dunes. A period of high accumulation between ~ 8 ka and 6 ka in six of the dunes, corresponds to the Holocene warm period during which the Indian summer monsoon winds were stronger^[3]. This study demonstrates the utility of the port-OSL technique for determining the spatial variability in dune accumulation at large spatial scales (~ 100 km) within the Thar desert.

References

- [1] Srivastava A, Durcan J, Thomas D. Analysis of late Quaternary linear dune development in the Thar Desert, India. *Geomorphology*. 2019; 344:90-98.
- [2] Stone A, Bateman M, Burrough S, Garzanti E, Limonta M, Radeff G et al. Using a portable luminescence reader for rapid age assessment of aeolian sediments for reconstructing dunefield landscape evolution in southern Africa. *Quaternary Geochronology*. 2019; 49:57-64.
- [3] Jiang W, Leroy S, Yang S, Zhang E, Wang L, Yang X et al. Synchronous Strengthening of the Indian and East Asian Monsoons in Response to Global Warming Since the Last Deglaciation. *Geophysical Research Letters*. 2019; 46(7):3944-3952.

OP-29. OTOR application in nano-sized luminophores; the impact of nano-crystallite sizes on the Thermoluminescence glow-curve shape, activation energies and kinetic parameters.

Efstathios Tsoutsoumanos^{1,2,*}, M. Saleh³, P.G. Konstantinidis⁴, V. Altunal⁶, P.D. Sahare⁵, Z. Yengigil⁶, T. Karakasidis¹, G. Kitis⁴, G.S. Polymeris²

¹ Condensed Matter Physics Laboratory, Physics Department, University of Thessaly, GR-35100, Lamia, Greece

² Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, NCSR "Demokritos", GR-15310, Ag. Paraskevi (Athens), Greece

³ Department of Materials Science, University of Milan-Bicocca, MI-20125, Milan, Italy

⁴ Nuclear and Elementary Particle Physics Laboratory, Physics Department, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki,

⁵ Department of Physics and Astrophysics, University of Delhi, 110007, Delhi, India

⁶ Physics Department, Çukurova University, 01330, Adana, Turkey

Nanostructured materials can be defined as solids with nanoscale or partly nanoscale microstructures in terms of crystalline diameter. Over the past years, they have received a major identifiable activity in many different fields of materials science due to their unique properties and characteristics. In Stimulated Luminescence, despite the voluminous literature studying dosimetric properties of nanostructured materials, there is a limited number of studies dealing with either signal characteristics or comparison with the corresponding features of their micro-structured counterparts. Specifically, in Thermoluminescence (TL) cases that extensively study the geometrical signal processing, the kinetic parameters of certain TL peaks along with the possible dependence of the activation energy on the crystallite size fraction are missing from the literature.

The present work attempts to fill this gap by studying either TL glow curve or glow peak features of nanostructured luminescence solids that are suitable for radiation dosimetry, using both Deconvolution analysis and Peak Shape Methods (PSM) where the latter is feasible. The study has been extended to complex TL glow curves, besides cases of single, unique prominent TL peak exists. The materials of the present study include BeO:Li,Na [1], LiF:Mg,Cu,P, NaLi₂PO₄:Eu, K₃Na(SO₄)₂:Eu, CaSO₄:Eu and other nanomaterials indicate TL glow curves with single TL peaks, such as Ba_{0.97}Ca_{0.03}SO₄:Eu, LiNaSO₄:Eu, K₂Ca₂(SO₄)₃:Eu [2-7]; finally, natural Fluorapatite originated from Mexico was also investigated [8]. Special emphasis will be devoted to the activation energy (E_a), the ratio of the re-trapping to the recombination probabilities, signifying the parameter in the One Trap - One Recombination center (OTOR) model indicating the kinetic order, along with the temperature that corresponds to the maximum intensity (T_m), as the crystallite diameter gradually decreases in size. While the analysis imposes several interesting cases on the implementation of the results, the study has shown that under different crystallite sizes a minor signal shift is observed to lower temperatures, without significant TL glow curve shape alterations.

References

- [1] Altunal, V., Yengigil, Z., Tuken, T., Depci, T., Ozdemir, A., Guckan, V., Bulur, E. (2018). Optically stimulated luminescence characteristics of BeO nanoparticles synthesized by sol-gel method. *Radiation Measurements*. doi:10.1016/j.radmeas.2018.08.009
- [2] Salah, N., Sahare, P. D., Lochab, S. P., & Kumar, P. (2006). TL and PL studies on : Dy nanoparticles. *Radiation Measurements*, 41(1), 40–47. doi:10.1016/j.radmeas.2005.07.026
- [3] Salah, N., Sahare, P. D., & Rupasov, A. A. (2007). Thermoluminescence of nanocrystalline LiF:Mg,Cu,P. *Journal of Luminescence*, 124(2), 357–364. doi:10.1016/j.jlumin.2006.04.004
- [4] Sahare, P. D., Ranjan, R., Salah, N., & Lochab, S. P. (2007). K₃Na(SO₄)₂:Eu nanoparticles for high dose of ionizing radiation. *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, 40(3), 759–764. doi:10.1088/0022-3727/40/3/011
- [5] Pandey, A., Sahare, P. D., Bakare, J. S., Lochab, S. P., Singh, F., & Kanjilal, D. (2003). Thermoluminescence and photoluminescence characteristics of nanocrystalline LiNaSO₄:Eu phosphor. *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, 36(19), 2400–2406. doi:10.1088/0022-3727/36/19/014
- [6] Sahare, P. D., Bakare, J. S., Dhole, S. D., Ingale, N. B., & Rupasov, A. A. (2010). Synthesis and luminescence properties of nanocrystalline LiF:Mg,Cu,P phosphor. *Journal of Luminescence*, 130(2), 258–265. doi:10.1016/j.jlumin.2009.08.018
- [7] Salah, N., Sahare, P. D., Nawaz, S., & Lochab, S. P. (2004). Luminescence characteristics of K₂Ca₂(SO₄)₃:Eu,Tb micro- and nanocrystalline phosphor. *Radiation Effects and Defects in Solids*, 159(5), 321–334. doi:10.1080/10420150310001633648
- [8] Polymeris, G. S., Sfampa, I. K., Niora, M., Stefanaki, E. C., Malletzidou, L., Giannoulatou, V., ... Kitis, G. (2018). Anomalous fading in TL, OSL and TA – OSL signals of Durango apatite for various grain size fractions; from micro to nano scale. *Journal of Luminescence*, 195, 216–224. doi:10.1016/j.jlumin.2017.11.034

OP-30. A luminescence imaging instrument for rapid *in-situ* assessment of bleaching depth in rocks

Myungho Kook^{1*}, Elaine Louise Sellwood¹, Mayank Jain¹

¹*Department of Physics, Technical University of Denmark, Roskilde, Denmark*

**Corresponding Author e-mail: myko@dtu.dk*

Rock surface dating technique is being increasingly applied to constrain chronologies of otherwise challenging-to-date geological and archaeological deposits. However, often in rock surface burial dating, a majority of sampled rocks do not show desirable characteristics, e.g. luminescence sensitivity, transparency or sufficient light exposure prior to burial. Similarly, in rock surface exposure dating, it is difficult to plan a sampling strategy in the field without knowing in advance the relative exposure history of different bedrock surfaces. Currently, such knowledge can be obtained only by laboratory measurements after the field work has been concluded. An instrument that could screen samples in the field for their suitability for rock surface dating would lead to a huge saving on both time and expenses. Here we report on the development of such an instrument based on Infra-Red Photoluminescence (IRPL) [1] and Infra-Red Stimulated Luminescence (IRSL) signals, for rapid *in-situ* imaging of luminescence-depth profiles in rocks. The non-destructive IRPL signal is particularly attractive because of the high sensitivity of IRPL measurements, its robustness with respect to accidental exposure while sampling, and the non-necessity of (pre)heating [2]. Furthermore, IRPL and IRSL signals complement each other in terms of bleachability, and a combination of the two can help in extraction of stable yet rapidly bleachable signals such as Δ IRPL [3].

Our instrument consists of two light sources (830 nm laser and 850 nm LED), a filter changer, optical lens, a camera and a laptop, and it is powered by an 18 V battery commonly used for power tools. A rock is cut perpendicular to the (prior) exposed surface and placed on the stage followed by IRSL and IRPL imaging of up to 8×7 cm sized sample surfaces. Instead of an ionising radiation source, signal normalisation is based on using signals of different bleachabilities so as to account for spatial variations in luminescence sensitivity [4]. An analyses software with the graphical user interface has been developed in order to quickly generate luminescence-depth profiles, and assess bleaching depths at the sampling site itself. It takes ~20 minutes, including sampling time, to obtain a bleaching profile per rock. We carried out three field excursions in Denmark, at the Risø beach, a gravel pit in Mogenstrup, and a geopark in western Jutland, for testing our portable luminescence-imaging instrument. These imaging results, the basic design and performance of the instruments will be presented and discussed here.

Keywords: Luminescence imaging, In-situ, Rock surface dating

References

- [1] Prasad, A. K., Poolton, N. R., Kook, M., & Jain, M. (2017). Optical dating in a new light: a direct, non-destructive probe of trapped electrons. *Scientific Reports*, 7(1), 1-15.
- [2] Kumar, R., Kook, M., & Jain, M. (2021). Sediment dating using infrared photoluminescence. *Quaternary Geochronology*, 62, 101147.
- [3] Jain, M., Kumar, R., Kook, M., 2020, A novel coupled RPL/OSL system to understand the dynamics of the metastable states, *Scientific Reports*. 10, 1, 15 p., 15565
- [4] Sellwood, E.L., Kook, M, and Jain, M, 2022, Rapid *in-situ* assessment of luminescence bleaching depths in rocks for deriving burial and exposure chronologies of rock surfaces, *Quaternary Geochronology*, 67, 101227

OP-31. Investigation of past hydrological extremes (HEX) using river flood plain sediments: Sakarya River, NW Türkiye

Hilal Okur^{1*}, Mehmet Korhan Erturaç¹, Meltem Çelen¹, Eren Şahiner², Zeki Bora Ön³, Nesibe Köse⁴, Sena Akçer-Ön³, Özlem Makaroğlu⁵, Nurgül Karlıoğlu-Kılıç⁴, Hüseyin Tuncay Güner⁴, Emrah Bulut⁶, Fatma Küçük⁶, Burçin Aşkın Gümüş⁷, Alper Gürbüz⁸, Mehmet Salim Öncel¹

¹ Gebze Technical University, Institute of Earth and Marine Sciences, Kocaeli, Türkiye

² Ankara University, Earth Sciences Application and Research Center, Luminescence Dating Researches Laboratory

³ Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University, Department of Geological Engineering, Muğla, Türkiye

⁴ İstanbul University-Cerrahpaşa, Faculty of Forestry, İstanbul, Türkiye

⁵ İstanbul University- Cerrahpaşa, Department of Geophysical Engineering, İstanbul, Türkiye

⁶ Sakarya University, Research Development and Application Center, Sakarya, Türkiye

⁷ Gazi University, Faculty of Science, Department of Biology, Ankara, Türkiye

⁸ Niğde Ömer Halisdemir University, Department. of Geological Engineering, Niğde, Türkiye

*hilalokur@gtu.edu.tr

Hydrological extremes and critical events (HEX) are defined as abrupt changes in river's discharge above (flood) or below (drought) average threshold. HEX studies now extend beyond the instrumental (long term monitoring) data towards compiling historical record and investigation of fluvial record for past hydrological and climatological changes in the river's basin. We detail the recent floodplain of the Sakarya River at Adapazarı Basin, east of Marmara Sea in NW Türkiye.

The unique tectonic position of the basin enabled in deposition of 4.5 meters of fine-medium grained sediment since 1200 CE. This time-period corresponds to the Little Ice Age (LIA) and the ruling period of the Ottoman Empire. Our multi-disciplinary and multi-proxy (grain size, mineralogical, geochemical analysis, magnetism, pollen assemblages) approach enabled us to determine the palaeohydrology of the river and in contrast detection of the HEX events. All the determined events and episodes were put in a high-resolution timescale with the help of luminescence, dendrochronology and radiocarbon dating methods.

The focus sedimentary record revealed that the Sakarya River experienced distinct long-duration optimum flow and drought episodes with intermittent flooding events for the last 600 years. These episodes are closely comparable with the published local and regional paleoclimatic record but in-contrast not with the historical social disturbances.

This study is funded by TÜBİTAK 121Y110 project.

Keywords: Palaeohydrology, Flood Plain, Hydrological extremes (HEX), Little Ice Age, Luminescence dating, Sakarya River

Online Conference

POSTER PRESENTATIONS

PP-01. Firing temperature estimation of archeological burned materials using sensitivity change of OSL optically stimulated luminescence

Yorinao Shitaoka¹, Yasuhiro Takai², Ken'ichi Kobayashi³

¹*Rissho University*

²*Enecom Co. Ltd., Japan*

³*Chuo University*

The firing temperatures of archeological burned materials were estimated from the sensitivity change of optically stimulated luminescence (OSL). If no heating occurs, then the OSL intensity does not change the OSL sensitivity to the radiation dose. This characteristic is used for firing temperature estimation.

Assuming the past temperature of heat exposure as T_0 and the temperature of heat treatment by the electric furnace as T_1 , then for the same sample with the same radiation dose, when the heat treatment temperature by the electric furnace does not exceed the past heat treatment temperature ($T_0 > T_1$ or $T_0 = T_1$), the sensitivity changes of the OSL intensity of the "heat treated sample" to the OSL intensity of the "no heating sample" are negligible or small. By contrast, when the heat treatment temperature by the electric furnace exceeds the past heat treatment temperature ($T_0 < T_1$), the OSL intensity undergoes a sensitivity change. Also, the "heat treated sample" shows systematic changes with respect to the "no heating sample". Cases in which the temperature at which the OSL intensity begins to increase after the OSL intensity remains constant and cases in which the OSL intensity is almost identical to that of the "no heating sample" are particularly examined. Based on those findings, one can estimate that the past heat-treated temperature is near the temperature at which the OSL intensity sensitivity begins to increase.

Firing temperature estimation using the OSL sensitivity change was evaluated using an artificially annealed sample. The findings show good agreement between the annealed temperature and the estimated firing temperature. Moreover, because of the XRD pattern, the estimated temperatures show good agreement with results found for thermal transformation of natural clay minerals.

The method using OSL sensitivity change is useful to estimate the firing temperatures of archeological burned materials. Our poster presentation will announce results of firing temperature estimation for pottery of the Jomon period at Japan. The results were within approximately 500–900°C.

Keywords: OSL, XRD, pottery, temperature

PP-02. Evaluation of the ESR intensity associated to the Al centre measured in optically bleached coarse quartz grains: a comparative study

Ben Arous, E.^{1,2,3}, **Duttine, M.**⁴, **Duval, M.**^{2,5}

¹Max Planck Institute for the Science of Human History, Pan-African Evolution Research Group, Jena, Germany

²Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana (CENIEH), Burgos, Spain

³Museum national d'Histoire naturelle, Histoire naturelle de l'Homme préhistorique, Paris, France

⁴Institut de Chimie de la Matière Condensée de Bordeaux (ICMCB), Univ. Bordeaux, CNRS, Bordeaux INP, Pessac, France

⁵Australian Research Centre for Human Evolution (ARCHE), Griffith University, Brisbane, Australia

Since the pioneering study by Yokoyama et al. (1985), ESR dating of optically bleached quartz grain has been mostly based on the measurement of the Aluminium (Al) signal, while the use of the various Ti centres through a combined approach has only become increasingly popular about a couple of decades later. Following Toyoda & Falguères (2003), the ESR intensity of the Al signal has been traditionally extracted from the measurement of the peak-to-peak amplitude between the top of the first peak and the bottom of the 16th peak from $g = 2.0185$ to $g = 1.9928$ (Method 1). However, other fundamental studies (e.g. Kabacińska & Timar-Gabor, 2022) have shown that this traditional approach could overestimate the Al signal intensity because of the presence of interfering signals, recommending thus instead the use of the absorption lines around $g=2.0603$ (Kabacińska & Timar-Gabor, 2022; Duttine, 2005). For example, Kabacińska & Timar-Gabor (2022) proposed a peak-to-baseline amplitude measurement in that area (Method 2), whereas Duttine (2005) suggested the double integration of the low-field component of the first-derivative signal. While only a few comparative studies are available to evaluate the potential of each approach, the present work aims at contributing to fill this gap by selecting and analysing several coarse (120-200 μm) quartz grains from Early Pleistocene to modern-age sediment samples. The Al ESR intensities were evaluated following Methods 1 and 2, in addition to Methods 3 (peak-to-baseline amplitude centred around $g=2.0603$ after a baseline correction using a cubic function) and 4 (integration of the curve as used in Method 3). Resulting Dose Response Curves (DRCs) and corresponding D_E estimates were compared, providing essential additional baseline data in order to help defining the most appropriate method to measure the ESR intensity of the Al signal for dating purpose.

References

- [1] Duttine, M. (2005). *Recherche de provenance de quartz et d'obsidiennes préhistoriques en Europe occidentale. Apports de la résonance paramagnétique électronique (RPE)*. PhD thesis. Université Bordeaux Montaigne.
- [2] Kabacińska, Z., & Timar-Gabor, A. (2022). Dating Sediments by EPR Using Al-h Centre: A Comparison between the Properties of Fine (4–11 μm) and Coarse (>63 μm) Quartz Grains. *Molecules* 2022, Vol. 27, Page 2683, 27(9), 2683. <https://doi.org/10.3390/MOLECULES27092683>
- [3] Toyoda, S., & Falguères, C. (2003). The method to represent the ESR signal intensity of the aluminium hole center in quartz for the purpose of dating. *Advances in ESR Applications*, 20, 7–10.
- [4] Yokoyama, Y., Falguères, C., & Quaegebeur, J. P. (1985). ESR dating of quartz from Quaternary sediments : first attempts. *Nuclear Tracks*, 10(4–6), 921–928.

PP-03. Testing infrared radiofluorescence dating on polymineral fine-grains from the Luochuan loess-palaeosol sequence, Chinese Loess Plateau.

Gwynlyn Buchanan¹, Tsukamoto, S.¹, Zhang, J.¹, Long, H.²

¹*Leibniz Institute for Applied Geophysics, 30655, Hannover, Germany.*

²*State Key Laboratory of Lake Science and Environment, Nanjing Institute of Geography and Limnology, Chinese Academy of Sciences (NIGLAS), Nanjing, 210008, China.*

To date, infrared radiofluorescence (IR-RF) dating has yet to be systematically evaluated on polymineral fine-grains. In this study we investigate the IR-RF signals generated from polymineral fine-grains (4-11 μm) on 6 loess samples (~30 to 480 ka) from the Luochuan loess-palaeosol sequence on the Chinese Loess Plateau. Both the natural and regenerative IR-RF signals were uncharacteristically flat with little vertical dynamic range using both bleaching durations of 1500 s and 20 000 s between the natural and regenerative measurements. X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analyses showed that the polymineral fine-grains were dominated by quartz and Na-feldspars. The mid-grain (38-63 μm) sample set were further prepared and the K-feldspar and Na-feldspar fractions were separated and measured. The IR-RF signals from the K-feldspar mid-grains exhibit the characteristic IR-RF decaying exponential signal, while the IR-RF signal from the Na-feldspar mid-grains is flat with little dynamic range. This suggests that the Na-feldspar generated signal dominates the polymineral fine-grain measurement. The ages calculated from these signals show that, despite the flat nature of the curves, on average the polymineral fine-grain ages (with both bleaching settings) were generally consistent with the reference ages up to 300 ka. However, due to the flat nature of the curves the age uncertainties were relatively high. The consistency of the results using the two bleaching durations indicates that the bleaching duration has a less significant role in the IR-RF dating with polymineral fine-grains than in the coarse grains (63-150 μm), as suggested by a previous study. Additionally the ages calculated from the IR-RF signals on the K-feldspar mid-grains (bleaching duration of 1500s) were consistent with the reference ages up to 200 ka and of the Na-feldspar mid-grains up to 360 ka, with the Na-feldspar mid-grains consistently performing better than the K-feldspar mid-grains. Dose recovery tests were undertaken on all samples and protocols, and were not able to predict which measurements would perform better when compared with the reference ages. Despite the flat IR-RF signals due to the dominance of Na-feldspar in the samples, dating using polymineral fine-grains in this instance was possible up to 300 ka and could potentially prove to be more successful in polymineral fine-grains with more favorable feldspar compositions.

PP-04. An empirical study on the variability of luminescence ages for coeval loess samples

Constantin, D.^{1*}, Begy, R.^{1,4}, Vandenberghe, D.A.G.J.², Veres, D.³, Timar-Gabor, A.^{1,4}

¹ *Institute for Interdisciplinary Research in Bio-Nano-Sciences, Babeş-Bolyai University, Treboniu Laurian 42, 400271 Cluj-Napoca, Romania*

² *Ghent University, Department of Geology, Laboratory of Mineralogy and Petrology, Krijgslaan 281 (S8), B-9000 Ghent, Belgium*

³ *Romanian Academy, Institute of Speleology, Clinicilor 5, 400006 Cluj-Napoca, Romania*

⁴ *Faculty of Environmental Sciences and Engineering, Babeş-Bolyai University, Fântânele 30, 400327 Cluj-Napoca, Romania*

*Corresponding author. E-mail: daniela.constantin@ubbcluj.ro

An increasing number of studies exploit the advantages of a single-aliquot regenerative-dose protocol (SAR) for equivalent dose determination with sampling at relatively closely-spaced vertical intervals (of the order of 10-30 cm). The resulting ages are, at least in principal, ideally suited for age-depth modelling. The modelling, however, is made difficult owing to the variety and complex combination of uncertainties associated with luminescence dating. Moreover, we previously reported on a variability in age results for coeval loess samples that is significantly larger than expected and remains to be understood.

In this study, we examine this problem explicitly by observing the degree of precision and accuracy that can be achieved by luminescence dating of multiple coeval loess samples of known age. The main goal is to improve our understanding of how luminescence ages are to be incorporated into age-depth models, thus increasing their robustness and accuracy.

Fourteen samples were taken at closely-spaced horizontal intervals from loess deposits immediately over- and underlying the Campanian Ignimbrite/Y5 tephra layer ($^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ dated to 39.2 ± 0.1 ka), as exposed at a section in the Lower Danube Basin in southeastern Europe. Luminescence analyses were carried out using the single-aliquot regenerative-dose (SAR) protocol and OSL signals from 63-90 μm quartz fraction. We report an average age of 47 ± 2 ka for the seven samples collected below the tephra layer and 42 ± 3 ka for the seven samples collected above it. The individual random and systematic uncertainties contributing to the individual ages vary from 2.4 % to 5.6 % and from 6.0% to 6.1 %, respectively. We obtain an improved overall precision on the age of the sedimentary context by calculating the weighted average age and combining the individual random and systematic uncertainties following Aitken (1985, Appendix B). Thus we report weighted average ages of 46 ka and 41 ka for the horizontally sampled sediment layers intercalating the ash layer and associated overall random uncertainties of 1.5 % and an overall systematic uncertainties of 6.1 %. The insights gained from this are discussed in relation to age-modelling studies of luminescence-dated paleoclimate archives, and loess deposits in particular.

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by a grant of the Romanian Ministry of Education and Research, CNCS – UEFISCDI, project number PN-III-P1-1.1-PD-2019-0895, within PNCDI III.

Keywords: luminescence dating; precision; random uncertainty; quartz

PP-05. Different Fitting Functions And Its Implications For Equivalent Dose Determination In Multiple Centers ESR Dating: A Case Study In Jiangnan Basin, Middle Yangtze River, Central China

Yawei Li^{1,2*}, **Chuanyi Wei**^{2,*}, **Changan Li**³, **Chunru Liu**², **Rujun Guo**³

¹ College of Tourism and Planning, Pingdingshan University, Pingdingshan, 467400, China

² State Key Laboratory of Earthquake Dynamics, Institute of Geology, China Earthquake Administration, Beijing 100029, China

³ School of Earth Sciences, China University of Geosciences, Wuhan 430074, China

*Corresponding Author e-mail: liyaweicug@163.com; chuanyiwei@ies.ac.cn

To examine different fitting functions and their implication for equivalent dose determination in multiple centers ESR dating approach. In this study, we collected 18 fluvial sediment samples derived from the Zhoulao core, which is located in the depocenter of Jiangnan Basin and is one of the most typical drilling cores in this region.

Different fitting functions (SSE EXP+LIN Ti-2) were performed on the Al center and Ti-Li center to obtain a precise equivalent dose. The results showed that equivalent does fit by different functions were consistent within the error range with low irradiation (<20000 Gy). Compared with the other functions, the SSE function yielded a higher adjusted r^2 and a lower error rate, which indicated that the SSE function may be superior to the EXP+LIN function for the Al center and could provide a goodness-of-fit equally for the Ti-Li center based on our data. SSE function could be an optimal fitting method for equivalent dose determination and reduce the maximum irritating dose significantly.

According to the equivalent dose, we suspect that the Ti-Li center may be more suitable for 600-1000 Gy sample dating. Both Al center and Ti-Li center deduce highly consistent equivalent dose for 1000-3000 Gy samples, While even older samples(> 3000 Gy), the Al center exhibit a great potential for ESR dating. Our results strengthen the understanding of fitting functions and dating range from different centers and provide a preferred scheme applied to sediments dating from boreholes.

Keywords: quartz; Al center; Ti-Li centers; different fitting functions; electron spin resonance (ESR) dating; equivalent dose; Zhoulao core

PP-06. Luminescence sensitivity of quartz, a tracer for aeolian transport? An example from the Ili Basin of SE Kazakhstan

Aditi K. Dave^{1,2*}, Saida Nigmatova⁴, Kathryn E. Fitzsimmons^{1,2}

¹*Department of Geosciences, University of Tübingen, 72076 Tübingen, Germany*

²*Research group for Terrestrial Palaeoclimates, Max Planck institute for Chemistry, Hahn-Meitner Weg-1, 55128 Mainz, Germany*

³*Institute of Geological Sciences K. Satpaeva, Ministry for Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan, Almaty, Kazakhstan*

**Corresponding Author email: aditikrishna.dave@gmail.com*

Luminescence sensitivity of quartz grains is often linked to the source rock (origin) and/ or the sedimentary history experienced by the quartz grains [1, 2]. Luminescence sensitivity of quartz is increasingly being investigated as an indicator of sediment transport pathways [3]. Understanding of processes that govern sediment transport is key to linking resulting depositional landforms and climate dynamics in a region. In an aeolian setting, this would imply the need to investigate the link between potential source and sink sediments within a sedimentary basin. In this context, the Ili basin of southeast (SE) Kazakhstan, with its extensive piedmont loess deposits and desert dunefields, provides an excellent case study for investigating aeolian earth-surface processes and their links to climate.

Quartz, being one of the most ubiquitous minerals in clastic sediments – makes an excellent candidate for tracing sediment movement. Here we investigate the luminescence sensitivity of fine grain quartz from loess deposits of varying ages, as well as from surface sediments collected from various depositional settings across the Ili Basin of SE Kazakhstan. We observe variation in the luminescence sensitivity of fine grain quartz extracted from loess of varying depositional ages, highlighting a likely difference in transport pathways. In order to validate our hypothesis, we compare our luminescence datasets from modern settings with more recent back-trajectory models for dust transport in the region [4], which in turn provides us an empirical understanding of modern aeolian earth-surface processes. Based on the luminescence sensitivity data, we extend our understanding of modern processes to investigate past aeolian transport pathways and evaluate the role of sediment recycling, and consequently homogenisation on the luminescence sensitivity of fine-grained quartz within a sedimentary Basin.

Keywords: Quartz, luminescence sensitivity, loess, aeolian transport processes

References

1. Sawakuchi, A.O., Blair, M.W., DeWitt, R., Faleiros, F.M., Hyppolito, T., Guedes, C.C.F., 2011. Thermal history versus sedimentary history: OSL sensitivity of quartz grains extracted from rocks and sediments. *Quaternary Geochronology* 6, 261–272.
2. Sawakuchi, A.O., Jain, M., Mineli, T.D., Nogueira, L., Bertassoli, D.J., Häggi, C., Sawakuchi, H.O., Pupim, F.N., Grohmann, C.H., Chiessi, C.M., Zabel, M., Mülitz, S., Mazoca, C.E.M., Cunha, D.F., 2018. Luminescence of quartz and feldspar fingerprints provenance and correlates with the source area denudation in the Amazon River basin. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 492, 152–162.
3. Gray, H. J., Jain, M., Sawakuchi, A. O., Mahan, S. A., & Tucker, G. E. (2019). Luminescence as a sediment tracer and provenance tool. *Reviews of Geophysics* 57, 987–1017.
4. Fitzsimmons, K.E., Nowatzki, M., Dave, A.K., Harder, H., 2020. Intersections between wind regimes, topography and sediment supply: Perspectives from aeolian landforms in Central Asia. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 540, 109531.

PP-07. ESR signals in recrystallized carbonates and their suitability for dating

Hao Ji¹, Chunru Liu¹, Peiquan Zhang², Chuanyi Wei¹, Gongming Yin¹

¹State Key Laboratory of Earthquake Dynamics, Institute of Geology, China Earthquake Administration, Beijing 100029, China

²Seismological Bureau of Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, Nanning 530022, China

Recrystallized carbonates produced by faulting have recently proved to be an ideal material for determining fault movement in carbonate rock areas using the ESR method, providing a new dating material for carbonate rock areas that are difficult to conduct chronology studies. In this study, three recrystallized carbonate samples were collected from the Napo-Ande Fault, Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, Southwest China, in order to investigate ESR signals that existed in this material and their suitability for dating. The results showed that: (1) ESR spectra of recrystallized carbonates generally display two signals at $g = 2.0006$ (h3) and $g = 2.0040$ (BL), no $g = 2.0057$ signal has been observed. (2) the $g = 2.0040$ (BL) signal seems unsuitable for dating because it leads to serving age overestimation. (3) $g = 2.0006$ (h3) is a suitable signal that can be used for dating purposes.

Keyword: ESR dating; recrystallized carbonates; carbonate rock area; fault movement

PP-08. Provenance analysis of muds with luminescence properties

Kento Yokoo^{1*}, Toru Tamura²

¹ Graduate School of Frontier Science, The University of Tokyo, Chiba, Japan

² Geological Survey of Japan, AIST, Ibaraki, Japan

*Corresponding Author e-mail: 1825721398@edu.k.u-tokyo.ac.jp

Sediment provenance provides important information for understanding earth surface processes and environmental changes. Methods for deciphering sediment provenance with luminescence properties of sediments have been attempted but remain largely unexplored (Sawakuchi et al., 2018; Mendes et al., 2019). Intensities and signal components of luminescence are known to vary depending on the source (Tokuyasu et al., 2010). A few studies show optically stimulated luminescence (OSL), infrared stimulated luminescence (IRSL), and thermoluminescence (TL) of fluvial sediments could be used as proxies of past precipitation changes. However, few cases have used luminescence properties of muds for quantitative provenance analyses.

We attempt to develop a new method for quantitatively determining the mixing ratio of sediment from multiple origins using OSL, IRSL, and TL of feldspar and quartz through experiments and the application to fluvial sediments. Fine grains (4–11 μm in diameter) of two geographically distant sources (Sendai Bay, Japan and the Mekong River floodplain, Cambodia) with different luminescence properties were artificially mixed in 10% increments, and their luminescence properties were quantified. Then we checked how clearly each of the luminescence properties reflect the mixing ratio. Here, the regenerated luminescence by c. 160 Gy dose was observed after bleaching the natural luminescence. Observed luminescence signals include IRSL at 125 °C of polymineral grains, OSL of quartz grains and thermoluminescence up to 260 °C of polymineral and quartz grains. For polymineral grains, IRSL intensities showed a relatively strong correlation with the mixing ratio for IRSL while less clear correlation was obtained for TL, and in both cases, there were large variations between aliquots from the same sample. In contrast, quartz showed a very strong correlation for both OSL and TL, and the inter-aliquot variations were relatively small. These results suggest that the quartz luminescence properties are more suitable at least for distinguishing two samples studied here. In addition, a very strong correlation was obtained between OSL and TL from quartz, which may be used for more complicated cases.

Keywords: luminescence intensity, OSL, IRSL, TL, mixing ratio, Sendai Bay, Mekong River

References

- [1] Sawakuchi, A. O., Jain, M., Mineli, T. D., Nogueira L., Bertassoli Jr., D. J., Häggi, C., Sawakuchi, H. O., Pupim, F. N., Grohmann, C. H., Chiessi, C. M., Zabel, M., Mulitza, S., Mazoca, C. E. M. and Cunha, D. F. (2018) Luminescence of quartz and feldspar fingerprints provenance and correlates with the source area denudation in the Amazon River basin. *Earth and planetary science letters* 492, 152–162.
- [2] Mendes, V. R., Sawakuchi, A. O., Chiessi, C. M., Giannini, P. C. F., Rehfeld, K., and Mulitza, S. (2019) Thermoluminescence and optically stimulated luminescence measured in marine sediments indicate precipitation changes over northeastern Brazil. *Paleoceanography and Paleoclimatology*, 34, 1476–1486.
- [3] Tokuyasu, K., Tanaka, K., Tsukamoto, S. and Murray, A. (2010) The Characteristics of OSL Signal from Quartz Grains Extracted from Modern Sediments in Japan. *Geochronometria*, 37, 13–19.

PP-09. Investigation on radiation-induced radicals in primary alkylamines in silica clathrates

Nobuyuki Tamai^{1*}, Shusuke Isogai², Yuka Yokoyama², Atsushi Tani^{2†}

¹ Faculty of Global Human Sciences, Kobe University

² Graduate School of Human Development and Environment, Kobe University

*Presenting Author: 1951020h@stu.kobe-u.ac.jp

†Corresponding Author: tani@carp.kobe-u.ac.jp

Chibaite is one of silica clathrates with SiO₂ cages. Hydrocarbon molecules such as methane, ethane, propane, and isobutane are enclathrated in the cages as guest molecules in naturally found chibaite (Momma et al., 2011). The clathrate structure is similar to that in gas hydrate structure II with H₂O framework. Chibaite was found in quartz veins in marine sediments of Early Miocene age (Hota Group) at Arakawa, Minami-boso City, Chiba Prefecture, Japan. It means that chibaite would be formed after sedimentation. At this moment, unfortunately, we do not know when and where chibaite was formed.

Gamma-irradiated clathrate hydrates have been investigated, revealing that radiation-induced radicals are relatively stable within the cages in comparison with the other matrices (e.g. Takeya et al., 2004). These studies in the hydrates suggest that the radicals in chibaite would be stable and could be used as a radiation-induced signal in ESR dating. Actually, tert-butyl radical in chibaite is stable up to 240 °C and the intensity increases linearly up to 400 Gy. These results indicate that tert-butyl radical is suitable for estimation of ESR age in chibaite (Isogai, 2022). However, it is difficult to understand the detailed thermal stability of the radicals of tert-butyl and the other radicals because natural chibaite contains various kind of gas molecules and the several ESR spectra due to the organic radicals are overlapped (Yokoyama et al., 2022). Another difficulty is to synthesize silica clathrate with a specific hydrocarbon molecule as a guest.

Fortunately, it was reported that primary alkylamine molecules were enclathrated as guest molecules in silica clathrates, one of which has the same silica structure as chibaite (Gunawardane et al., 1987). In this study, we have synthesized silica clathrates with methyl, ethyl, and isopropyl amines as guest molecules instead of ethane, propane, and isobutane, respectively. We will show the organic radicals in the synthetic silica clathrates after gamma irradiation and discuss the thermal stability of the radiation-induced radicals in silica clathrates.

Keywords: ESR, silica clathrate, organic radical, alkylamine, chibaite, synthesis

PP-10. Estimation of ESR age of chibaite using organic radicals

Shusuke Isogai^{1*}, Yuka Yokoyama¹, Kenta Kusuki¹, Hirotsugu Nishido², Atsushi Tani¹

¹Graduate School of Human Development and Environment, Kobe University

²Faculty of Biosphere-Geosphere Science, Okayama University of Science

*Presenting Author: 203d401d@stu.kobe-u.ac.jp

Silica clathrates have a SiO_2 framework structure of cage-like voids occupied by guest species such as hydrocarbons and a similar framework structure to those of gas hydrates which contain molecule compounds enclosed within cage-like structures of water molecules. Chibaite is a natural analogue of gas hydrate structure II and has larger cages than melanophlogite, isostructural to gas hydrate structure I. It suggests that the cages in chibaite store propane and isobutane together with methane and ethane as guest molecules. Chibaite was found in marine sediments of Early Miocene age (Hota Group) at Arakawa, Minami-boso City, Chiba Prefecture, Japan (Momma *et al.*, 2011). It occurs in quartz veins as euhedral ranging from a few mm to 1 cm thick in tuffaceous sandstone and mudstone. Although chibaite had crystallized after marine sedimentation, it is not clear when it formed. If organic radical species in silica clathrates are thermally stable in geological time scale, electron spin resonance (ESR) dating could be applied to evaluate the formation age. To obtain a reliable ESR age, it is necessary to assess a thermal stability of the radical species in chibaite. Our previous studies shows that methyl radical and *tert*-butyl radical are stored in the natural chibaite samples. The ESR signal intensity of *tert*-butyl radical in chibaite increased by gamma irradiation, whereas the intensity of methyl radical almost unchanged. In annealing experiments, *tert*-butyl radical is thermally as stable as the defects such as Al center and Ti center in quartz (Toyota and Ikeya, 1991). In this study, we have conducted to measure chibaite samples by ESR to investigate how the ESR signals of *tert*-butyl radical in chibaite respond to gamma-irradiation doses, and to estimate the ESR age of chibaite.

We gently crushed chibaite samples with a mortar into several particles about 2-3 mm in diameter, and evaluated the total radiation dose for two portions of the samples by additive dose method using gamma-rays from a source of ^{60}Co . ESR measurements were performed at room temperature.

The ESR signal intensity of *tert*-butyl radical of these samples increased linearly with gamma-rays irradiation up to 400 Gy. The equivalent dose was estimated to be 30 ± 8 Gy obtained by extrapolation method. Assuming the annual dose rate reported for various rocks in Japan (Matsuda and Minato, 1999), the ESR age of chibaite can be evaluated at 65 ± 17 ka. Based on the average uplift rate in the southern part of Boso peninsula (Nakata *et al.*, 1980; Kikuchi, 2001), the formation of chibaite could be calculated to be at around 130 m in burial depth. It is disagreed with the formation environment estimated by Momma *et al.* (2011). In this presentation, we will discuss the issues of underestimation of ESR age of chibaite.

Keywords: silica clathrate, chibaite, electron spin resonance, radical species, ESR dating

PP-11. Feldspar pIRIR dating for defining depositional sequences in an uplifted coast since the Middle Pleistocene, eastern Japan

Tamura T.^{1,2,3*}, Okazaki, H.⁴, Naya, T.¹, Nakashima, R.¹, Nakazato, H.⁵, Seike, K.¹, Okuno, J.⁶

¹ Geological Survey of Japan, AIST, Ibaraki, 305-8567, Japan

² Graduate School of Frontier Science, The University of Tokyo, Chiba, 277-8563, Japan

³ Institute for Space-Earth Environmental Research, Nagoya University, Aichi, 464-8601, Japan

⁴ Fukada Geological Institute, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo, 113-0021, Japan

⁵ Institute for Rural Engineering, NARO, Ibaraki, 305-8609, Japan

⁶ National Institute of Polar Research, Tokyo 190-8518, Japan

*Corresponding Author e-mail:

We present the application of post-infrared infrared stimulated luminescence (pIRIR) dating to a 35-m-long sediment core collected from the marine terrace in the Kanto plain, eastern Japan, and examine how effective its chronology is for identifying depositional sequences related to the relative sea-level fluctuations since the Middle Pleistocene [1]. The Kanto coastal plain is characterized by a unique tectonic setting near the triple junction of plate boundaries and extensive development of the Last Interglacial raised marine terrace in contrast to the longer-term subsidence trend. The sediment core was collected in the northeastern Kanto plain and shows a succession of seven facies units, A to G, in ascending order, representing shallow marine to shelf (units A to C), fluvial to brackish salt marsh (unit D), beach to shoreface (unit E), fluvial to aeolian (unit F), and loess (unit G) sedimentation. According to pretests, pIRIR at 225 °C after prior infrared stimulated luminescence at 50 °C was chosen as an optimal signal for dating. The pIRIR is characterized by modest anomalous fading. Fading-corrected pIRIR ages are consistent with the stratigraphy. Units A and B are dated as Marine Oxygen Isotope Stage (MIS) 7 and units C to F as MIS 5. However, uncertainties of individual age estimates do not allow further chronological correlation. Instead, using sea-level changes inferred from characteristic facies transitions as additional constraints, units C to F can be correlated to substages in MIS 5. Unit E represents coastal progradation during the MIS 5c sea-level highstand, which refines the date of the marine terrace around the core site as MIS 5c and revises up the rate of tectonic uplift accordingly. Our results exemplify a successful application of feldspar pIRIR dating for defining depositional sequences formed in relations to 100-kyr glacial cycles, in which with additional information of the sedimentary facies higher-frequency sequences may be defined.

Keywords: Last Interglacial period, optically stimulated luminescence, post-infrared infrared stimulated luminescence, sea-level changes, tectonics

References

[1] Tamura, T., Okazaki, H., Naya, T., Nakazato, H., Seike, K., Okuno, J. (2022) Luminescence chronology for identifying depositional sequences in an uplifted coast since the Middle Pleistocene, eastern Japan. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, in press.

PP-12. Cross-shore and longshore variations in residual doses of modern K-feldspar sands in the Kujukuri coast, central Japan

Kotaro Komori^{1*}, Koji Seike², Toru Tamura²

¹*Graduate School of Frontier Sciences, The University of Tokyo, Chiba, 277-8563, Japan*

²*Geological Survey of Japan, AIST, Ibaraki, 305-8567, Japan*

**Corresponding Author e-mail: 7142028052@edu.k.u-tokyo.ac.jp*

K-feldspar infrared stimulated luminescence (IRSL) and post-IR IRSL (pIRIR) signals complement quartz optically stimulated luminescence dating or are used for different applications. These signals are prone to the residual dose owing to incomplete bleaching. While the residual dose is a problem for accurate dating, it may also provide a clue to deciphering the sediment transport processes. This study characterizes the cross-shore and longshore variations of residual doses of IRSL and pIRIR from modern K-feldspar sands on the modern coastal dune, beach, shoreface, and shelf in the Kujukuri coast, and examines the sediment transport processes that the variations reveal. K-feldspar sands extracted from surface sediments were used for the measurements. IRSL signal at 50 °C and pIRIR signals at 150, 225 and 290 °C after prior IRSL at 50 °C from K-feldspar sand were obtained. In the coastal dune and beach, residual doses of IRSL at 50 °C before pIRIR at 150 °C was < 0.1 Gy, equivalent to several decades for the average dose rate in this region. Residual doses of pIRIR at 150 and 225 °C were < 0.8 and < 3 Gy, respectively, equivalent to < 400 and < 1500 years. Residual doses of pIRIR at 290 °C in the beach is characterized by a large range from 10 to 28 Gy, defining a downdrift decrease from the sea cliff (Byobugaura) on the north side, which is the main source of sand supply for the Kujukuri coast. A landward decrease in the residual dose of pIRIR at 290 °C is also identified in a distance 100–200 m from the beach to the coastal dune. These longshore and cross-shore variations are attributed to the sunlight exposure of sands during their transport by longshore currents and onshore wind. For offshore samples collected at water depths ranging from 5 to 70 m, residual doses of IRSL at 50 °C, pIRIR at 150 and 225 °C were < 0.2, < 2, and < 5 Gy, respectively, comparable to those from samples collected in the beach and coastal dune. Samples deeper than 70 m show slightly higher residual doses of these signals. pIRIR at 290 °C from offshore samples is characterized by large variations in the residual dose ranging from 8 to 35 Gy. The spatial variations of the residual doses obtained in this study are generally consistent with the prevailing direction of the sediment transport in the Kujukuri coast and, if defined in higher resolution, useful for characterizing the sediment transport of the entire coastal system.

Keywords: K-feldspar, infrared stimulated luminescence, post-infrared infrared stimulated luminescence, residual dose, coastal system

PP-13 Luminescence chronology of point bars and their utilisation in Past discharge estimation in the Southern West Bengal

Dr. Manoj Kumar Jaiswal

Inter-University Accelerator Centre (IUAC) New Delhi

Point bars are sinuous accretionary wedges of sand and finer sediments deposited by laterally migrating meandering rivers. They provide an excellent means to study past environments due to their ability to preserve the sedimentary structures corresponding to alteration in energy conditions. At the same, the dimension of the meander loops is directly proportional to the discharge of the river and the type of sediment load. The present work aims to study the point bars in Southern West Bengal to calculate the past river discharge and thus reconstruct the past climate. Luminescence dating is applied on the point bars to build the chronology. Field investigations and grain size analysis of point bar sediments supported by luminescence ages have shown point bars as a potential proxy for paleoflood and paleodischarge estimation. The study reveals that the region received good rainfall during reported periods of intense monsoon (Medieval Warm Period, Sub Altantic Period, Sub Boreal Period) and remained devoid of discharge during cold or dry events. (Little Ice Age) and 4.2 ka dry event (Meghalayan aridification).

PP-14. Interdisciplinary analysis of bricks from Royal Castle in Poznań (Poland)

Malgorzata Mrozek-Wysocka¹, Piotr Moska², Danuta Michalska¹

¹ Institute of Geology UAM, Poland

² Silesian University of Technology, Institute of Physics, Poland

On the basis of historical data and relative chronology it is estimated that the buildings and walls of the Royal Castle in Poznań were raised at the end of 13th cent. To verify the age of the first phases of castle erection the samples of bricks from the chronologically oldest part were taken for luminescence analyses. Dating were preceded by detailed material characterization. Different methods like macro- and microscopic observations using polarizing light microscopy and scanning electron microscopy with electron dispersive spectrometer (SEM-EDS), together with thermal analyses (DTA and TG), were applied. The collected bricks differ macroscopically. These differences are consistent with two different types of brick binding, Vendian and Gothic found in the castle walls.

For the luminescence dating 15 samples were collected. The OSL dating results were compared with the relative chronology.

Keywords: brick OSL, SEM-EDS of bricks, chronology of Royal castle in Poznań, bricks dating

PP-15. Kinetic analysis of the thermoluminescent glow curve of aquamarine (Be₃Al₂(SiO₃)₆)

Rafael Cogollo^{1*}, Jorge Herrera C¹, Omar D. Gutiérrez²

¹*Grupo de Materiales y Física Aplicada, Departamento de Física y Electrónica, Universidad de Córdoba, Carrera 6A #77-305, Montería, Colombia*

²*Grupo Alquimia, Facultad Ciencias Exactas y Aplicadas, Instituto Tecnológico Metropolitano, Calle 73 No 76A-354 Vía al Volador, Medellín, Colombia*

*Presenting Author: rafaelcogollo@gmail.com

Kinetic analysis of the thermoluminescent glow curve of aquamarine, cyan variety of beryl (Be₃Al₂(SiO₃)₆), is reported. Samples were irradiated at room temperature using a 90Sr/90Y β source at a rate of 0.10 Gy s⁻¹. Measurements made at 1°C/s after irradiation from 1 to 100 Gy show a main peak at 75°C followed by three secondary peaks at 113, 188 and 306°C respectively. The dose response of the main peak is linear within the first 10 Gy but tends towards sub-linearity as the dose is further extended to 100 Gy. The peak fades with the delay between irradiation and measurement about 14% of its initial value 600 s after irradiation. Reproducibility analysis shows that the material reproduces its response under identical experimental conditions with an uncertainty of 0.8% after 10 Gy beta dose irradiation. The kinetic analysis of the glow curve was carried out using the curve fitting method [1]. The results show that the main peak follows first order kinetics, its activation energy is of the order of 1 eV and the frequency factor is between 10¹² and 10¹⁴ s⁻¹, while some secondary peaks follow general order kinetics.

Keywords: Beryl, aquamarine, thermoluminescence, kinetic-analysis, dose-response, fading, reproducibility

References

[1] Pagonis. V, Kitis. G, Furetta. C. (2006). Numerical and practical exercises in thermoluminescence. 1st ed. Springer. New York, NY. <https://doi.org/10.1007/0-387-30090-2>

PP-16. Effective Mineral Extraction: A note on improving heavy liquid density separation during sample preparation in Trapped Charge Dating

Gloria I. López^{1,2,3*}

¹Colombian Geological Society, Mirador de Takay, Bogotá D.C., 111321, Colombia

²Recanati Institute for Maritime Studies RIMS, University of Haifa, Abba Khoushy Ave 199, Haifa, 3498838, Israel

³Geochronology & Nuclear Applications Group, Nuclear Affairs Directorate, Colombian Geological Survey, Diagonal 53 #34-53, Bogotá D.C., 111321, Colombia

*Presenting Author: lopezgi.phd@gmail.com lopezgi@sci.haifa.ac.il

Trapped Charge Dating methods, namely Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL) and Electron Spin Resonance (ESR), require the use of purified mineral separates for all their signal analyses procedures and dating measurements. The extraction of quartz (Qz) and its separation from feldspars (Flds) and all other accessory minerals involves the application of a suite of relatively simple yet precise physico-chemical treatments derived from long established mineralogical and sedimentological laboratory techniques.

Although the sample preparation process is pretty straightforward, the mineral isolation procedure may be more or less of a challenge depending on sediment/rock provenance, type of depositional environment, the target particle size, and the quality of the mineral fraction, but also and not less important, on the limitations and equipment and consumables existing in each laboratory facility. In our Scientific Community, the traditional and most commonly used technique to isolate Qz and Flds is undoubtedly standard density separation using heavy liquids such as Sodium (SPT) (and its variants) or Lithium (LST) Polytungstate. Other separation techniques have been long or recently proposed by some authors reporting good results but require specialised equipment or chemicals that are not necessarily common or affordable to all Trapped Charge Dating laboratories.

When separating Qz and Flds, a variety of density values and ranges are reported in the published literature. This comparative study found at least 10 different sets of densities, ranging from 2.50 to 2.75 g/cm³ (mostly using SPT) applied to isolate either Qz or Flds from samples collected from a variety of geographic locations and environments, with particle size fractions ranging from 63 to 250 µm, being 90-125 µm the most common one. Unfortunately, most authors in our Community publish minimal details when it comes to sample preparation procedures, often generalising them briefly, or even only mentioning 1-2 old, standard references. Sadly, poor physico-chemical treatment specifications are often the norm in published papers, posing an enormous challenge when it comes to improving or comparing laboratory sample treatment protocols.

A judicious analysis of these reported density ranges was done using 3 control samples: A) 90% Qz-rich; B) 90% Flds-rich; C) 50-50% mixture of A and B. The resulting separates (normalised by weight) were then compared to 3 other separates obtained using the new set of density values and separation steps proposed in this study: 1) If Qz is the focus mineral, use the following densities in this order 2.68, 2.58 g/cm³ (optional 2.76 g/cm³ if heavy mineral extraction is needed for other analyses); 2) If Flds are the goal, use 2.58, 2.76, 2.56 g/cm³. In all cases, either SPT or LST solutions should be newly mixed or super clean (ensuring at least triple filtering during recycling). With these 2 new protocols the target silicate family may be extracted, from the most commonly dated and best suited, to the least used or discarded sub-species: average Qz (density range: 2.53-2.68 g/cm³), α -Qz (2.62-2.65 g/cm³), K-Flds (density range: 2.50-2.58 g/cm³), Na-Flds (density range: 2.62-2.72 g/cm³), Na-Ca-Flds (2.64-2.76 g/cm³), Ca-Flds (2.75-2.76 g/cm³).

This experiment aims to provide a detailed examination of the various density range limits routinely used for mineral separation in our Scientific Community, assessing the suitability of a newly proposed variation to obtain cleaner and more abundant separates of the most suitable Qz & Flds grains used for dating. This new protocol has been effectively applied on a multitude of samples from both geological and archaeological contexts, from diverse regions of Europe, the Middle East, Asia, and South America, which have been successfully OSL- & ESR-dated since 2017. As a general remark, it is always important to understand in detail the geological context of the target deposit, in particular its mineralogy. As a Community, we should be more diligent in improving the various physico-chemical treatments used during laboratory sample preparation as many of the procedures some take for granted have not been tested in years.

Keywords OSL; ESR; mineral extraction; heavy liquids; laboratory preparation; sample care

PP-17. Thermoluminescence characterization of Cu or Ag doped Lithium Triborate

Lois Sevastidis^{1*}, S. Iflazoglu^{2,3}, P.G. Konstantinidis¹, A. Yilmaz², G. Kitis¹, G.S. Polymeris⁴

¹ Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Physics Department, Nuclear Physics and Elementary Particles Physics Section, 54124-Thessaloniki, Greece

² Middle East Technical University, Department of Chemistry, 06800, Ankara, Turkey

² TUBITAK Space Technologies Research Institute, 06800, Ankara, Turkey

³ NCSR "Demokritos", Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, Ag. Paraskevi, 15310 Athens, Greece

* Presenting Author: isevasti@auth.gr

Lithium Triborate (LiB_3O_5 or LTB thereafter), doped with Al, was very early suggested as a thermoluminescent dosimeter of ionizing radiation and X-rays (Ogorodnikov et al., 1996). LTB belongs to the same family as Lithium ($\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$) and Magnesium (MgB_4O_7) Tetraborates, which were extensively studied for dosimetric applications. LTB is characterized by chemical stability and good mechanical properties, and it has an effective atomic number ($Z_{\text{eff}}=7.39$) close to that of the human tissue ($Z_{\text{eff}}=7.42$), making it a potential dosimeter. Despite the initial promising results, the idea of using LTB for dosimetric applications was abandoned. So, the luminescence community knows very few things regarding the sensitivity of the material, the glow curve and minimum detectable dose, as well as the linearity features of the corresponding dose response (Depci et al., 2008; Pekpak et al., 2010). The objective of this research is to examine the Thermoluminescence (TL hereafter) features and dosimetric characteristics of either Cu-doped or Ag-doped LTB. The material was synthesized using the solid state technique and four different dopant levels were used for each element (0.1%, 0.5%, 1%, 3%); various techniques such as X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) were used for structural and compositional characterization, for samples annealed at 500 °C for 1 hour in all cases. The irradiations were accomplished via a $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ beta source with a dose rate of 0.53 Gy/min and all TL measurements were carried out using a Harshaw-3500 TLD Reader in a nitrogen atmosphere with a low constant heating rate of 2 °C/s. Specific TL features were studied, such as TL glow curve shape, sensitivity, and sensitization, as well as kinetic characterization using three supplementary techniques, namely peak shape methods, fractional glow technique and deconvolution analysis. Furthermore, the samples were irradiated at different doses, ranging from 0.53 to 2000 Gy, in order to study the corresponding dose response. For the main dosimetric TL peak, a linear dose response that was yielded, throughout the entire dose response region, suggests that the specific material could be effectively used for dosimetric applications for doses higher than 1 Gy.

Keywords: Lithium Triborate; Thermoluminescence; Dosimetry; Characterization;

References

- [1] I.N. Ogorodnikov, V.I. Kirpa, A.V. Kruzhalov, A.V. Porotnikov, 1996, Thermostimulated Luminescent Emission of Electrons and Photons in Non-Linear crystals LiB_3O_5 , Technical Physics Journal, 1997, Vol. 67, Number 7, Ural Technical University, 620002, Ekaterinburg.
- [2] E. Pekpak, A. Yilmaz, G. Özbayoglu, 2010, An Overview on Preparation and TL Characterization of Lithium Borates for Dosimetric Use, The Open Mineral Processing Journal, 2010, 3, 14-24.
- [3] T. Depci., G. Özbayoglu, A. Yilmaz., A.N. Yazici, 2008. The thermoluminescent properties of lithium triborate (LiB_3O_5) activated by aluminium. NIM B 266(5), 755 – 762.

PP-18.Late Quaternary evolution of the Belan River Basin, Central India

S. Singh^{1,2*}, Mahadev¹, B. Narzary¹, V. Shivsagar¹, M.K. Jaiswal¹, P. Singh³

¹ Department of Earth Sciences, Indian Institute of Science Education and Research (IISER) Kolkata, Mohanpur, Nadia, West Bengal, India.

² Department of Geology, Institute of Earth and Environmental Sciences, Dr. Rammanohar Lohia Avadh University, Ayodhya, Uttar Pradesh, India.

³Department of Geology, Institute of Science, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, India.

The Marginal Gangetic Plain is the southernmost segment of the Ganga Plain, formed by Himalayan Orogen thrust fold stress flexing the Indian lithosphere. Rivers originating in the Himalayas have received much attention (i.e., Ganga, Yamuna, Kosi, Ghagra, etc.). In contrast, the tributaries draining from the peripheral bulge of the foreland basin have not been studied in detail, and it encloses seismic activity in the basement of the craton. Belan River drains through the Marginal Gangetic Plain. Various tectonic-induced geomorphic signatures have been identified using Landsat Images, such as fluvial incision, river shifting, gorges channel formation, etc., in the Belan river basin. Geomorphic indices of active tectonics (asymmetry factor, SL index, basin elongation ratio, and long profile), drainage pattern, and lineament study have been performed for the basin. These parameters indicate slope adjustment due to uplift and subsidence of the parts of the basin areas. These observations are inferred from the tectonic exhumation of the southern and south-eastern parts of the Belan river Basin. The most recent and extensive valley fills started accumulating at $\sim 51 \pm 7$ ka and persisted until around $\sim 22 \pm 2$ ka. The aggradation was accompanied by a weakening summer monsoon, followed by incision after 22 ± 2 ka, indicating a return to warmer and wetter conditions and a stronger summer monsoon after LGM.

Keywords: Marginal Gangetic Plain; Belan River; Morphotectonic; Geomorphic indices.

PP-19.Secondary electron equilibrium revisited: when doses are given by photons

Shin Toyoda^{1*}, Ulku Sayin², Emel Ece³, Naoya Obata⁴

¹ *Institute of Palaeontology and Geochronology, Okayama University of Science, Okayama, Japan*

² *Department of Physics, Selcuk University, Konya, Turkey*

³ *Department of Physics, Karamanoglu Mehmetbey University, Karaman, Turkey*

³ *Graduate School of Science, Okayama University of Science, Okayama, Japan*

**Corresponding Author e-mail: toyoda@ous.ac.jp*

In the experimental procedures of ESR and luminescence dating, doses may be given by gamma rays. In such cases, it is well known that some materials have to be placed both in front and behind the samples in order to have secondary electron equilibrium ('build up') [1]. This is because the secondary electrons induced by photons give the effect of ionization (creating electron and hole pairs to be trapped in the samples subject to dating) but photons directly do not. Therefore, some materials which induces secondary electrons are needed to be placed both in front and behind.

The present study investigated what material is appropriate to sandwich the samples for dating (and also dosimetry) in order to have this secondary electron equilibrium. The amount of induced secondary electrons should be proportional to mass-energy absorption coefficient, μ_m , of the material. Therefore, in theory, the sandwiching material should be the same (having the same atomic number) as the sample. In the present study, we examined the cases of tooth enamel, alanine, and barite, sandwiched by nothing (air), PMMA (plastics), aluminium, glass, apatite and barite. The samples were irradiated by ⁶⁰Co gamma rays at Takasaki Research Institute of National Institutes for Quantum Science and Technology to doses of 2 or 1 kGy.

The ESR signals were observed by an electron spin resonance spectrometer, JEOL PX-2300 at Okayama University of Science. The intensities of the signals used for dating and dosimetry were examined and compared. The difference in signal intensities were observed depending of the sandwiching material. The signal intensities in tooth enamel in the samples sandwiched by PMMA are larger than those by apatite, glass, and aluminium, which are consistent with the values of mass-energy absorption coefficient, μ_m , of the materials [2] while those with nothing (air) showed the highest values, which are contrary to the impression given by a textbook [1]. Anyway, the present results confirm that we have to be cautious about secondary electron equilibrium ('build up') and therefore about the sandwiching material at the time of gamma ray irradiation.

Keywords: secondary electron equilibrium, gamma ray irradiation, mass energy absorption coefficient

References

- [1] Aitken, M. J. (1998) An Introduction to Optical Dating, p.49.
- [2] Ikeya, M. (1993) New Applications of electron spin resonance, Dating, dosimetry and microscopy, p.107.

PP-20. Optical bleaching and thermal annealing of the ESR signals in quartz

Naoya Obata^{1*}, Shin Toyoda²

¹ Graduate School of Science, Okayama University of Science, Okayama, Japan

² Institute of Palaeontology and Geochronology, Okayama University of Science, Okayama, Japan

*Corresponding Author e-mail: s20rd01on@ous.jp

Electron spin resonance (ESR) dating with quartz is one of the methods applied to sediments as useful as optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating, where it is assumed that exposure to sunlight erases the dating signals. ESR method has an advantage that it can be applied to samples with older ages than OSL method, but on the other hand, the dating signals bleach harder than OSL signals. The latter bleach in several ten seconds to several hours at longest while ESR signals take several hundred hours, implying that the residual signal intensity can be significant. It is known that the Al center (a hole trapped at an Al ion replacing silicon in quartz) has two components, bleachable and unbleachable, where the former has to be subtracted to estimate the ages. However, the thermal stabilities of these components were not well investigated.

In the present paper, the characteristics of ESR dating signals are systematically investigated. Quartz grains (100-200 μm) extracted from fluvial sediments (Brisbane river, Australia) were used. The natural quartz (no heating) and those annealing (heated at 400°C for 1 hour) or bleaching were irradiated to 1 kGy and 5 kGy by ⁶⁰Co gamma rays, and those were bleached by solar simulator SERIC SOLAX-500W. The stepwise heating experiment was made between 100 and 480°C for 15 minutes. ESR signals (Al, Ti-Li, Ti-H centers) were measured by JEOL JES-PX2300 X-band spectrometer equipped with a temperature control device, ES-CT-470, with liquid nitrogen.

The results of stepwise heating experiment indicate (1) the unbleachable signal of the Al center is thermal more stable than the bleachable component, (2) the sensitivity of Ti center does not change by thermal annealing nor optical bleaching, (3) the Ti center increases due to thermal transfer.

Our results suggest that the optical bleaching of the Al center can be replaced by heating, and that the Ti center can also reset by heating as well as bleaching when the equivalent dose is estimated.

Keywords: ESR, quartz, thermal stability, sediments, bleach

PP-21. Late Quaternary evolution of alluvial fans in Northern Tripura, India

Ria Kar^{1*}, Manoj K. Jaiswal²

¹ Department of Earth Sciences, Indian Institute of Science and Research Kolkata, India

² Department of Earth Sciences, Indian Institute of Science and Research Kolkata, India

*Corresponding Author e-mail: rk21rs016@iiserkol.ac.in

The Himalayas is a southward migrating fold-and-thrust Belt formed by the collision between the Indian and Eurasian plates. This belt has been demarcated by different northerly dipping thrusts. The main frontal thrust (MFT) is considered as most active thrust and is marked as mountain front. Alluvial fans are unconsolidated sedimentary deposits at a mountain front and act as important geomorphic archives for paleoseismic and past climate reconstructions. The present study is an attempt to understand the depositional history of alluvial fans in northern Tripura which is situated at the eastern margin of the Bengal basin and at the mountain front of the Indo-Burma ranges in the Eastern Himalayas. Tripura owes its origin to the collision between the Indian, Eurasian and Burmese plates forming the extensive Himalayan and Indo-Burmese ranges and previous geomorphic studies suggest that this area represents typical ridge-and-valley structural provinces where the structural complexity increases from west to east. The rivers of Tripura are mostly northerly flowing across the intermontane valleys, joining the rivers of Bangladesh. The southwest monsoonal winds also pass over Tripura and probably influenced the evolution of the fan system. However, despite its strategic position, Quaternary deposits in Tripura are studied in less detail. We use geomorphic and luminescence dating techniques to understand the depositional and geochronological history of the alluvial fans and the role of climate. Preliminary luminescence data suggests that the fluvial sediments in these study areas were deposited around 80, 69-65 Ka during the late Pleistocene Epoch. Additionally, it corresponds with the MIS 5 in the global scenario suggesting warmer phases that prevailed over the Northern Hemisphere.

Keywords: Luminescence dating, North-East India, Himalayas, Alluvial fan

References

- [1] Aitken, M.J., 1998. An Introduction to Optical Dating, Academic Press, Oxford University 359 Press, Oxford, U.K.
- [2] Singh, A. K., Jaiswal, M. K., Pattanaik, J. K., & Dev, M. (2016). Luminescence chronology of alluvial fan in North Bengal, India: Implications to tectonics and climate. *Geochronometria*, 43(1), 102-112.
- [3] Nandy, D. R., Dasgupta, S., Sarkar, K., & Ganguly, A. (1983). Tectonic evolution of Tripura- Mizoram fold belt. *Surma Basin, Northeast India. Quart. Jour. Geol. Min. Met. Soc. India*, 55(4), 186-194.

PP-22. Luminescence dating of neotectonic activity on the foothills of the Assam-Bhutan Himalaya, India

Belligraham Narzary¹, Saurabh Singh², Manoj Jaiswal¹, Vibhuti Shivsagar¹, Mahadev Rawat³, Atul Singh³

¹ *Department of Earth Sciences, Indian Institute of Science Education and Research (IISER), India*

² *Department of Geology, Institute of Earth and Environmental Sciences, Dr. Rammanohar Lohia Avadh University, Ayodhya, Uttar Pradesh, India*

³ *Inter-University Accelerator Centre, New Delhi, India*

The present study aims to understand the evolution of alluvial fan deposits in the foothills of Assam-Bhutan Himalaya in the Kokrajhar district of Assam. The study is mainly focused on the uplifted 30 km long fluvial deposition from the Pinkhua Khola River in the west and Leu Pani in the east. The study is important because it will help understand the southward propagation of the Himalayan fold and thrust belt. A 30 km long active, east-west trending, south-dipping Frontal Back Thrust (FBT) has been documented as the cause for the uplift, which is well within the south of the Main Frontal Thrust (MFT). The 30 km uplifted belt has been dissected by multiple south-flowing rivers forming six distinct geomorphic blocks of 5 to 8 km wide. Multiple layer clay deposits characterise the entire belt due to the blockade of the south-flowing rivers due to the episodic upliftment caused by the FTB. Dating these clay layers helped us reconstruct the neo-tectonics movements during the Late Quaternary. Three such activities have been identified based on field investigations and OSL dating. The luminescence age of the clay deposit suggests that the FTB was activated at ~45 ka and experienced two other phases of deformation at ~27 ka and ~12 ka.

Keywords: Luminescence Dating, Assam-Bhutan Himalayan Foothills, Backthrust

PP-23. Kinetic analysis of the glow curve of α -Al₂O₃

Rafael Cogollo Pitalua^{1*}, Yulissa Espitia¹, Omar D. Gutiérrez²

¹ Grupo de Materiales y Física Aplicada, Departamento de Física y Electrónica, Universidad de Córdoba, Carrera 6A #77-305, Montería, Colombia

² Grupo de Química Básica, Aplicada y Ambiente, Facultad de Ciencias Exactas y Aplicadas, Instituto Tecnológico Metropolitano, Calle 73 No. 76^a-354, Medellín 050034, Colombia

*Presenting Author: rafaelcogollop@gmail.com

In this work, the kinetic parameters of the main thermoluminescence (TL) peak of pure alumina (α -Al₂O₃) samples irradiated at 1 Gy is reported. The pellets were irradiated using a 6 MeV linear accelerator (LINAC), in air at room temperature, located at the Instituto Medico de Alta Tecnología (IMAT) in Montería city. The TL reading of the samples was performed on a Bicron® TLD 4500 system. The Initial Rise (IR), Peak shape (PS), Whole glow peak (WGP) and Curve fitting (CF) methods were used to carry out a detailed kinetic analysis. Analysis of the TL shows four glow peaks at 162.5, 265.9, 338.7 and 407.7 °C with activation energies of 1.14, 1.26, 1.98 and 1.40 eV respectively, being the recombination processes the main deactivation path. Dosimetric properties such as dose response and reproducibility are also reported.

Keywords: Al₂O₃; thermoluminescence; kinetic-parameters; dose-response; reproducibility

PP-24. Fitting supralinear dose responses using non-empirical expressions; optimization using two computing environments

Konstantina Prevezanou^{1*}, G. Kioselaki¹, P.G. Konstantinidis¹, E. Tsoutsoumanos^{2,3}, G.S. Polymeris³, V. Pagonis⁴, G. Kitis¹

¹ Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Physics Department, Nuclear Physics and Elementary Particles Physics Section, 54124-Thessaloniki, Greece

² Condensed Matter Physics Laboratory, Physics Department, University of Thessaly, GR-35100, Lamia, Greece

³ NCSR "Demokritos", Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology Demokritos, Ag. Paraskevi, 15310 Athens, Greece

⁴ Physics Department, McDaniel College, Westminster, MD 21157, USA

*Corresponding Author e-mail: kpreveza@physics.auth.gr

The response as a function of radiation dose is the fundamental experimental result in all applications of Thermoluminescence (TL) and Optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) as well as in dosimetry using electron spin resonance (ESR). The TL/OSL dose response is generally straightforward albeit non-linear, with linear dependence, if present, being restricted to relatively narrow dose regions, depending on the material. A linear dose response is an empirical relationship that has been highly preferable, especially in cases of TL, as it makes the calibration of TL and OSL dosimeters simple and accurate. In contrast, a non-linear behaviour, namely saturating exponential, although being still an empirical equation too, could be an obstacle in applications where high doses are involved. So, in either case an empirical dose response relationship has been traditionally used.

Recently, implementation of analytical expressions derived from theoretical processes that describe TL, OSL dose response and other phenomena, according to phenomenological physical models, has been an attractive research topic. Based on the Lambert W function, Pagonis *et al.* (2020a, 2020b) formulated two analytical solutions of the irradiation stage, by numerically integrating the differential equations of one trap one recombination (OTOR) and two trap one recombination (TTOR) centre models. Also, Pagonis *et al.* (2020b) used the already known supralinearity index $f(D)$ in order to fit a large number of different experimental TL and OSL dose response curves in both models.

Following the pioneer works of Konstantinidis *et al.* (2022) and Prevezanou *et al.* (2022), the present study focuses on the two aforementioned analytical expressions and their implementation in two different computing environments; the cases of Excel and Python. For each one, three different analysis routines were created for each model to fit the dose response curves, a) one using the first analytical solution of the irradiation stage ($I(D)$), b) one utilizing the supralinearity index ($f(D)$) and c) the last one which fits both simultaneously. In all cases, the fittings were considered as highly preferable, with the parameters exhibiting small differentiation between the two computing environments. Finally, it should be mentioned that simultaneous fitting had a strong impact on fitting optimization, as it allows the value consistency of the parameters that had been occurred from the other two separate processes.

Keywords: Lambert W, OTOR, TTOR, Dose response, Supralinearity index, Python

References

- [1] Pagonis, V., Kitis, G., Chen, R., 2020a. A new analytical equation for the dose response of dosimetric materials, based on the Lambert W function. *J. Lumin.* 225, 117333.
- [2] Pagonis, V., Kitis, G., Chen, R., 2020b. Superlinearity revisited: a new analytical equation for the dose response of defects in solids, using the Lambert W function. *J. Lumin.* 117553.
- [3] P., Konstantinidis, Kioumourtzoglou, S., Polymeris, G. S., & Kitis, G. (2021). Stimulated luminescence: Analysis of complex signals and fitting of dose response curves using analytical expressions based on the Lambert W function implemented in a commercial spreadsheet. *App. Rad. and Iso.*, 176, 109870.
- [4] K., Prevezanou, G., Kioselaki, E., Tsoutsoumanos, P.G., Konstantinidis, G.S., Polymeris, V., Pagonis, G., Kitis, 2022. Implementation of expressions using Python in stimulated luminescence analysis, *Radiation Measurements*, 154, 106772.

PP-25. Python in stimulated luminescence: a further step in dose response fitting

Georgia Kioselaki^{1,*}, K. Prevezanou¹, P.G. Konstantinidis¹, E. Tsoutsoumanos^{2,3}, G.S. Polymeris³, G. Kitis¹, V. Pagonis⁴

¹ Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Physics Department, Nuclear Physics and Elementary Particles Physics Section, 54124-Thessaloniki, Greece

² Condensed Matter Physics Laboratory, Physics Department, University of Thessaly, GR-35100, Lamia, Greece

³ NCSR "Demokritos", Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology Demokritos, Ag. Paraskevi, 15310 Athens, Greece

⁴ Physics Department, McDaniel College, Westminster, MD 21157, USA

*Corresponding Author e-mail: georgiakioselaki8@gmail.com

Recently, Pagonis et al. (2020a, 2020b) formulated two analytical expressions derived from the phenomenological models of Stimulated Luminescence, specifically the one trap one recombination (OTOR) and two trap one recombination (TTOR) centre models. Also, by utilizing the supralinearity index ($f(D)$) in both cases, they managed to accurately fit a plethora of TL/OSL dose response curves (Pagonis et al., 2020b). Moreover, a new, flexible and versatile approach for mathematical formulation of stimulated luminescence phenomena was presented by Prevezanou *et al.* (2022). This approach includes the use of the Lambert W function in a computing environment developed in Python programming language, for both cases of deconvolution analysis of stimulated luminescence signals (TL, CW-OSL, LM-OSL curves) as well as for fitting dose response curves using non-empirical models. For the case of dose response fitting analysis, this approach enables the easy application of non-empirical models towards increasing the accuracy of ages within the region of saturation; this increase in the precision is feasible as the use of Lambert W function will decrease substantially the error of the equivalent dose calculation within the saturation region.

The present study follows on directly from this latter aforementioned publication, which ends by questioning whether simultaneous fittings of both dose response and the supralinearity index $f(D)$ might result in better understanding of the competition effects and the non-linear effects. The script code that describes this simultaneous fitting is presented, along with a mathematical expression for $f(D)$ which utilizes Lambert W function. This mathematical expression was derived for both OTOR and TTOR models. Fitting examples will be presented. Finally, another aim of this work is the implementation of Lambert W function in routine equivalent dose estimations, using the corrected OSL dose response curves of the highly applied Single Aliquot Regenerative (SAR) dose protocol (Murray & Wintle, 2000).

Keywords: Lambert W, OTOR, TTOR, Dose response, Supralinearity index, Python

References

- [1] Pagonis, V., Kitis, G., Chen, R., 2020a. A new analytical equation for the dose response of dosimetric materials, based on the Lambert W function. *J. Lumin.* 225, 117333.
- [2] Pagonis, V., Kitis, G., Chen, R., 2020b. Superlinearity revisited: a new analytical equation for the dose response of defects in solids, using the Lambert W function. *J. Lumin.* 117553.
- [3] Konstantinidis, P., Kioumourtzoglou, S., Polymeris, G. S., & Kitis, G. (2021). Stimulated luminescence: Analysis of complex signals and fitting of dose response curves using analytical expressions based on the Lambert W function implemented in a commercial spreadsheet. *App. Rad. and Iso.*, 176, 109870.
- [4] Prevezanou, K., Kioselaki, G., Tsoutsoumanos, E., Konstantinidis, P.G., Polymeris, G.S., Pagonis, V., Kitis, G., 2022. Implementation of expressions using Python in stimulated luminescence analysis, *Radiation Measurements*, 154, 106772.
- [5] Murray, A.S., Wintle, A.G., 2000. Luminescence dating of quartz using an improved single – aliquot regenerative – dose protocol. *Radiation Measurements* 32, 57–73.

PP-26. Simulation study of a nanomaterial interacting with ionizing radiation using OTOR and IMTS for different grain sizes

Efstathios Tsoutsoumanos^{1,2,*}, T. Karakasidis¹, P.G. Konstantinidis³, G.S. Polymeris², V. Pagonis⁴, G. Kitis³

¹ Condensed Matter Physics Laboratory, Physics Department, University of Thessaly, GR-35100, Lamia, Greece

² Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, NCSR "Demokritos", GR-15310, Ag. Paraskevi (Athens), Greece

³ Nuclear and Elementary Particle Physics Laboratory, Physics Department, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, GR-54214, Thessaloniki, Greece

⁴ McDaniel College, Physics Department, MD-21157, Westminster, USA

*Corresponding Author e-mail: etsoutsoum@uth.gr | e.tsoutsoumanos@inn.demokritos.gr

The experimental study of Thermoluminescence (TL) signals from nanostructured materials, especially for cases concerning different production techniques, has been a subject on a number of studies mostly for applications concerning radiation dosimetry, due to the linear response that nanodosimeters exhibit on high doses [1-3]. In the majority of those works a possible correlation between the nanocrystal size and the form, along with the magnitude of TL signal has been observed and stated but were not extensively investigated. Despite the fact that various studies made an effort to provide scientific explanations for such connections, the underlying physical mechanisms are not fully known.

This work attempts a thorough and extensive investigation on the physical mechanisms of a nanomaterial interacting with radiation through simulations. All simulations were conducted in Python and the theoretical luminescence signals were derived by numerically integrating the One Trap – One Recombination (OTOR) center, and the Interactive Multi-Trap System (IMTS), that are the two main mathematical models for describing Stimulated Luminescence. The present study aiming to simulate a theoretical material that has a pre-determined number of electrons and available traps, where these values were chosen similarly to actual values of real materials (metal oxides), such as the unit cell volume of the crystal lattice and the number of electrons capable to be trapped on the available positions. By setting these initial conditions accordingly, a nanomaterial of a given volume can be represented along with its number of electrons and available traps for different grain size fractions, by decreasing the diameter of the sphere from micro- to nano-scale. Furthermore, nanomaterial TL signals were compared with the TL signals of a theoretical bulk material where the latter is exposed to low radiation doses (low dose rate). In this case the same number of electrons can be theoretically studied in instances where there is a surplus in the available positions. Finally, the contribution of re-trapping and recombination probabilities values were also investigated [4]. The theoretical results were compared with experimental results of actual nanodosimeters and discussed furtherly.

References

- [1] Altunal, V., Yegingil, Z., Tuken, T., Depci, T., Ozdemir, A., Guckan, V., Bulur, E. (2018). Optically stimulated luminescence characteristics of BeO nanoparticles synthesized by sol-gel method. *Radiation Measurements*. doi:10.1016/j.radmeas.2018.08.009
- [2] Salah, N., Sahare, P. D., Lochab, S. P., & Kumar, P. (2006). TL and PL studies on CaSO₄: Dy nanoparticles. *Radiation Measurements*, 41(1), 40–47. doi:10.1016/j.radmeas.2005.07.026
- [3] Salah, N., Sahare, P. D., & Rupasov, A. A. (2007). Thermoluminescence of nanocrystalline LiF:Mg,Cu,P. *Journal of Luminescence*, 124(2), 357–364. doi:10.1016/j.jlumin.2006.04.004
- [4] Tsoutsoumanos, E., Konstantinidis, P.G., Polymeris, G.S., Karakasidis, T., Kitis, G. (2022). Electron trap filling and emptying through simulations: Studying the shift of the maximum intensity position in Thermoluminescence and Linearly Modulated Optically Stimulated Luminescence curves. *Radiation Measurements*, 153, 106735 doi: 10.1016/j.radmeas.2022.106735.

PP-27. Characterisation of grain extractions from Brazilian sand sediments using FT-IR, XRD, SEM/EDS, and ESR Methods

Rogério Baria^{1*}, Shigueo, W.¹ Chubaci, J. F. D.², Cano, N.³, Gennari, R. F.²

¹ Nuclear and Energy Research Institute, University of São Paulo, São Paulo, Brazil,

² Institute of Physics, University of São Paulo, São Paulo, Brazil,

³ Institute of Marine Sciences, Federal University of São Paulo, Santos, Brazil.

*Corresponding Author e-mail: rogeriobr@usp.br

Scientists have tried to develop a global chronology to understand the formation of coastal areas and rivers. Only after the Second World War did advances in physics and chemistry lay the foundations for an absolute chronology. There are many age collection methods, and electron spin resonance (ESR) is already well known. However, ESR dating presents many methodological problems. This paper proposes characterising grain samples using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), X-ray diffraction spectroscopy (XRD), Rietveld refinement, scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive spectroscopy (SEM/EDS), electron spin resonance (ESR) methods and the grains chemical treatment.

The sample was collected from the marine terrace located on São Paulo State (Brazil) coast. The chemical extraction using H₂O₂, HF, and HCl removes the particles from sediment samples. The entire treatment and ESR analysis were carried out in dark rooms under red and orange light. After the grains' physical and chemical characterisation, additional treatment with an ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid solution (EDTA), concentration 10⁻³ molar and pH 10, was applied to remove the chemical impurities from the grain surface. Subsequently, the ESR method was used to identify paramagnetic defects. An attempt to determine the paleodose was using the E'1 paramagnetic centre.

The results presented by the FT-IR, XRD, Rietveld refinement, and SEM/EDS methods demonstrated that the grains extracted from the sediment are formed mainly by titanite (97%), followed by quartz (2.7%) and other minerals (0.3%). Paramagnetic defects E'1, oxygen (OHC), iron (Fe³⁺), and vanadyl (VO²⁺) were placed. The titanium (Ti) and aluminium (Al) centres were not confirmed. The characterisation results by FT-IR, XRD, Rietveld refinement, and SEM/EDS techniques showed that all ESR would be dating. The paleodose results obtained from the paramagnetic centre E'1 are saturated. Consequently, the paleodose of titanite grains can systematically underestimate age.

Therefore, the characterisation and chemical treatments proposed for grains have proved helpful in understanding and improving the luminescence dating procedures.

Keywords: Characterisation, Dating, Extraction, Sediment, FT-IR, XRD, SEM/EDS and ESR.

PP-28. Quartz OSL dating of loess deposits from the eastern margin of the Tibetan Plateau

Shengli Yang^{1*}, Li Liu¹, Xiaojing Liu¹, Pushuang Li¹, Qiong Li¹

¹ *Key Laboratory of Western China's Environmental Systems (Ministry of Education), College of Earth and Environmental Sciences, Lanzhou University, Lanzhou, China*

**Corresponding Author e-mail: shlyang@lzu.edu.cn (S. Yang)*

Loess sequences in the eastern Tibetan Plateau (ETP) are valuable paleoenvironmental archives for reconstructing the environmental history. The lack of detailed dating results limits the scope for understanding and interpreting the aeolian dust history and paleoenvironmental implications around the Tibetan Plateau. In this study, we conducted detailed optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) analysis on two typical loess sequences, named the Wenchuan (WCH) section and Zhouqu (ZQ) section, located on high terraces in the ETP. Our results show that: 1) The quartz OSL signals of the loess at the eastern Tibetan Plateau are dominated by the fast component with good performance for De measurements by single aliquot regenerative dose protocol. 2) The bottom ages of the studied loess sequences are ~60 ka, indicating an important dust event in the ETP. 3) The mass accumulation rate (MAR) significantly varied during the last glacial period. The MAR in MIS 3 was the relatively high, and four enhanced dust events were superimposed on the long-term changes in MAR records. The discrepancy in the MARs of the ETP loess since the last glacial period compared with that of the Chinese Loess Plateau may imply different dust deposition processes in the Tibetan Plateau.

Keywords: Quartz OSL, loess, dust history, mass accumulation rate

References

- [1] Yang, S.L., Liu, N., Li, D., Cheng, T., Liu, W., Li, S., Chen, H., Liu, L., Luo, Y., 2021. Quartz OSL chronology of the loess deposits in the Western Qinling Mountains, China, and their palaeoenvironmental implications since the Last Glacial period. *Boreas* 50, 294-307.
- [2] Liu, L., Yang, S.L., Cheng, T., Liu, X., Luo, Y., Liu, N., Chen, H., Chen, Z., Li, P., Liu, W., 2021. Chronology and dust mass accumulation history of the Wenchuan loess on eastern Tibetan Plateau since the last glacial. *Aeolian Research* 53, 100748.

PP-29. New insights on ESR dating of siliceous sinter and travertine outcrops on Tibet Plateau and its information for geothermal history

Sheng Wang^{1,2,3}, Tongyan Lü^{2,3*}, Zhonghai Wu^{2,3}

¹ Department of Geography and Spatial Information Techniques, Ningbo University, Ningbo 315211;

² Institute of Geomechanics, Chinese Academy of Geological Sciences, Beijing 100081;

³ Key Laboratory of Active Tectonics and Geological Safety, Ministry of Natural Resources, Beijing 100081

Siliceous sinter and travertine are the products of hydrothermal activity under the influence of regional tectonic movement. Under the influence of tectonic activities, a series of north-south hydrothermal belts have formed on Tibet Plateau and have led to several periods of siliceous sinter and travertine outcrops along the hydrothermal zone. How to date these outcrops accurately is still an important and hot issue. ESR dating is an important method for obtaining these outcrops ages. Compared with the application of ESR dating of deposition in hot spring on Central and southern Tibet Plateau, few work discussed the ESR dating method itself. In this study, we focus on the ESR spectrums, the thermal stability of ESR centers, and the influence of irradiation in order to improve the reliability of ESR dating. At last, our results indicate that: 1) The ESR spectrum of the travertine contains the signal at $g=2.0034$ which is regarded as a relative stable and effective ESR dating signal. It can be used for a dating attempt. 2) Higher irradiation has limited influence on ESR dating for our samples. 3) The pretreatment process in ESR dating could improve to reduce the influence of surrounding rock on the accurate determination of the age of Tibetan siliceous sinter. The dating results show that the Xikangjian travertine were formed in 36-290 ka, and the hydrothermal activity in West Tibet is a part of the overall hydrothermal activity in Tibet.

Keywords: ESR dating; siliceous sinter; travertine; tectonic; geothermal history

Online Conference

6th Asia-Pacific Conference on Luminescence
and Electron Spin Resonance Dating
26-28 September 2022, Ankara, Türkiye, Online